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**PRIORITY DIRECTIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT
OF SCIENCE AND EDUCATION**

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**“PRIORITY DIRECTIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF
SCIENCE AND EDUCATION”**

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Austin, USA

Modern Science and Innovations

This study aims to determine the importance of science education, to present a brief historical development of science education and to analyse which factors are effective for its development. Science education is the teaching and learning of science to non-scientists, such as school children, college students, or adults within the general public. The field of science education includes work in science content, science process (the scientific method), some social science, and some teaching pedagogy.

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SOCIAL STORY

TELLING AND CRITICAL REFLECTIONS ON DIFFERENCE

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Abstract

This exposition investigates novel practices for showing social morals through narrating. Drawing from my encounters showing a high level undergrad Narrative Ethics workshop, I clarify how my understudies reacted to a narrating unit through which they inspected their qualities and narrating morals. I entwine perceptions from my educating with experiences assembled from my understudies' in-class conversations and composed reflections to show the instructive points, results, and difficulties experienced while drawing in this material. I center especially around submitting thoughts for urging understudies to (a) embrace cutoff points to their comprehending of others and (b) perceive how tuning in for, and communicating, contrast assumes a basic part in their own, social, and moral development.

Keywords:- Reflection, social, and moral development.

Introduction

Setting and Rationale My advantage in building up this course originated from my perceptions of different social issues influencing my grounds local area. At Denison University (a completely private human sciences establishment), understudies are very close, collaborating with each other much of the time both in and outside of the homeroom. Through serving various grounds activities, like the "Board for Residential Life" and the "Helpful Justice Program," I learn firsthand about understudies' interests over a "divided" and "critical" social culture. A few understudies report that gatherings are "screened" by entryway screens who concede select people and reject others; in different examples, obnoxious ambushes are communicated against understudy gatherings and associations, particularly those that are specific to minorities. Also, given the recurrence with which understudies experience each other, they report having uplifted tensions over how their personalities are seen. Subsequently, they blue pencil how they say and deal with ensure their picture, regardless of whether it requires retaining their convictions.

These examples, among a few others, absolutely influence how understudies authorize and encapsulate their every day collaborations in manners not quickly perceptible in the homeroom setting. As a teacher of social correspondence, I perceived a need to create scholarly courses that react to issues influencing my understudies' quick friendly setting. Accordingly, drawing from my perceptions of the grounds culture, I utilize my Narrative Ethics course as a chance to connect with understudies in correspondence rehearses fundamental for talking really about their encounters and qualities. In this course, I arrange

story morals as a dynamic, social cycle, one through which people take a stab at certified discourse.

These inclinations—to evade struggle—are not restricted to my homeroom encounters. They happen in regular discussions when individuals endeavor to keep up agreement and abstain from posing intense inquiries or communicating contrasts. For example, while noticing the social environment nearby, I witness understudies floating towards others like their selves. What's more, in homeroom conversations, they regularly try not to communicate values that would possibly affect conflict. Along these lines, through this narrating unit, I need my understudies to perceive their disparities while understanding their cutoff points to understanding others' one of a kind auras. At the point when this result doesn't show, I question my educating. Since I frequently urge understudies to react to each other's weakness by making open, open talking circumstances, my accentuation on comfort probably guides them away from interrogating each other further regarding how their worth frameworks contrast in manners that may incite uneasiness. Subsequently, I propose a questioning meeting during which I bring up basic issues for my understudies to talk about in lieu of their discoveries from the narrating unit.

Questioning the Storytelling Unit I approach this questioning meeting with the objective of getting my understudies to consider how recognizing the two similitudes and contrasts is essential while relating morally with others. I initially request that they thoroughly analyze how likenesses and contrasts assume huge parts in the connections they create.

When reacting to this inquiry, my understudies express the strains they experience with identifying with others' very own implications while narrating. We talk about how imparting shared characteristics to others fortifies our feelings of having a place. Then, we likewise recognize our requirement for others to scrutinize the particularities of our encounters to uncover uniqueness and focuses yet to be thought of. Through this cycle, my understudies think about how their connections, manufactured through sharing likenesses, may here and there hinder them from encountering contrasts fundamental for growing their self-improvement and social profundities. Moreover, while relating these perceptions to their grounds culture, my understudies perceive all the more clearly how the divided idea of their social environment is expected generally to their companions' hesitance to experience contrast. Drawing this association makes the learning in the homeroom "genuine," to such an extent that my understudies perceive the need to learn account rehearses imperative for suggesting social contrasts.

Conclusion

Including understudies in dynamic narrating welcomes them to exemplify and institute moral practices for finding esteem in their own lives and companion connections. In the interim, teachers should take care of the manners in which understudies structure associations through such correspondence. The methodologies excused all through this reflection urge understudies to analyze their own qualities while likewise contemplating their associations with others. Hence, these perceptions are fit well for social

correspondence courses wherein listening cautiously to other people and taking part in equitable practices are vital. By perceiving narrating as an amazing methods for hoisting human association, educators also ought to think about their educational practices: How may we grow more imaginative practices for including understudies in examining their disparities? How should we investigate innovative methods for assisting understudies with perceiving cutoff points to their understandings that call further inquiries—leaving stories with and about others open-finished for future revelation? These inquiries mark beginnings for ventures ahead as we keep creating individual, social, and additionally educational practices for developing a moral mindfulness through narrating.

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MEDICINAL PLANT - MOUNTAIN BASIN (ORIGANUM VULGARE)

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Abstract: The article introduces the structure, distribution and composition of the medicinal plant Mountain Basil, its beneficial properties for human health and its use in folk medicine.

Keywords: Extraction, tincture, rhubarb, essential oil, flavonoids.

Introduction

The flora of Uzbekistan is very diverse, and the role of medicinal plants in this diversity is invaluable. Our people have always used these plants as food and medicine. Even in the modern era of scientific development, the need for these plants is growing day by day, and the study of their useful properties and their application in production is underway. More than 4,300 plants belonging to the local flora, 750 species are medicinal, of which 112 species are registered for use in scientific medicine, of which 70 species are actively used in the pharmaceutical industry. carried out in accordance with modern regulations, under which extraction purification, concentration, standardization is carried out in accordance with all international quality standards of production.

One of the most common medicinal plants in Uzbekistan is Mountain Basil, which is found almost everywhere. The medicinal properties of this plant have long been known to the local population. It is consumed, used as a spice in food, tea and tinctures are prepared, used instead of medicines. In pharmacies and cosmetics stores we can also see special herbal tinctures, herbal preparations for the bath, various useful additives, essential oils, and others. The product contains natural minerals, vitamins, and biologically active substances.

The Main Findings and Results

Geographical distribution: The plant is found in Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, Kyrgyzstan, as well as in southern Kazakhstan. It is found on small rocky slopes in the lower and middle parts of mountain ranges, in the foothills of rocks and boulders, and It also grows in the European part of the CIS (except the northern part) in the Caucasus, in the dry open meadows in the southern regions of Siberia, in the hills, cliffs, rocks and bushes on the dry forest and forest edges.

Chemical composition. The product contains essential oil, additives, ascorbic acid (in flowers, leaves) and phenolic carboxylic acids, ascorbic acid. The seeds contain fatty oils, as well as resins, triterpene acids, coumarins, polyphenols, flavonoids

Effects and application: decoctions and tinctures of turmeric are used to treat gouty joint pain, as a sedative in inflammatory diseases of the respiratory system, as well as in various neuroses, to stimulate the appetite; used for rinsing, washing purulent wounds, scabs. When eaten, it opens the clots and nodes of the body organs, expels mucus, relieves digestion of heavy foods, increases sexual energy, opens the appetite, increases the need for food, improves the lungs, liver, stomach and intestines, It clears phlegm and harmful moisture, blocks the passage of toxins to the brain, prevents stuttering, brightens the complexion and clarifies the face. It is known from the literature that galenic preparations of mountain basil are used in folk medicine in Tajikistan. It is widely used to treat inflammatory diseases (cholecystitis, gastritis, ulcerative colitis, abdominal rest, bronchitis, pneumonia, urinary stone disease), as well as for rinsing the throat from angina, stomatitis, laryngitis. In modern medicine, thyme is widely used as a remedy for coughs, convulsions, spasms, reducing inflammation, improving digestion. Mountain basil has been found to increase the activity of the pancreas, increase bile production, as well as reduce the amount of cholesterol in the bile.

Medicinal properties; The product is included in teas, which are used for sweating and chest diseases. Mountain basil, a species that grows in mountainous areas of Uzbekistan, is allowed to be used in medical practice.

Use in local medicine: Infusion:

1. To make medicine at home, take two teaspoons of crushed turmeric and infuse it with 400 g of boiling water. The prepared tincture can be consumed throughout the day.
2. Dip 1 tablespoon of chopped turmeric in 400 ml of boiling water and soak for 2 hours. Take 100 ml of the tincture 4 times a day before meals, it helps with colds and coughs. It also helps digest food when gastric juices are low. It is recommended to prepare more than a tincture and take a bath mixed with water for washing purulent wounds and other skin diseases.
3. Infuse 1 teaspoon of chopped herbs in 250 ml of boiling water for 1 hour and filter. Drink 100 ml of the tincture 2-4 times a day as a sedative and tonic. The crushed (apparently) mountain basil leaves and flowers are placed in the form of a bar, if dry, softened in hot water and placed on a hard inflamed area where the skin has hardened. In scientific medicine, thymol is extracted, as well as liquid extracts and various extracts.

Mountain basil is used as a spice in barley or dried form. Mountain basil herb is part of many collections. This wonderful plant is also used in the treatment of radiation exposure. It has been found that regular consumption can even serve as a remedy for smallpox. Undoubtedly, the benefits of mountain basil for the human body are endless, as it has many types and large amounts of nutrients and unparalleled healing properties. The great scholar Abu Ali Ibn Sina also used the riches of the green world - medicinal plants - in the treatment of various diseases.

Conclusion

Collection and storage of raw materials: Due to the medicinal properties of the flowers, leaves and seeds of the mountain basil plant, it is harvested during the flowering period, when the weather is clear and dry. The cut green mass is dried in the shade. Once harvested, the plant produces leaves again, grows and is ready for the second harvest before the onset of the autumn cold. The obtained raw material is stored in a well-ventilated place. The natural fragrant smell of plants stored in airtight and moisture-free places is preserved for a long time. It is a medicinal

plant that grows in the wild and is important for human health. .) is used as a drug and medicinal raw material

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GYPQUAL MATERIALS BASED ON LOCAL AND SECONDARY RAW MATERIALS FOR CONSTRUCTION PURPOSES

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Abstract: In connection with the growth of industrial, civil and housing construction in Uzbekistan, the demand for finishing building materials based on cement and gypsum has sharply increased. The most widely used materials for the interior decoration of buildings under construction are materials based on gypsum.

Keywords: Filler, water repellent, heat resistance, slaked lime, powdered silica.

Introduction

Since independence and the establishment of market relations in the Republic of Uzbekistan, fundamental changes have taken place in all branches of industrial production, including in the construction industry. Due to the growth of industrial, civil and residential construction, the demand for finishing building materials based on cement and gypsum has increased dramatically. Gypsum-based materials are the most widely used for interior decoration of buildings under construction [1]. Their advantages are significantly lower than for lime and cement production, fuel consumption during production, sufficiently high strength, fast hardening and rapid strength gain. A generalized formulation of the gypsum system used for the production of both products and inorganic powder composite materials based on it. It consists mainly of a gypsum binder, where various fillers, fillers and modifiers are introduced:

- * gypsum binder (possible addition of lime, Portland cement);
- * filler/filler;
- setting retarder;
- water-retaining and / or rheological additive;
- hydrophobizator;

- * defoamer (if necessary);
- air intake (if necessary).

Methods

For the production of gypsum binders [6], natural dihydrate gypsum, anhydrite, clay gypsum, as well as some industrial waste consisting mainly of dihydrate or anhydrous calcium sulfate or a mixture of them (phosphogypsum, borogypsum, citrogypsum, etc.) are used as the main raw materials.

Waste from the production of phosphoric fertilizers and extraction phosphoric acid contains impurities of fluorine, phosphoric acid, sodium, potassium, which pollute the environment. The intensification of agricultural development leads to an even greater increase in the production of phosphorus fertilizers, and, consequently, an increase in phosphogypsum waste. Therefore, solving the problem of recycling these wastes is of great importance for the development of the country's economy and improving the environmental situation in the region [2, 5]. The most promising of the outlined areas of utilization of phosphogypsum should include its processing into phosphogypsum binders, which are suitable for the manufacture of a wide range of construction products, dry building mixes, self-leveling floors, etc. [3, 4].

At cost, gypsum materials based on phosphogypsum binders are about two times cheaper than mixtures obtained from natural gypsum, since their production eliminates the stages of extraction, crushing and grinding of rock, which are the most energy-intensive in the production of gypsum binders.

A. V. Volginskiy suggested gipsokartonnye (GPCs) and gipsoshlakobetona binders (GSCP), which is a mixture of construction or high-strength gypsum cement or slag cement and pozzolanic additive. They are characterized by a rapid increase in strength due to the presence of semi-aqueous gypsum, and the ability to harden in wet conditions like hydraulic cements [6].

Results

To improve the construction and technical properties of composite gypsum-containing materials for construction purposes, various additives modifiers are used, which, depending on the purpose, are divided into:

- modifying additives - regulators of rheological properties;
- modifying additives - regulators of setting and hardening processes;
- modifying additives-structure regulators; modifying additives for special purposes;

- modifying additives of multifunctional action.

The most significant task in the field of obtaining gypsum-containing composite materials for construction purposes is to increase the durability, weather resistance and durability of products made of gypsum binders. This becomes possible when using mechanical activation, i.e., finer grinding of the initial components or by introducing additives into the composition that increase the water resistance of gypsum. Such additives include Portland cement, active mineral additives, ash, slag, etc.

Based on the results of the analysis of literature sources and patent-information search, it was concluded that for the production of high-performance composite mixtures based on gypsum binders for construction purposes, the most promising are:

- application of mechanical activation of raw materials (gypsum, anhydrite, fillers);
- use of chemical additives to increase the durability, plasticity and workability of solutions based on gypsum-containing materials;
- use for the preparation of gypsum binder of industrial waste-phosphogypsum, natural anhydrite and anhydrite, which is a waste of the ceramic industry;
- selection of rational granulometric and material composition of fine aggregate and filler based on local sands and waste from the stone processing industry. The basic technological scheme for the production of powder inorganic composite materials modified with chemical additives consists of the following sections::
- the site of preparation (fine grinding) of the filler;
- mixing area of components;
- the site of production of finished products;
- the packaging area.

Discussion

In increasing the scientific and technical level of the technology for producing powdered inorganic composite materials, an important place belongs to the grinding process, which has a significant impact on the construction and technical properties of binders and is characterized by a high level (up to 30-40 %) of energy, metal and capital costs from the total costs of their production. The main requirements for the grinding process are a rational grain composition of binders, high energy efficiency and reliability with minimal labor and material costs.

Fine grinding, along with reducing the particle size, is accompanied by a number of physical

and physico-chemical effects that affect both the efficiency of the process itself and the physical properties of the crushed materials [8-14]. Mechanical activation contributes to an increase in the activity of the crushed material as a result of various kinds of defects, an increase in the number of active centers on the surface of the particles, etc.

Classification of gypsum binders is carried out not only by their strength indicators, but also by the degree of grinding-they are divided into binders of coarse, medium and fine grinding [9-20].

Conclusions

1. Having analyzed the economic, environmental and technological aspects as raw materials for the production of modified inorganic powder composite materials for construction purposes based on local raw materials and industrial waste that meet the requirements of world standards in terms of their indicators (strength, durability, adhesion, atmospheric, water, frost and biostability), to adopt gypsum rocks from different deposits of Uzbekistan, phosphogypsum - waste from the production of extraction phosphoric acid, fillers and aggregates from river and dune sands, limestone and marble chips - waste from the stone processing industry.

2. To improve the construction, technical and rheological properties of the developed powder composite materials based on gypsum and phosphogypsum binders, modifier additives were selected to increase the durability (increase the setting time), improve the rheological properties, water, weather and biostability.

3. The most effective way to obtain a fine powder material consisting of several components is its mechanical activation in a dismembrator, where the material is finely ground in a short time.

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THE ROLE OF RESOURCEFUL IRRIGATION NETWORKS IN INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF THE IRRIGATION SECTOR

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Abstract: This article describes in detail the current state of existing irrigation networks in the irrigated areas of Bukhara region and the causes of water wastage and ways to eliminate it.

Keywords: irrigation, damp removal, gutter, waste, maintenance, leakage, evaporation, hydramodule, water consumption.

Introduction

Over the past 4 years, great changes have taken place in all spheres in our country. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyayev dated December 11, 2020 No PP-4919 "On measures to accelerate the introduction of water-saving technologies in agriculture" to a certain extent.

The main water resources of the republic flow from the borders of foreign countries. 180,000 km of irrigation canals serve 4.3 million hectares of irrigated land. It is known that irrigation networks are divided into permanent and temporary irrigation networks according to their function. Water from these networks is divided into 3 in terms of waste.

The system of water wastage in the canal

$$Q_l = Q_f + Q_E + Q_T, \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$$

here:

- Q_f - The amount of water lost to the bottom of the river (90-95%) is m^3/s
- Q_E - the amount of water evaporated from the water surface into the air (2-4%) m^3/s
- Q_T - the amount of water lost for technical reasons (2-4%) m^3/s

Water wastage in irrigation networks is inextricably linked to the length of irrigation networks. The tendency of irrigated lands of Bukhara region to become saline leads to the constant supply of reclamation networks.

Irrigation networks at the expense of water management organizations in Bukhara region , of November 1, 2020 (total canals)

The total length of canals in Bukhara region is 1721.1 km, of which the length of canals is 981.6 km, concrete canals are 728.6 km, gutters are 10.8 km. In percentage terms, most irrigation networks are groundwater channels. In turn, this will lead to an increase in waste in the irrigation network.

Conclusion

It should be noted that in the context of water scarcity, an important factor in the efficient use of water resources is to increase the efficiency of irrigation networks. This is one of the most important tasks facing farm and cluster leaders and all employees working in the field.

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CIRCULATION ONCOLOGY SCHOOLING AND INVOLVEMENT WITH THE UNDERGRAD CLINICAL SETTING

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Abstract

The objective of this investigation was to decide the effect and experience of circulation oncology instruction in the undergrad clinical involvement with the USA. A rundown of American clinical schools was consented from different sources including the Association of American Medical Colleges and American Association of Colleges of Osteopathic Medicine in the mid year of 2009. Information was removed through establishment site survey, singular calls and email circulation. An aggregate of 198 projects were incorporated. Each clinical school educational plan had oncology address during MS year 1 and 2, albeit an insignificant sum had a RO-explicit talk during MS year 1 and 2. There were huge contrasts in the RO training and involvement with allopathic versus osteopathic programs. Home circulation oncology projects and profession exhorting were related with a circulation oncology elective during year 3 and 4. Besides, RO vocation counsels and more established schools were related with having one understudy match into circulation oncology. RO schooling during the educational bit of the undergrad clinical experience

remains amazingly restricted. This constraint is much more articulated in clinical schools without RO mentorship and in osteopathic clinical schools. This absence of RO openness propagates itself by carrying less understudies into the field. These issues require consideration both on a public and clinical school-explicit level.

Keywords:- Circulation oncology; instruction; undergrad clinical schooling.

Introduction

Malignancy is the subsequent driving reason for death around the world, and affects pretty much every field of medication. While a few clinical fortes might be engaged with the consideration of malignant growth patients, oncologists, circulation oncologists, and specialists stay the three principle mainstays of disease therapy in medication. Circulation therapy is utilized for the therapy of roughly half of all patients with disease and records for more than 40% of the fix rates. Past examinations have shown an absence of oncology instruction in the undergrad clinical setting. Besides, circulation oncology stays a little extent of the oncology instructive experience for clinical understudies. Different projects have endeavored to expand exhibition sure to RO are in phases of improvement or potentially execution, yet it is obscure how powerful these have been [3,6]. The objective of this investigation was to decide the impact to RO training and involvement with the undergrad clinical involvement with the USA.

Technique A rundown of American clinical schools was agreed from different sources including the Association of American Medical Colleges and American Association of Colleges of Osteopathic Medicine in the mid year of 2019. After the underlying rundown was made, schools with various grounds were merged into one area. Clinical schools that were as of late settled and had no graduating class were barred from the examination. An aggregate of 198 projects were remembered for this investigation. Information was extricated from different sources including the school's site, calls, and messages. Key attributes were gathered including MD or DO program, RO program with or without inhabitants, RO explicit vested party, oncology lectures including RO-explicit talk during MS1-2, RO rotations electives during MS3-4, vocation advisors for RO, and match into a RO residency program.

Discussion

Our examination shows the fluctuation of RO education and involvement with undergrad clinical training. Albeit all clinical school educational plans have oncology-based talks, not many schools have a RO explicit talk. Past investigations have shown practically zero association of circulation oncologists in the instructive bit of the undergrad clinical experience. A new study shows 60.8% of clinical understudies had no openness to RO [8]. This presents prompt zone of progress for our field. There was a powerless relationship between pre clinical RO training with home RO divisions' inhabitants, which may show an extraordinary interest in instruction in these offices [3]. More examinations are important to comprehend the impact of home RO programs on educational plan improvement

during the initial two years of clinical school. Besides, discoveries recommend huge vary ences between the allopathic and osteopathic clinical schools were found. Understudies at osteopathic clinical schools have less openness to RO both in their pre clinical and clinical years. Restricted RO openness and the expanded competitiveness of RO may clarify this critical distinction.

To improve RO instructional training, oncology education all in all ought to be improved. Studies have set up that oncology-related schooling stays under-underlined contrasted with different subjects, and clinical understudies are not as alright with oncology when contrasted with different orders. Clinical schools may have to retool oncology education for the cutting edge clinical understudies because of the connection of malignant growth with different fields. Moreover, RO offices with both scholarly and private practice suppliers should contact their clinical schools to help create educational plan appropriate for every single clinical understudy. Past examinations have exhibited great results with this alternative [6]. Because of the increment of new clinical schools, public RO organizations, for example, ASTRO and ACRO can create universal addresses that can be utilized by clinical schools to improve educational program, particularly on the off chance that they don't have a set up home RO office. Taking everything into account, RO schooling during the instructional segment of the undergrad clinical experience remains very restricted. This impediment is much more articulated in clinical schools without RO men torship and in osteopathic clinical schools. This absence of RO openness sustains itself

by carrying fewer understudies into the field. These issues require consideration both on a public and clinical school-explicit level.

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BIOECOLOGY OF CALIFORNIA SHIELD (DIASPIDIOTUS PERNICIOSUS COMST.) IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: Dangerous coccids are widespread in Uzbekistan. Of these, the californian shield insect is a quarantine pest. It damages many plants. It damages apple, pear, plum, quince, peach, almonds, hawthorn, elm, poplar and others. Diapausing larvae of the first age overwinter, covered with a dark gray or black shield. In spring, it feeds intensely, molts and forms a shield similar to that of an adult female. After the second molt, adult females are formed. After mating, the female spawns larvae of strollers, which spreads along branches and leaves, and can also settle on fruits. It gives rise to the next generation.

Keywords: Female, male, larva, phase, cycle, molting.

Introduction

California shield insect (*Diaspidiotus perniciosus* Comst.) - One of the serious pests of fruit, greenhouse, ornamental crops, forests and parklands in Uzbekistan. In the republic, it is subject to internal quarantine. To date, biology, ecology, harmfulness, the spread of California shield insects, and measures to combat it in the republic are not well understood. The harmfulness of California shield insects is very high [3].

Material and methods of research

In Uzbekistan, the pest most intensively propagates on apple, quince, pear, plum, cherry plum, cherry, peach, apricot, walnut, willow, lilac and rosehip. During mass reproduction, the Californian shield insects populate all the aerial parts of trees: boles, branches, leaves and fruits. On the leaves, mainly nymphs of males and larvae of the 1st and 2nd ages are found, on the fruits all stages develop. On populated fruits, small red spots form as a result of feeding on the insects. Fruits populated in the early stages acquire an ugly shape [4,5].

Due to the nutrition of California shield insects, the growth and development of trees slows down, annual growth and the number of growing shoots decrease; individual branches dry up, and young trees aged 2–5 years, heavily populated by a scab, die completely. Observations showed that the scabbard has a selective ability in relation to various varieties of apple and pear [1,2].

Research results and discussion

The pest in Uzbekistan is developing in three generations. Winters in the stage of 1st-instar larvae under a dense large black shield on the bark of tree trunks and branches. Wintered larvae awaken in spring at a temperature of $\pm 10\text{--}15^{\circ}\text{C}$ with the beginning of sap flow in plants. The pest population is significantly affected by climatic features. The air temperature of the winter and spring periods is a determining factor in the life cycle of the pest, shifting the timing of the onset of the stages in one direction or another within $\pm 8\text{--}12$ days. In the conditions of the Tashkent region, molting of 1st-instar larvae of the wintering generation begins in the middle of the second decade of March with an average daily temperature of $\pm 12\text{--}15^{\circ}\text{C}$. The bulk of larvae of the 2nd age turns into females at the beginning of the first decade of April. They eat intensely, their body grows in size and mates at the beginning of the second decade of April. In the middle of the third decade of April, a massive flight of males takes place. A month after mating, at the beginning of the second decade of May - until the middle of the first decade of June, females hatch the larvae of strollers. By the beginning of the second decade of June, larvae of the 1st age and single larvae of the 2nd age are found in mass in nature. The development of the second generation of shield insects begins in the first decade of July. At the end of the second decade of July, numerous colonies of larvae of the first age of the second generation are observed on branches, leaves and fruits (apple, pear and plum). In the third decade of July, the larvae pass into the 2nd age, and in early August turn into females. Hatching of larvae of vagrants of the third generation occurs at the end of the second decade of August and lasts until the end of the first decade of September. The beginning of molting of larvae of the 1st age is observed in the first decade of September and lasts until the middle of the third decade of the month. Larvae of the 2nd age turn into females at the end of the second decade of September. The flight of males takes place at the beginning of the third decade of September. At the beginning of the first decade of October, females begin to hatch larvae, and it lasts until the end of the second decade of October. At

the end of the first decade of November in nature (on the leaves of apple and plum), larvae of the 1st and 2nd ages are found in mass, which subsequently go to winter.

Female III age

Conclusion

Thus, the development of the 1st generation of the pest lasts from the 1st decade of April to the middle of the 3rd decade of June, the 2nd generation - from the 2nd decade of June to the 2nd decade of August, the 3rd generation - from the 2nd decade of August to the end of the 1st decade of November. The full cycle of development of the first generation takes place within $\pm 43-53$ days, the second generation $\pm 42-45$ days and the third generation $\pm 66-82$ days. The fertility of females of the first generation is $\pm 75-95$, the second generation $\pm 125-155$, the third generation $\pm 110-130$ larvae of strollers. It should be noted that I and II, II and III generations have been developing in parallel for a long time. The simultaneous hatching of larvae leads to an imposition of developmental periods for different generations. In connection with this summer, the simultaneous development of all stages of shield insects is observed. Therefore, during this period, insecticides that destroy all stages of the pest can be effective. California shield insects are distributed mainly with planting and grafting materials. In addition, stroller larvae can be carried by wind, water, birds, or actively spread through nearby trees.

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COLORADO BEETLE (LEPTINOTARSA DECEMLINEATA) PEST OF POTATO

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Abstract: The main food plant is potatoes, but it can feed on eggplants, tomatoes and wild nightshade plants. Belongs to the order of beetles or beetles (Coleoptera), the family of leaf beetles (Chrysomelidae).

Keywords: Potato agrocenzen, Colorado beetle, populate, imago, eggs, etc., larvae.

Introduction

Adult beetles are short-oval, convex in shape. Pronotum and elytra yellowish or yellowish-red. Pronotum has 12-14 black spots, of which the middle is in the form of a Roman numeral V. 5 narrow stripes run along each elytra. The base of the elytra is bordered by a narrow rim. The beetle is 7-12 mm long, 4.5-8 mm wide. The egg is oblong-oval, light orange, 1.1-1.8 mm long, 0.8 mm wide, first yellow, then orange. The larvae of the first instar are dark gray, 1.5-2.4 mm long, the second - red, 2.5-4.5 mm long, the third - reddish-orange-yellowish, 9.1-16 mm long. The head, sides of the body and legs of the larvae of all ages are black, the shape is convex, the abdomen is wider than the chest, pointed at the end; pronotum with black transverse spot; abdominal sides with two black spots on each segment.

Fig. 1. Colorado potato beetle eggs

Beetles overwinter in the soil of the fields where it reproduced and fed, at a depth of 20-70 cm. Beetles start overwintering when the soil temperature becomes 12-16o C. Beetles come to the surface and feed on plants. after increased feeding, mating and oviposition begins, usually one month after the beetles emerge. After mating, the females lay eggs on the underside of the leaves and are arranged in heaps (25-30 pcs.). One female lays an average of 400-700 eggs, some individuals - up to 2400 eggs. After 5-17 days, larvae emerge from the eggs, which begin to greedily eat the leaves of the plants. They do the main harm to plants. The larvae begin feeding on leaves immediately after hatching. The larvae of young instars gnaw holes on the upper leaves, and the older instars eat the leaves from the edges, and later eat the petioles and stems. The caterpillar stage lasts 16-34 days and goes through 4 instars. Adult larvae go into the soil to a depth of 5-18 cm, pupate there and turn into beetles after 10-24 days. In July-August, beetles of the summer generation appear. This is the second generation of beetles, which can lay eggs again in 15-20 days. It takes 30-70 days for one generation to develop.

There are 3 generations in the conditions of Uzbekistan. Adult beetles live 12-14 months; on warm days they can fly up to 10 km. Beetles and larvae roughly eat leaves. With an average number of 20-40 larvae and beetles per bush in the field, in most plants the leaves are destroyed by half, in some places almost completely. In tomato, the larvae prefer to eat

the stems, sometimes gnawing them so hard that the latter break off under the weight of the fruit. The larvae do not disdain fruits either.

Fig. 2. Colorado beetle (*Leptinotarsa decemlineata*)

Control measures: There are various ways to control the Colorado potato beetle. It is always important to detect pest foci in a timely manner. You can collect and destroy beetles and larvae, especially when the plants have not yet grown. Early detection and destruction of egg-laying is effective. They also use a bait method to combat adult beetles. This is done in early spring, before the seedlings are planted, when the beetles came out of wintering, spreading the skin of the tubers or small substandard tubers along the edges of the field. Beetles gather on these baits, which together with the bait are collected and destroyed. These methods of control are successful if there are few pests. Otherwise, planting nightshade crops is treated with biological and chemical preparations.

The economic threshold of harmfulness is the presence of 2-3 larvae per plant together with adults or in case of damage of 20% or more of crops. Of the chemical agents for fighting the Colorado potato beetle on nightshade vegetables, it is recommended to use the following drugs: Fosalon, Chloratraniliprol, Cypermethrin, Esfenvalerat, Lufenuron, Fipronil, Zeta-cypermethrin, Lambda-cyhalothrin and other approved drugs. The first treatment is carried

out during the period of mass release of overwintered beetles, the second time - when larvae appear.

Conclusion

On eggplant, it is necessary to fight against overwintered beetles when no more than 1% of plants are populated. Tomato is less favorable for the nutrition and development of the Colorado potato beetle than eggplant and potatoes; larvae are fought on it. The economic threshold of harmfulness on tomato approaches 10% of the infested plants, if the number of larvae on each plant exceeds more than four individuals.

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DISTRIBUTION, DAMAGE AND CONTROL MEASURES OF TOMATO MOTH (TUTA ABSOLUTA MEYR.)

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Abstract: In our country, the leadership of our state attaches great importance to providing the population with food products, including domestically grown tomatoes. One of the most pressing issues today in our country is agriculture in a market economy, aimed at improving the living conditions of the population and protecting the environment. In particular, the promotion of a sufficient number of agricultural products per capita to the level of highly developed countries is the basis of the agrarian policy pursued in the Republic. This is due to the fact that in recent years, from the southern to the northern regions of the country, as a result of damage to the tomato crop (*Tuta absoluta* Meyr), the plant withers, yields fall, market prices rise.

Keywords: biology, morphology, damage control measures.

Introduction

The homeland of the tomato moth is South America. In 1980, it was discovered to be present in all parts of the region. In recent years, it has spread to Spain, France, Italy, Greece, Malta, Morocco, Algeria, Libya, Turkey, Syria, Lebanon, Jordan, Iran, Egypt, Sudan, Ethiopia, Senegal, and Ukraine, causing great damage. It has been found in Russia since the fall of 2010 and in Kazakhstan in 2011.

It was found that tomato crops grown in Navoi, Bukhara, Kashkadarya, Samarkand and Tashkent regions of the country, as well as in some greenhouses and open fields of the Fergana

Valley are infected with tomato moth (*Tuta absoluta* Meyr). In the last 5 years, the early arrival of spring and the overheating of the air temperature have created favorable conditions for the growth and development of tomato moth. In addition, the mass flowering of tomatoes was observed in May, a little earlier than every year, when the first generation of tomato moth in the open field, as a result of which 50–70% of tomatoes planted during the growing season died during the growing season.

Main Part

Tomato moth In open fields during the entire growing season of tomatoes, especially in areas where maintenance agrotechnical measures are not carried out in a timely manner, their damage increases, and the buds, leaves, stems and fruits at the point of growth of plants sometimes damage the root collars of the stem. Therefore, this year, as a result of the increase of this pest in the tomato fields of farms of the republic, it was observed that the yield increased by 50-100% and caused serious damage. In addition, as a result of the removal of plant moth-infested plant residues in the greenhouse in May due to the end of the growing season, the moths in the plant residues flew to the open field and grew sharply in the open field. the resulting damage was found to be increasing. For this reason, urgent agro-technical and biological control measures must be taken. **Countermeasures:**

Agrotechnician. The main advantage of the agrotechnical method in the protection of vegetable crops from pests is that there are no additional costs when using this method, as all agrotechnical measures are part of the technology of cultivation of plants. The application of timely and reasonable agro-technical complex measures to vegetable crops improves its growth and development, increases its resistance to tomato moth. To increase the plant's resistance to pests, it is necessary to provide mineral nutrition, timely watering, fertilizing. Some leaves of the first infected plants should be removed or strongly damaged plants should be removed from the

greenhouse or field, buried or burned. Weeding (belonging to the family of alfalfa) and disinfection of the greenhouse should be carried out.

Biological control measures. Currently (in Bukhara, Navoi, Tashkent region and valley regions) against the moth butterflies "Coppert BV" pheromone catchers "Pherodis", "Biobest", "Tutasan", "IFODA" and "OSIYOHIMIMPORT". Pheromone catchers are used and high results are achieved. "Tutamon" pheromone trap 2 pheromone traps will be approved for monitoring 1 hectare of land. 20-30 pheromone traps are provided for mass catching of butterflies on 1 hectare of land. To use the "Tutasan" pheromone handle, they are placed in the middle of the water container in special devices, to increase the viscosity of the water, 100 ml of liquid soap or oil is added to the water inside the container and placed 1 meter above the ground. When this pheromone trap was applied at 10-40 per hectare, thousands of butterflies were observed to fall in one day. Hanging screens with yellow glue at 35 per hectare will also prevent the spread of butterflies on the tomato moth.

Biological control measures. "Tutasan" pheromone catcher

Research on pheromone traps, which are widely used in the country today, is carried out by the staff of the laboratory "Fumigation and application of pheromones" of the Plant

Quarantine Research Center. Pheromone traps of 2 pieces per hectare are planted at a height of 15-20 cm from the plant and control of butterflies falling on the pheromone trap is carried out.

The order of control is as follows: Planted tomatoes (March-early, July-late) germinate and put pheromone traps in the phase of 4–5 leaves. After the pheromone traps are placed, monitoring is performed every 3 days until the first butterfly falls. As soon as the first butterfly is detected, it is counted every morning. The number of fallen butterflies is calculated for each contour, and the data obtained are recorded in a notebook. Information on the results of generalized pheromonitoring in the region (districts) is submitted to the inspection "Uzstatekarantin". By clarifying the areas where the tomato moth has spread, the areas where it can spread next year are predicted and a map is formed. This means that in order to reduce the spread and damage of tomato moth in greenhouses and in the open field, first of all, timely agro-technical measures, biological and chemical control measures can be used to maintain productivity. In order to prevent the damage caused by tomato moth in the country and to obtain high and quality yields from these crops, it is necessary to implement the following control measures:

- Pre-sowing treatment of tomato seeds with chemicals;
- selection of varieties and hybrids resistant to tomato moth, taking into account soil and climatic conditions, their placement on a scientific basis;
- Proper organization of crop rotation when planting tomatoes;
- Loss of wintering phases through high-quality autumn plowing;
- organization of burial of plant remains in specially dug pits and bags, which will be removed after the end of the season in the greenhouse;
- Selection of seedlings from nurseries not affected by moths and other diseases, chemical treatment of seedlings before planting in the field;

- to organize the systematic use of pheromone traps (to know the timing of emergence and, in part, as a measure of control) based on the timing of reproduction and reproduction.

- During the growing season of tomatoes it is necessary to apply the permitted drugs against these pests in the required time and in the prescribed manner.

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THE MANKIND AND AFRICA'S GROWTH

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Abstract: African governments have put forth individual and aggregate attempts to advance improvement programs/projects on the landmass since autonomy was accomplished in the majority of the nations during the 1960s. These endeavors have brought about minimal achievement and sometimes the yearnings have deteriorated. The truth is that most of the nations are poor with feeble socio-political establishments. The circumstance is convoluted by the conspicuous reality that Africa is yet to make a critical forward leap nearby science and innovation which could help improvement as is as of now realistic in different mainlands of the world. Indeed, even with this hole, advancement organizers in the landmass have not given critical consideration to the Mankind. This paper sets that the Mankind are not just fundamental for the advancement of the African landmass; yet it is the superstructure whereupon the mainland's improvement endeavors should be based. It further exhibits that no significant improvement can happen in the landmass without a top to bottom information on the set of experiences, and culture like dialects, religion and the customary information pool of the African public and same being utilized as a reason for arranging and advancement.

Keywords: African public, growth, fundamental for the advancement of the African landmass.

Introduction

In 2011, the African chiefs who accumulated in Lusaka, Zambia, to disclose the New Partnership for Africa's Growth vowed that "...based on a typical vision, and a firm and shared conviction, they have a squeezing obligation, to kill neediness and spot the African nations, both separately and aggregately on a way of feasible Growth and advancement, and simultaneously to partake on the planet economy and body politic". Sixteen years after this vow was made, Africans have not seen any obvious improvement in their lives and material conditions than they did in 2001 when the promise was made. Without a doubt, day to day environments in most African nations have plunged since NEPAD was conceived. This paper inspects the Mankind and Africa's improvement. It is partitioned into four areas. Segment one is the presentation, segment two looks at the idea of improvement and applied explanations of Mankind and advancement. Segment three spotlights on the Mankind and advancement in Africa and the commitments of the Mankind to Africa's improvement. Area three is worried about the difficulties of the Mankind to improvement in Africa, while segment four is the end.

The Concept of Growth

There is no agreement on what establishes improvement. What might be viewed as improvement of a group at a specific stage in their set of experiences may really be viewed as retrogression if not obliteration for one more gathering of individuals at different stages in their turn of events. It should be noticed that meanings of improvement are affected by

the characterizing authority's reasoning and the socio-political tendencies of the area so characterized. For, example advancement in industrialist, communist and blended economy is drawn from their current circumstance and is additionally a sign of the author's socio-political leanings. It is troublesome subsequently to give an exact importance of „Growth“. Moreover, the importance of improvement has throughout the years turned out to be wide, changed and furthermore relied upon the abundance and expectation for everyday comforts of the characterizing specialists. In view of the above mentioned, it is important to momentarily think about a portion of the common viewpoints of advancement.

Advancement in UNDP's see additionally implies an improvement in a country's monetary and social conditions. It explicitly alludes to upgrades in the methods of dealing with an areas normal and HR to make riches and improve lives. The UNDP explained further that while there can be esteem decisions on what advancement is and what it isn't, it ought to be an all around worthy point of improvement to make for conditions that lead to the acknowledgment of the possibilities of the individual.

The rot in the book distributing industry in the landmass is a significant test to the investigation of the Mankind. Global distributing organizations that began the book unrest during the 1960s have since the most recent twenty years of the 20th century migrated from the mainland. Journalists who might some way or another have had the option to go further have discovered their professions deteriorated as believed distributors are hard to come by. Neighborhood distributors are generally doubted by writers and monetary foundations, who accept that they are backers of book robbery and consequently are

more certain to give up their original copies to unfamiliar distributing organizations than the nearby ones. Understudies of the Mankind consequently need to depend for the most part on books composed by non-African writers and those gave to libraries, asset focuses and sold at book fairs and bookshops. This will unquestionably restrict their insight into the landmass. It should be underscored here that a flourishing, autonomous local book distributing industry in Africa is an essential segment of the turn of events and social renaissance of the landmass.

Conclusion

By and by the African landmass has shown up at another basic crossroads in its set of experiences; it has a decision, confronted with either driving Africa out of its present financial backwardness and a culture of destitution and sickness or to keep on pandering to the impulses of a bad neighborhood government. The Mankind as a part of information must be overwhelmingly sought after, energized and concentrated from the kindergarten to the tertiary level. Advancement endeavors need to follow a base up approach as well as a matter of most extreme significance be moored on the establishments, accounts, dialects, nearby pool of information, writing, expressions and customs of the African public. Certified local answers for Africa's improvement emergencies are required not imported ones.

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THE IMPORTANCE OF CREATING VIRTUAL RESOURCES FROM A MAIN FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract: The introduction of computer technology in the educational process is increasing the interest of students in science. The computer and a number of its programs allow students to better understand the nature of the object, to take an active part in its study, to record the results in programs, to independently change both its parameters and task conditions. At the same time, the teacher's goal is not to transfer basic knowledge in the process of communication with the group, but to improve the electronic recording of the results of laboratory work and practical training, independent work and learning to conduct research. Nowadays, students are learning to record electronically the instructions and concepts given by the teacher during the lesson. Recording programs play an important role in this. They allow you to save any notes and change them at any time, and make it easier for students to record the results of practical work and laboratory work, and enter them into the computer.

Keywords: Computer programs, English, virtual resources, ICT

Introduction

It should be noted that due to the fact that the study of science with computer tools is very easy, now there is a growing interest in these hardware and software. At present, effective results are being achieved in the educational process with computer technology. The role of WHO is invaluable, especially in teaching a foreign language. It should be noted that the quality of education can be improved by the fact that the simulation models, which are effective in the study of foreign languages, especially English, are easily accessible and versatile in the development of the main foreign language. Of course, many researchers are working on this. At present, not only in European countries, foreign languages are studied through virtual resources, but also in our country, similar research is being conducted. Take, for example, researchers at the Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages and teachers at Samarkand State University. They are engaged in the production of special virtual resources as a practice, developing theories such as the creation of virtual resources from foreign language subjects with the help of special simulation models and their application in the educational process for the introduction of scientific innovation in direct education. Such effective work will increase the attention to foreign languages in education and will once again give an impetus to its quality.

The main results and findings

However, such work increases the attention to the English language. Work is underway not only in our country, but also in other countries to create a basis for the younger generation to learn a foreign language, especially English, using new methods to strengthen its interest in a foreign language in order to achieve its full development.

Teaching English on the basis of WHO increases the interactivity of the lesson, provides interactivity of the lesson. The use of virtual resources in the organization of learning processes ensures a lively lesson, which leads to dynamic processes. During these lessons, the opportunity to review and repeat thematic virtual resources will increase. Virtual resources created in English help to understand the language and to receive new information through sight and hearing. A lot of work is being done to teach foreign languages at universities on the basis of WHO. In particular, the Samarkand branch of the Tashkent Institute of Information Technologies has published special dictionaries on the basis of WHO, which contain information on the use of Uzbek and English words. It is known that in order to learn a foreign language, it is possible to learn the language only through Russian literature. Its grammar is a set of rules used in speech only in Russian. This complicates language learning. In the developed models, based on national values, its interpretation in the Uzbek language is currently carried out by researchers. With the help of virtual resources created in English, the learner easily absorbs and develops the ability to work with ICT tools. Every subject studied by means of ICT is easily and quickly delivered to the recipient. Its virtual database makes it easy to store data in random access memory. Nowadays, students are learning to record electronically the instructions and concepts given by the teacher during the lesson. Recording programs play an important role in this. They allow you to save any notes and change them at any time, and make it easier for students to record the results of practical work and laboratory work, and enter them into the computer. It is known that in the study of a foreign language there are similar records, which are made by computer through various visual representations and presentations. After our independence, many reforms have been carried out in the educational process, including the use of modern information

technologies in education, the introduction of various interactive games to improve the quality of education. All of these systems are aimed only at teaching a foreign language and creating effective teaching processes. Knowledge of a foreign language is an important factor in mastering the secrets of any profession, gaining skills and abilities. Knowledge of the chemical language means a high level of qualification of a specialist working in any field of national economy.

For this reason, even if high school graduates do not set a goal to enter higher education, it is important for them to learn a foreign language in depth and acquire fluency. is very necessary for future professionals who intend to work in various fields of economy. Among the most effective approaches to foreign language teaching are the methods of language teaching in distance learning through information and communication technologies. Computer technology, especially the Internet, has a great potential for language learning. They are manifested in the following: 1) active use in practice of knowledge and skills acquired in oral communication in a foreign language, learning to use the acquired language materials not only in his speech, but also in understanding the speech of the interlocutor he met on the Internet ; 2) develop the ability to adapt the acquired speech knowledge to the changing situations of the relationship; 3) to create a strong, immediate motivation and a motivation to approach the truth in relation to the organization of the conversation, the study of speech, which takes place in the form of informal communication; 4) overcoming psychological barriers, in particular, the fear of speaking a foreign language and making mistakes, the removal of the barrier, as well as internal and external tension and embarrassment; 5) high quality and immediate effectiveness of education; in the second exercise, users begin to speak the foreign

language they are learning in the speech pattern provided in the main textbook; using suggestive means of textual influence (including memorization), the lessons are taken into account from the first exercise; 6) provide and master a large number of spoken, high and grammatical units; 150-200 new words, 30-50 speech patterns and a few ordinary speech events are introduced and mastered in one presentation. The methodology of intensive foreign language teaching has found its place in all stages of the teaching process in secondary schools, at the primary, secondary and higher levels. Suggestopedic technology can complement the recent emergence of new models of foreign language teaching with new content, including: field teaching model, second foreign language teaching model, primary education model . Development of an accelerated methodology for the secondary school environment includes the following aspects:

- growth of educational indicators from quantity to quality
- reconsideration of the ratio between home and classroom work in favor of classroom work for all types of speech activities using suggestopedic technology output and build new features of the user and the interaction of users with each other.

- time allocation is the main important difference between the accelerated method and the traditional method.
- The accelerated method cannot be used in its entirety to study the school curriculum in a foreign language.

- Special methods of intensive method can be successfully used in foreign language classes at school. It is known that the history of foreign language teaching methods in the 60s and 70s of the last century is considered as a period of emergence and development of a number of new teaching methods, commonly known as "intensive teaching methods". All these methods, which first appeared in different countries and in

different years of this period, are nevertheless a general response of the methodology to the social order of modern society. The international situation of this period, the scientific and technological revolution that led to the "explosion" of information, and the expansion of cultural and practical contacts, the growing number of specialists in various fields of science and technology directly involved in international scientific and technical relations. the need to know, in particular, placed its own demands on the ability to know foreign languages, and thus combined some of the principles and guidelines of new methods in teaching. Conditions of communication in a foreign language, which is a means of communication, cognition, information acquisition and collection, determine the need to know all types of speech activities: speaking and comprehension of this foreign language and reading, writing, knowledge of this or that type of speech activity, directly in the practice of communication in a foreign language, reading authentic and high-content literature on the specialty, the exchange of written information in the form of books, annotations to them, theses for conferences, practical notes. According to the American scholar Lake, "the use of a mixed method in language learning leads to the development of traditional teaching methods". However, the concept of a mixed method is a difficult task given to the teacher. The WHO will help to solve these problems. The teacher can use a variety of teaching aids in the classroom, but this is not enough for students to learn. Of course, the role of imitation models is invaluable in providing students with additional information in education and to ensure that lessons are conducted live. Scientist Lake's "We connect lessons with different fields, help to improve the quality of education".

Conclusion

This means that in language learning, not only through a focused field, but also in connection with it, computer imitation tools. also mentioned in the study. Nowadays, in order to teach English with the help of ICT, it is necessary for teachers to have enough ICT specialists. The teacher should be the facilitator of the lessons through WHO. This will ensure the activation of the teaching process through the planned teaching aids. The next process is the lesson planning process, in which programs are developed and Internet tools are activated. One of the most popular ICT tools for learning English in Europe today is the Internet. Through the module, they provide distance learning to students. One of their goals is to make the lesson process easy and understandable to the audience. Creating English language lessons according to the levels of virtual resources will ensure the development of a foreign language.

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ANALYSIS OF NEUROLOGICAL COMPLICATIONS IN HIP ARTHROPLASTY

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Abstract: Currently, in orthopedics, effective, but technically more complex and time-consuming operations are used, one of which is endoprosthetics for dysplastic coxarthrosis. In connection with the increase in the number of patients who underwent hip arthroplasty, the problem of prevention and treatment of postoperative complications becomes especially urgent. In the structure of specific local complications arising in the early postoperative period after total hip arthroplasty, damage to the peripheral nerves of the lower extremities occupies one of the main places.

Keywords: dysplastic coxarthrosis, hip arthroplasty, postoperative neurological complications.

Introduction

Diseases of the musculoskeletal system (DMS) rank first in frequency among diseases leading to temporary or permanent disability [1]. Deforming arthrosis of the hip joint (HJ) is one of the most common and disabling orthopedic diseases. The steadily progressive nature of the process in this pathology in 60-64% of cases leads to a decrease in working capacity and in 11.5% - to disability of people of working age (25,28,37). Due to the severity of the lesion, every eleventh of those suffering from hip joint diseases ultimately becomes disabled, while in all diseases of the support and movement organs, every hundredth is disabled (2,3).

Improvement in the techniques of arthroplasty and endoprosthetics should lead to a minimal risk of neurological complications in the surgical treatment of hip joint pathology. The priorities for the outcome of the operation have now changed. According to leading experts in this field, it is precisely the improvement of the “quality of life” of patients that is the main goal of endoprosthetics. At the same time, the issues of rehabilitation after such operations, in particular their neurological aspects, await further development (1,3).

Purpose of the study: Conduct a retrospective analysis of neurological complications during hip arthroplasty in patients treated in 2015-2019. in the department of orthopedics of RITO MH RUz.

Material and research methods: At the Research Institute of Traumatology and Orthopedics (RITO) for the period 2015-2019 a retrospective analysis of neurological complications in the postoperative period was carried out in 1762 patients with dysplastic and idiopathic coxarthrosis. These patients underwent endoprosthetics of the hip joint (HJ) in the department of orthopedics of the RITO MH RUz. The area of intervention included the zones of innervation of a number of large nerves: the femoral, sciatic, obturator, and external cutaneous nerve of the thigh. Nerve injuries were of traction, compression (compression by hematoma), and iatrogenic genesis. Basically, these are mononeuropathies of mixed traumatic-ischemic genesis.

Research results: The total number of complications in hip arthroplasty was 142 (8.1%) cases. There were 28 somatic complications (1.6%). Among the somatic complications, pulmonary embolism (PE) was observed in 11 patients (0.6%); hospital pneumonia in 5 patients (0.3%), acute coronary insufficiency against the background of ischemic heart disease - in 3 (0.2%); DIC syndrome - in 3 (0.2%); anaphylactic shock (toxic effect of cement) - in 1 (0.1%); bacterial toxic shock - in 2 (0.1%); contact allergic dermatitis - in 3 (0.2%). The lethal outcome was noted in 11 cases (0.6%) and was observed in the following cases of somatic complications: in hospital pneumonia - 1 case; with pulmonary embolism - 6; with disseminated intravascular coagulation - 2; with anaphylactic shock (toxic effect of cement) - 1; with bacterial toxic shock - 1.

Local complications were noted in 114 cases (6.5%), of which: infection of the surgical site - 37 patients (2.1%); vascular complications - 29 (1.6%); neurological complications - 53 (3.0%); dislocation of the endoprosthesis - 11 (0.6%); hematomas of the area of surgical intervention - 12 (0.7%); intraoperative femoral fracture - 6 (0.3%).

Of the neurological complications in 53 patients, the following pathology was identified. Neuropathy of the femoral nerve (4 cases - 8% of patients with neurological complications) was accompanied by impaired flexion in the TS, extension in the knee, impaired walking up the stairs, atrophy of the anterior muscles of the thigh, the knee reflex faded, the sensitivity along the anterior surface of the thigh was impaired. Neuropathy of the external cutaneous nerve of the thigh (in 7 patients - 13%): motor functions are not impaired, sensitive disorders of hyperesthesia, paresthesia with hyperpathy along the outer surface of the thigh in the area of the postoperative scar. Neuropathy of the obturator nerve (in 11 patients - 21%): impaired adduction of the thigh, impaired sensitivity along the inner surface of the upper third of the thigh. Sciatic nerve neuropathy (in our observations, in 31 patients - 58%) was manifested by impaired flexion in the knee joint, extension in the hip, abduction and rotation of the hip outward, the foot drooped, the calcaneal and plantar reflexes faded, the sensitivity on the lateral, posterior-outer surfaces of the thigh was impaired, shins, feet.

Mild violations with a quick elimination of their cause (for example, evacuation of a hematoma) disappear without a trace. With a sharp loss of nerve function, the

prognosis worsened. In the treatment of pain in the postoperative period, nerve blocks were performed with 0.5% - 1% solution of novocaine 20-25 ml, intramuscular administration of analgesics and antispasmodics in mixtures, NSID, administration of antihistamines, sedatives, tranquilizers in mixtures. All patients underwent complex therapy (physiotherapy, massage, ACS). In the period from one to 4 years after the operation, 19 (35.6%) patients showed restoration of function, the remaining 64.4% had partial restoration of function, but they adapted to everyday and work loads

Conclusion

Thus, according to the study, it was revealed that the total number of complications in hip arthroplasty is 8.1%, of which 1.6% are somatic and 6.5% are local. In total, neurological complications were observed in 53 (3.0%) patients. The sciatic nerve is most often affected - in 21.0% of patients with neurological complications. This was due to the nature of the surgical intervention, which was caused by its overstretching during implantation of the endoprosthesis and the reduction of the artificial head into the cup.

Recommendations: To avoid gross neurological complications, it is necessary to lengthen the limb during the operation by no more than 3-4 cm, and if a neurological deficit is detected, the appointment of targeted treatment.

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HOUSEHOLD ADAPTATION IN THE LONG-TERM PERIOD OF TRAUMATIC INTRACRANIAL HEMATOMAS

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Abstract: The best outcomes for domestic adaptation in the long-term period were established in the group of observations with subdural hematomas. Good and satisfactory results of social adaptation were obtained in 92.6% of patients of working age, unsatisfactory - in 1% of patients. The good and often satisfactory degree of social adaptation of our patients, noted in the majority of patients, is the key to a good labor prospect.

Keywords: Cranial Brain trauma, cerebral hematomas, household adaptation

Introduction

Traumatic brain disease often leads to permanent disability and impairs the social adaptation of patients. The program of medical rehabilitation of patients with the

consequences of traumatic brain injury (TBI), especially of working age, should be selected individually, taking into account the clinical and pathomorphological characteristics (1,3).

Rehabilitation of patients with the consequences of TBI is one of the most important medical and social problems. To increase the efficiency of work on the prevention of disability in victims of TBI, continuity is required between inpatient rehabilitation centers for the disabled in the social security system with the mandatory continuation of training in household rehabilitation and occupational therapy rooms (2).

Purpose of the study: To assess social and labor adaptation in the long-term period of treatment of traumatic intracranial hematomas.

Material and research methods: The study is based on a study of 197 patients in the long-term period of traumatic intracranial hematomas. The patients underwent a complex clinical and instrumental study, which allowed judging the functional and structural and morphological changes in the brain in the long-term period of TBI.

To assess household adaptation, the scale of daily vital activity (GOCA) was used, which includes 5 classes according to the classification of the Institute of Neurology of the Russian Academy of Medical Sciences: we classified grades I and II as good household adaptation (returning to the previous job without restrictions or with restrictions, such as a decline in qualifications, a decrease in the volume and / or duration of working hours, a return to the performance of previous household duties, independence from others in everyday life); III class - to satisfactory everyday adaptation (patients can serve themselves, there is a partial dependence in daily life activity, failure to return to their previous work or to perform their previous household duties); IV and V grades - to unsatisfactory everyday adaptation (difficulties in self-service, sharp or complete dependence on others).

Research results: Household adaptation of patients with traumatic hematomas was assessed depending on the initial severity of the condition, gender, age, and localization of the hematomas. When analyzing the dependence of household adaptation on the course of hematoma in the acute period, it was found that in acute, subacute, chronic hematomas, most often the lack of proper social adaptation is observed in patients with

severe primary brain lesions. In the group of patients who were in the acute period in the phase of clinical subcompensation, good domestic adaptation was obtained in 74% of cases, satisfactory - in 20%, unsatisfactory domestic adaptation was not noted. In the group of patients in the phase of moderate decompensation - 57%, 26% and 2%, respectively, in the phase of gross decompensation - 70%, 23% and 2%, respectively, the lethal outcome was 5%, 15% and 5%, respectively. There is a statistically significant relationship between the clinical phase and the number of observations with good and satisfactory everyday adaptation. In the group of patients who were in the acute period in the clinical phase of moderate decompensation, complications developed in the early postoperative period. Household adaptation depending on the sex of patients is presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Dependence of household adaptation on the sex of patients

Household adaptation	Wom.	Men	Total
Good	22 (75%)	111 (66%)	133
Satisfactory	4 (14,5%)	41 (24%)	45
Unsatisfactory	—	2 (1,2%)	2
Death	3 (10,5%)	14 (8,3%)	17
Total:	29 (100%)	168 (100%)	197

The analysis of the results of household adaptation showed that in the group with good adaptation there was a statistically significant dependence on gender, the frequency of good results for women and for men was 75% and 66% ($p < 0.05$). The dependence of household adaptation on age is presented in table 3.

Table 3

Household adaptation in the long-term period, depending on the age of patients, abs (%)

Household adaptation	20-29 years old	30-39 years old	40-49 years old	50-59 years old	60-69 years old	Over 70 years old	Total
Good	43 (32,3%)	40 (30,0%)	29 (21,8%)	14 (10,5%)	4 (3%)	3 (2,3%)	133 (100%)
Satisfactory	15 (33,3%)	13 (29%)	10 (22,2%)	1 (2,2%)	5 (11,1%)	1 (2,2%)	45 (100%)
Unsatisfactory	1 (50%)	1 (50%)					2 (100%)
Death	3 (17,6%)	6 (35,3%)	2 (11,7%)	3 (17,6%)	3 (17,6%)		17 (100%)
Total:	62	60	4 1	18	12	4	197

The majority of patients - 91% (181 observations) - were under the age of 60. In the group of patients of working age, good and satisfactory household adaptation was noted in 92.6% of cases. Unsatisfactory household adaptation in patients in the group under 40, in the acute period patients with unsatisfactory household adaptation were in a prolonged unconscious state, had extra- and intracranial complications. Statistical analysis revealed the dependence of household adaptation on age in the group of patients under 50 years old.

The indicators of household adaptation in the long-term period of treatment of traumatic hematomas, taking into account their localization, are presented in table 4.

Table 4

Household adaptation depending on the type of hematoma

Household adaptation	SDH	EDG	ICH	ESDG	SDH + ICH	IVG	EDG + ICH	Total
Good	7 57.0%	2 7.67%	0 0%	1 6.9%	75%		1 3.367%	11
Satisfying	1 9 18.1%	2 9 2%	5%	4 25%	25%	1 100%		4 5.23%
Unsatisfied	1	1		—				2

Note: SDH - subdural hematoma, EDG - epidural hematoma, ICH - intracerebral hematoma, ESDG - epidual hematoma, IVG - intraventricular hematoma.

It was found that with unsatisfactory household adaptation, hematomas were of subdural and epidural localization, 0.9% and 2.5%, respectively. The best outcomes for domestic adaptation in the long-term period were established in the group of observations with subdural hematomas ($p < 0.05$). Correlation analysis did not reveal a linear relationship between domestic adaptation in the long-term period and the localization of hematomas.

Conclusion

Good and satisfactory results of social adaptation were obtained in 92.6% of patients of working age, unsatisfactory - in 1% of patients. The good and often satisfactory degree of social adaptation of our patients, noted in the majority of patients, is the key to a good labor prospect.

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JOBS AND PROVOCATION OF MECHANIZATION IN COMMUNAL COLLECTIVE MANAGEMENT

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Abstract: Many accept that Communal Collective Management is immaterial and awful for organizations, while others swear of its essential significance for the general development of neighborhood and worldwide economies. This paper examines the effect of innovation on communal ethics and collective duty. Organizations like GE and Nike direct assets and techniques to reinforce the climate and neighborhood and worldwide networks. Through improving instruction projects and putting resources into innovation, these organizations endeavor to satisfy their collective obligations to numerous communities. Companies utilize communal collective duty to construct a standing and famous brand name. Through innovation, the world's economy is synchronized. Making and sharing innovation upgrades the world's efficiency and economy, fundamentally in light of the fact that non-industrial nations are unequipped for putting much in innovative work. As the imbue ment of innovation adds to the development of the worldwide economy, the inquiry stays how much the mechanical discoveries make moral and good concerns while investigating new boondocks, and how much researchers think about the collective and moral results when testing and exploring.

Keywords: Collective, instruction, innovation, morals, moral, cloning, engineered, and development.

Introduction

Communal collective duty's actual importance is disappearing. The center has moved from turning into a decent communal resident - who is collectively capable and responsible to the general public and the climate to an apparatus many communal use to deal with their picture, image, and notoriety. CSR isn't modest, as per Double the Donation 2018 examination, The fundamental target of For-benefit associations is to expand the abundance of their investors. The inquiry remains, for what reason to turn out to be collectively mindful - knowing its significant expense, the answer is: on the grounds that it pays. The advantages surpass the expense; the organization's picture will improve, however the business will draw in more clients and possible financial backers, and connect with and hold beneficial representatives.

Direct TV's methodology has been in arrangement to their business; they have fused different instructive channels to their programming. A portion of these diverts are likewise accessible in Spanish to serve and arrive at Hispanic youngsters and families. Direct TV had additionally made and carried out PBS stations to which taking part schools may approach mentioned materials. Intel accepts that understudies - given the essential devices will be the up and coming age of creative masterminds. Intel made responsibilities to explicit

projects, for example, instructor preparing, greatness in science and math, innovation development at colleges, and local area learning. Intel has not restricted itself to the US, yet additionally broadened their help and came to internationally.

Contrasts between neighborhood conditions and global innovation – including collective contrasts, nearby government arrangements, and neighborhood and unfamiliar players to give some examples - are viewed as obstructions to the dispersion of worldwide innovation in neighborhood economies. Worldwide innovation and advancement change to neighborhood economies help support the financial expansion to these countries, keep up creation limit, and improve the quality existence of the number of inhabitants in these nations. The part of capital (human and monetary) aggregation and instruction are a higher priority than typically accepted, and R&D and training lead toward innovation development.

The United Nations attempted to unite sees concerning this issue - the US position to boycott human cloning with the end goal of creation and the position drove by a few European areas who looked to boycott human-cloning for creation purposes however permit logical examination to occur. UN ambassadors abandoned making and changing an arrangement law; the two sides acknowledged they would not get sufficient help to make universal ratification. The inquiry remains whether science is liable for making collective issues, or is it individuals who control science and misuse innovation.

Conclusion

Mechanization is a vital segment of obligation to communal collective duty. Research and development and developments add to the development of the nearby and worldwide

economies as it decides how people and partnerships cooperate and advance. The general public everywhere is liable for investigating the unfathomable wilderness while adjusting the longing to develop with all good and moral issues that identify with securing life and protecting the climate.

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EVOLUTION OF PROPERTIES OF IRRIGATED GRASSLAND SOILS

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Abstract: This article discusses the change in the mechanical, physical and chemical properties of irrigated grassland soils of the Mirzachul oasis during irrigation. The regularities of evolutionary processes in soil were analyzed.

keywords: soil, mechanical composition, absorption capacity, calcium, magnesium, sodium, potassium, evolution, irrigation.

Introduction

Soil evolution is one of the basic issues of contemporary soil science. As a result of studying the evolutionary processes taking place in the soil, it is possible to predict the events that can occur in the properties of the soil.

Numerous scientific researches have been carried out on the transformation of soils as a result of person activity, i.e. development, irrigation. Including M.L. Sizemskaya [1] aimed to study the dynamics of changes in soils as a result of natural and human factors. At the same time, the greatest attention is paid to the comparison of such indicators as changes in soil reclamation, i.e. dynamics of the groundwater level, increasing mineralization.

V.I. Taburkin [2] published an article on the methodological analysis of the contemporary concept of soil evolution. This article explains concepts such as “soil development”, “soil evolution” and “soil self-development”. Definitions given by the various authors to the above concepts have been analyzed and it has been pointed out that there are no general opinions.

A.M. Rusanov et al. [3] studied the evolution of saline meadow-black soils, which were irrigated for 50 years and then stopped. The basic changes in the physical and physicochemical properties of the soil are noted. It was observed that the level of mineralization of groundwater increased by 3 times, the amount of sodium increased as a result of rising groundwater.

According to Sh.M. Turdimetov [4] analyzed and compared the evolutionary processes of the soils of the old and newly irrigated parts of Mirzachul. The regularities of changes in the agrochemical and agrophysical properties of the soil as a result of development and irrigation have been studied, and possible evolutionary processes have been predicted.

According to E.I. Ergina [5] believes that two factors influencing soil evolution should be considered. These are: soil change and soil development.

He analyzed data on soil evolution and showed that evolutionary materials also differ due to the complex structure of the soil.

According to Sh.M. Turdimetov et al. [6] conducted experiments to improve the agrochemical properties of the soils of the Mirzachul oasis by planting various secondary crops.

According to A.E. and Bayshanova, B.Sh, the Kedelbaevs identified factors influencing the change in soil properties. It was revealed that the change (decrease) in the amount of

humus in the desert and gray earth regions is different. It was noted that the rate of depletion of humus in the desert area is high.

To determine the evolutionary processes in the soil, we analyzed the results of the changes that occurred in 1994 after 25 years of repeated felling by the author on the irrigated meadow soils of the T. Gulamov massif Saykhunabad region.

The size of particles larger than 0.25 mm is about 0.3-1.0%. The particle size of 0.25–0.1 mm is up to 20%. Particles of 0.1–0.05 mm are not evenly distributed along the cross section of the soil. One of the main properties of gray soils is the predominance of large dust particles in their mechanical composition. The content of large dust particles in these sections was 35-50%.

The increase in the duration of irrigation has led to a slight aggravation of the mechanical composition of the soil. This was especially due to the increase in the amount of large dust particles (0.01–0.05 mm). In the driving layer we can see that its content has increased by up to 6 per cent compared to the initial period.

Changes in the absorption capacity and composition of the soil were also studied. The soil absorption capacity in the soil sections was 13 mg / eq, an increase of 8%. The amount of absorbed calcium was 48.72 percent and the amount of magnesium was 40.81 percent. That is, with a decrease in the amount of calcium by 10 percent, the proportion of magnesium increased to 3 percent. In the lower layers, a decrease in the proportion of calcium and an increase in the proportion of magnesium were also observed. According to these indicators, we can observe an increase in the proportion of both sodium and potassium.

Conclusion

As the duration of irrigation increases, the mechanical composition of the soil becomes heavier. As the duration of irrigation increases, the texture of the soil becomes heavier. This is due to the spread of turbid particles during irrigation.

Irrigation with various levels of mineralized water can also lead to changes in the composition of salts, resulting in changes in the amount and composition of absorbed cations.

Information on the absorption capacity and its composition is significant in such activities as the establishment of standards for the application of fertilizers, planning of chemical reclamation processes.

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PROSPECTIVE DIRECTIONS OF CIVIL SOCIETY IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: The article reveals the prospects for the development of civil society in Uzbekistan and analyzes the problems of the development of legal consciousness and legal values in modern society, identifies important structural and material differences between law and law, which is one of the main components of law.

Keywords: civil society, legal consciousness, legal values, standard, common duty, consolidation.

Introduction

The importance of political and legal socialization of the individual in civil society is undeniable. The process of political and legal socialization seems to have two interrelated and interdependent sides. On the one hand, civil society itself creates a politically socialized individual, assigning him the role of a passive assimilator of the political experience accumulated by humanity. On the other hand, a person builds himself and adapts to the goal, adapts to the socio-political conditions of life, often trying to change them in accordance with his own interests. Moreover, the process of political and legal socialization is not limited in time and continues throughout a person's life, regardless of his wishes. At the same time, a person acquires political and legal norms and values very

selectively because of their specific beliefs, speculative and practical political and legal knowledge and their own political participation (which has not always been successful).

Civil society is characterized by a high degree of self-organization based on economic, socio-political and other systems of regulation, but given the complexity, depth and efficiency of this society, the inconsistency of its development cannot exist outside the state and legal influence. With the development of civilization, along with the assertion of the ideas of humanity and freedom, there is a dependence of a person on powerful, constantly increasing social forces - economy, power, ideology.

Social and legal regulation is a special influence exerted by the law as a special regulator and institutional regulator. The specificity of this impact is reflected in its purposefulness, system of legal instruments and effectiveness. However, only social relations are included in the law, which require not only legal influence, but are also objectively regulated by law.

The Main Findings and Results

The value of law is its special qualities - normativity, common duty, formal trust, etc., which make it a necessary and more effective means of social and normative regulation. Legal norms are defined (sanctioned) by the state as mandatory requirements for all citizens, and the fact of their universality is the most important motive for compliance with the law. The law influences the processes of social development as a complex, structured and dynamic social system that works with a high degree of efficiency.

Laws legally guarantee the implementation of the principles of social structure - humanism, equality, social justice, democracy. At the same time, along with the achievements of social development, a higher level of implementation of these ideas of social development will be ensured. Here, the goals, hopes and principles of civil society

find their civilized expression in a system of stable, trustworthy laws, their interaction with the entire system of social and regulatory regulation is increasingly strengthening, which allows the formation of civil society institutions.

As a result of the analysis of the problems of the development of legal consciousness and legal values in modern society, it is important to identify important structural and material differences between law and law, which is one of the main components of law. Achieving the rationality of the social structure through the consolidation and, to a certain extent, the combination of various social (class, national, private) interests determines the overall significance of law as a state, socially necessary regulator of relations in society. There is always a need for legal regulation, but this is especially felt in the context of the changing realities of life, the emergence of new directions of relations that require discipline, or the acceleration of the dynamics of social processes. People in any society are accustomed to living in accordance with the reliable and reasonable principle of the law, and not in accordance with the circumstances, as it has been confirmed by many studies in this area. Legal behavior, on the one hand, and positive law, on the other, in turn, are factors in the development and change of the legal culture of society. However, in modern society, both of them give an ambiguous or even negative direction to the development of public legal consciousness and legal culture.

Quasi-democratic forms of state power and the practice of the political system of state administration today lead to the development of negative social reactions of avoidance, alienation and nihilism among the masses, who are especially distrustful of the rule of law, the possibility of legal protection and is the sphere of legal relations for which claims arise.

The inconsistency of the legal structure makes double demands on the legal behavior of citizens in general. On the one hand, the necessary conditions are created in the field of going to court and social initiative is encouraged, on the other hand, opportunities for avoiding the liability of various legal entities are expanding, legal uncertainty and regulatory confusion lead to social irritation, increased bureaucracy, corruption and crime.

The results of the study confirm the high relevance and practical importance of studying legal values in the legal consciousness of citizens and legal relations of modern society with the predominance of legal nihilism and the absence of institutionalization of democratic legal relations. A more effective and least studied aspect of the problem, which requires further development, is the study of dialectical connections between the legal values of various social groups - legal consciousness - legal behavior. With the formation of new value foundations and a new type of legal registration of social development of society, another important direction should appear, less important from the point of view of the importance of translating legal culture in the formation of legal education. culture lends both a philosophical and a generational dimension to this problem. Elimination of legal nihilism and deviations in the field of legal thinking, compensation for distortions caused by historical errors, reliance on the best in domestic legal traditions and a radical rejection of the worst of them are necessary conditions for the normalization of legitimacy. To fully meet the challenges of future research, it is also important to determine the ability of people to adapt culturally to new legal standards and values.

Civil society is an area where people are free and pursue their interests in the process of civilized interaction. In such a society, people are given the opportunity to enter into social relations without government control. The collapse of the USSR significantly changed the conditions for the formation of civil society on a global scale. The new

direction of political forces in Central Asia in general and in Uzbekistan in particular has created opportunities for democratic reforms. In this political environment, any autonomous public organizations arose that began to give way to themselves in the political system. Over the past two decades, the environment of open political regimes has created a very favorable environment for strengthening civil society. Such regimes provide a legal and regulatory framework that protects the rights of social groups; they enable civil society organizations to have active media that enable them to communicate their values and programs to the public; and political elites behave in ways that help them embrace social diversity and political differences. For this reason, F. Starr believes that the Central Asian states are not a fertile ground for the development of civil society, and gives the following reasons:

1. The hierarchical nature of their cultures has created a tradition in which power is transferred from the top down, not from the bottom up (from citizens to governors).
2. The clan foundations of the social system do not allow people to unite in voluntary associations that form the basis of civil society.
3. The Soviet government formed subordinates, not free citizens from the people.
4. Post-Soviet practice has only strengthened the hierarchical principle. Volunteer initiatives are now not only regulated, but also controlled by the state at the local level.
5. Laws, to a greater or lesser extent, permitting and protecting civil society are not supported by judicial practice that ensures their application [1].

To claim civil society as a Western invention is to completely ignore its historical context. But even if we declare civil society as the “western dream”, it is impossible to go so far as to argue that civil society has been understood in the same way throughout history [2]. Studying the history of Muslim countries, orientalist have pointed out that the

absence of civil society as a whole is the main reason why attempts to create democratic institutions there have not been crowned with success. However, in the 1990s, when civil society (non-governmental organizations) began to emerge in Central Asia under the influence of an atmosphere of recovery, this did not happen by accident. In other societies, the institutions we are talking about have evolved over many generations, but Central Asian societies have their own traditions rooted in the past.

There is another form of civil society that dates back to ancient times and was rebuilt after the collapse of the Soviet Union. True, some authors believe that in Soviet times, due to the absolute domination of the state, civil society did not exist in any form, because not only politics and economics, but all aspects of life and society, including religion, education, social relations, art, culture, history obeyed and served the purposes of control from the center. However, despite this suppression, local problems were always resolved, religious ceremonies were carried out, and so on. The evidence supporting this claim suggests a second wave of theoretical discussion of civil society issues. This began in the second half of the 1990s, when the Western context of civil society activities attracted the attention of debates.

Scholars of the Islamic world have often found civil society at the beginning of rethinking as a concept and phenomenon of social life. If we proceed from the concept of civil society in the West, based on the ideas of free elections, free media and a market economy, we must recognize that civil society in Central Asia must be created from scratch. In other words, there was nothing harmful in building civil society in Central Asia.

Conclusion

For centuries, the sacred religion Islam, as the social and religious consciousness of the Uzbek people, has been an important part of the national spiritual culture, and in the modern society of independent Uzbekistan it is one of the greatest national and state values. In our country, the moral and spiritual values of Islam, the main Muslim holidays of Ramadan and Eid al-Adha are invaluable, as well as its educational role in introducing the ideas of enlightenment and humanity in a modern civilized society. For example, the Uzbek people celebrate Ramadan in an atmosphere of friendship, love and appreciation for Islamic values, which mainly includes spreading spirituality, visiting parents and relatives, doing good deeds and supporting those in need.

Thus, the goal of Islam is to ensure the further development of human culture and form a qualitatively new basis for human existence. Thus, the fundamental basis of Islam is a unique set of knowledge, skills, ideas, principles and norms.

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CHANGES IN LABOR MARKET INDICATORS IN A PANDEMIC

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Abstract: This article analyzes the state of the labor market and examines changes in its indicators in a pandemic. It clearly outlines the processes that affect labor market indicators, the systemic problems that arise in this regard, and the factors that lead to them. The Government has also detailed the measures that need to be taken during the pandemic and in the context of rising unemployment in the labor market. As a result of the analysis, well-founded proposals were put forward to address the identified problems, reduce unemployment and increase employment.

Keywords: labor market, labor resources, economically active population, unemployment, employment, pandemic, government programs, new jobs, labor resource balance, systematic analysis.

Introduction

The spread of coronavirus infection, to one degree or another, has affected the way of life of people in almost all countries of the world. Even some regions are experiencing a serious crisis.

The situation in the global labor market and the problem of unemployment will remain a matter of serious concern, not only during and after the pandemic, but also when serious measures are taken to improve the situation.

Due to the pandemic, the global labor market is facing the worst crisis since the Second World War. According to the International Labor Organization, quarantine measures have led to temporary, total or partial closings of businesses, which affect 81 percent of the world's workforce, or 2.7 billion people.

The longest working day has been reduced in Arab countries (8.1%). This means that 5 million people will lose their jobs. In terms of unemployment, Europe ranks second (7.8% or 12 million people), and the third place is occupied by the Asia-Pacific region (7.2% or 125 million people).

The Main Findings and Results

Analysts at the International Labor Organization (ILO) warn that there is a risk of job losses or working hours in areas that employ an additional 1.25 billion people. The most affected were the hotel business, the service sector, wholesale and retail trade. The least affected areas are education, health care, utilities, agriculture, public services and public safety. Construction, financial and insurance services are at moderate risk of a pandemic in the labor market. The risk of harm to the labor market in the arts and entertainment, transportation, hospitality and tourism, real estate, manufacturing, wholesale and retail trade, and car repair services is moderate.

It is possible that more than 1.5 billion people around the world may be left without life. Workers in the manufacturing and food industries are expected to fall into this category. The coronavirus pandemic is affecting the informal sector of the global labor market. The first month of the crisis resulted in a 60 percent reduction in the number of informal workers worldwide.

According to the UN, the crisis could leave at least 195 million people unemployed. Analysts say the global economy is facing historic unemployment rates.

The crisis caused by the pandemic holds great promise for the development of information technology, especially telecommuting and education, and delivery services. In other words, all spheres that are active in self-isolation are developing.

However, sooner or later the pandemic will end. The economy will continue to grow, but the effects of the pandemic crisis may take longer to heal than the virus itself.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, labor authorities regularly conduct social surveys, based on the results of which the level of employment and unemployment is analyzed. In particular, at the end of 2020, these bodies conducted another public opinion poll in 101 cities and regions of the country according to the methodology developed on the basis of the recommendations of the International Labor Organization. It was attended by 490 citizens' self-government bodies, 4.9 thousand households and 25.9 thousand citizens.

The study found that quarantine measures aimed at preventing the spread of coronavirus infection during the COVID-19 pandemic have had a significant impact on the labor market.

According to preliminary data, the number of labor resources amounted to 19 million people, an increase of 0.6% compared to the same period in 2019. However, due to the negative impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the activities of business entities, the number of employed in the economy decreased by 5% or 671 thousand people compared to the same period last year and amounted to 12.7 million people.

The number of people employed in the formal sector of the economy amounted to 5.5 million people, which is 0.2% or 12.4 thousand people less than in the same period last year.

At the same time, due to restrictive measures to prevent the spread of coronavirus infection, the number of individual entrepreneurs decreased by 167.5 thousand (46.4%)

compared to the same period last year, and 131.2 thousand unemployed were involved in paid public works, which helped to prevent a sharp decline in the number of employment in the official sectors of the economy.

According to the study, the number of people who went to work abroad amounted to 2 million people (a decrease by 553.2 thousand people compared to the same period last year and by 232.1 thousand people compared to the results of the 1st quarter of 2020).

The number of people employed in the informal sector (excluding labor migrants working abroad) decreased by 2.1% or 105.3 thousand compared to last year and amounted to 5.1 million people. At the same time, the number decreased:

- temporary one-time and seasonal workers (decreased by 108.4 thousand);
- employees of family enterprises and entrepreneurs without employment registration (87.6 thousand);
- entrepreneurs operating without registration and permits (110.6 thousand).

At the same time, due to an increase in the number of people sitting at home during the quarantine period, and a sharp increase in the amount of subsidies from the Employment Assistance Fund for the Development of Farms, the number of people employed in dekhkan and wild subsidiary plots increased by 201.1 thousand people.

Granting rights to business entities and self-employed citizens to take into account their work experience and enjoy benefits makes it possible to reduce the share of employment in the informal sector.

The number of economically inactive population in the country increased by 4.5% compared to the corresponding period of 2019. This figure increased during the survey due to the fact that representatives of business and services temporarily suspended their

activities during the quarantine measures and chose not to engage in other activities, intending to resume after the introduction of restrictions.

According to the results of the first half of this year, the unemployment rate in the country amounted to 13.2%. This figure was 9.1% for the same period in 2019. The total number of people in need of work is 1.9 million.

It is worth noting that quarantine in the country was introduced on March 16, 2020. Before the introduction of quarantine, the country's unemployment rate was 9.3%, and the total number of unemployed was about 1.4 million.

In January-June 2020, in order to mitigate the negative impact of the pandemic on the labor market, labor authorities provided services to 588.2 thousand unemployed. In particular: - 501.1 thousand people were provided with jobs through permanent employment and participation in public works; - trained 15.0 thousand unemployed; - 27.0 thousand unemployed received unemployment benefits in the amount of 10.1 billion soums at the expense of the Employment Promotion Fund.

Also through subsidies from the Employment Promotion Fund: - 24.8 thousand people became members of personal subsidiary plots; - 15 thousand people became members of agricultural, sewing and handicraft cooperatives; - 3 thousand people were involved in entrepreneurship; - material assistance was provided to 2.3 thousand unemployed in need of social protection.

Conclusion

The aforementioned measures taken by the state serve to alleviate labor market problems, support the unemployed, provide employment for those in need, and prevent income decline in the event of a pandemic.

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PUBLISHING IN UZBEKISTAN: PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS

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Abstract: This article discusses publishing houses in Uzbekistan. The article also reveals its problematic aspects and solutions. In recent years, important issues on the agenda have been reforms of an effective and innovative approach to the development of our industry, efforts to increase the share of information, publication and print, which is an important area of public policy. Over the years, many organizations in the system, especially publishing houses, have turned into businesses with no legal basis, financial base or reputation.

Since these enterprises were often viewed only as producers, their important role in social and political life, spiritual and ideological issues was forgotten.

Keywords: Publishing, book, editing, number, editor, proofreader, polygraph, book graphics.

Introduction

Information of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 13, 2017 No PP-3271 “On comprehensive measures to develop the system of publishing and distribution of book products, increase and promote the culture of reading and reading” and February 2, 2019 “Information under the Presidential Administration of the Republic of Uzbekistan and Resolution No. PD-4151 On the organization of the activities of the

Agency for Mass Communications” proved that the sector needs to be reformed, the system needs to be updated, and there are still enough problems. The need to modernize the information sphere and to provide our literary-loving people, especially young people and children, with high-quality book products has been on the agenda.

In recognition of the extensive work that has been done so far on these issues as a spokesperson for the field of literature, spirituality, publishing, let us make some suggestions and comments on the development of the industry.

Indeed, the contest “The best reader” initiated by the President, the project “1 million books for each region”, the process of implementation of the Five Initiatives in Boka district, new and effective actions in the country and many other socio-cultural events , proved how close and necessary the field of literature, publishing and printing is to life.

The Main Findings and Results

Currently’s audience is different. Today's reader doesn't believe in yesterday's fluffy buns. It is necessary to raise the prestige of book publishers, the number and weight of books they publish, their image and position in the eyes of authors to a new level. Circulation of the rarest works (even the books of famous writers such as Firdavsi, Saadi, Hafiz, Rudaki, Rumi, Jami, Navoi, Babur, Kadyri, Cholpon, Oybek, Zulfiya, A. Aripov, E. Vahidov) is still 5-10 the fact that there are no more than a thousand, that publishers often forget about the level and quality of the financial situation, that there is no specific procedure for pen fees, that the customer or publishers at their own expense do not respect the publishers, is a reality.

To overcome these problems, it is advisable to pay attention to the following.

First, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Public procurement for publishing houses in the system should be organized under the auspices of the Agency for Information and Mass Communications under the Ministry of Radio and Television. The state is the main reformer. His ideological policy is also broadcast primarily through the media and books. In this regard, it is necessary to introduce a unified state order for the publication of books with the active participation of the Republican Spiritual Center, the Writers' Union, the Youth Union, the Ministries of Higher and Secondary Special Education, Public Education, etc. Preschool education and culture. Only then will it be possible to form publishing plans based on orders, to bring the number of copies of our classical and modern literature to at least 40-50 thousand and evenly distribute them in places - regional libraries, educational institutions, in short, to the population as a whole. At the same time, the product becomes cheaper.

This is to ensure that the Agency manages and strictly controls the process of receiving government orders and distributing them for execution among publishers in the system. Simply put, the Agency determines the amount of funds allocated by the state and the volume of publications, and also monitors the execution of the order.

Second, it is well known that there is no such thing as a “public publishing house” or a “private publishing house” for the reader. They just take the book in their hands as a real reality. Today, the low level of books published by state publishing houses or private enterprises, the large number of errors and omissions, the fact that counterfeit products still exist, directly lead to a negative assessment of the image of the industry. In order to

prevent such cases, it is necessary to establish an Editorial Board or Arts Council consisting of qualified specialists and well-known artists in all publishing houses, regardless of the form of ownership, and to increase the responsibility for publishing books on this basis.

Third, the development of any state is closely linked to the upbringing of the younger generation. This issue is even more profound in the essence of the Five Initiatives put forward by the Head of State. Therefore, special attention should be paid to the fate of the newspaper “Tong Yulduzi”, magazines “Guncha” and “Gulkhan”. Because these publications, which lay the first ideological foundation in the hearts of the younger generation, are an important part of the policy of educating children and adolescents, informing them. Currently, these publications are under the jurisdiction of the Ministry of Public Education and are practically abandoned. However, in fact, they should be at the disposal of the Agency, and these publications should become one of the main means of propaganda in the education of the younger generation.

Fourth, our fast-growing industry, especially the training of skilled workers for publishing houses, remains open. It is well known that the Tashkent Institute of Textile and Light Industry has a faculty that trains printing specialists and the Tashkent Printing College under the Agency. But these are only grown by printing professionals. The most necessary specialists for publishing houses, such as editor, technical editor, proofreader, are still recruited at the expense of journalists or philologists. It takes two to three years for journalists and philologists to adjust to publishing. Pages, on the other hand, are often self-taught. However, publishing is an activity that requires special knowledge and skills. With this in mind, based on the experience of developed countries (Russia, USA, Germany, Japan, South Korea, Turkey, Poland), I think it is time for us to

open a publishing and printing institute. It is possible to create a new institute on the basis of the Faculty of Printing at the Tashkent Institute of Textile and Light Industry, the Department of Book Graphics at the Institute of Art and Design named after K. Behzod, the Department of Publishing and Editing at the University of Journalism and Mass Communications. At the same time, representatives of all three areas will be trained in one place, and the possibility of providing high-quality and ready-made personnel to publishing houses will increase, and representatives of these three specialties will be formed together during the training period.

Conclusion

In short, currently, after joining the publishing house, employees are mainly undergoing retraining for publishing. This negatively affects the quality of work and the development of the industry. Also, if such an institute is established, it will be possible to organize 6-month retraining courses for existing publishing professionals. Considering that such an institution will be the only one in Central Asia, on this basis it will be possible to admit students from neighboring countries, train them and invest in this area.

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HYDRAULIC STRUCTURES OF MIRZACHUL NATURAL AREA AND ITS IMPACT ON THE ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract: This article examines the morphometric dimensions of hydraulic structures built in the Mirzachul natural region and analyzes its impact on the environment.

Keywords: Mirzachul natural area, Khanbandi dam, hydraulic structure, reservoirs, environment, landscape.

Introduction

In order to improve the water supply of irrigated lands in Mirzachul natural area, a number of warehouses, streams and collectors have been built. It has been 10 centuries since the first hydraulic structure was built in the territory of the natural region. The Khanbandi Dam was built by the Karakhanids at the end of the 10th century on the Khanbandi Mountain of the Nurata system. According to experts, the Khanbandi Dam is the oldest irrigation facility built by the peoples of Central Asia - the ancient Turan. This dam has been preserved to this day.

The Khanbandi Dam is built of prickly granite blocking the entrance to the gorge. The lower part of the Khanbandi Dam is 24.35 meters shorter and the upper part is 51.75 meters. The height of the dam is 15.25 meters, which when filled with water forms a reservoir up to 1.5 km in length.

This hydraulic structure, built by our ancestors in ancient times to collect water, can still be used today. For example, it allows the collection of streams and flood waters that flow uselessly in the spring. To do this, it is necessary to build small dams, similar to the Khanbandi dam, given the volume of runoff.

Several reservoirs have been built in the Mirzachul natural area to regulate the flow and provide water to irrigated lands. Examples of such reservoirs are Jizzakh, Qorovultepa, Zaamin, Arnasay, Novka, Sardoba, Khojamushkent and Sarmishsay. About 400,000 hectares of land in the Mirzachul natural region are being irrigated with the help of reservoirs.

The Main Findings and Results

The Jizzakh reservoir, originally built in a natural region, began construction in 1963 and was completed in 1973 on the Yayilmasay cliff, 9 km east and southeast of Jizzak. The Jizzakh Reservoir overlooks the Syrdarya Basin and receives water from the Sangzor River and the Tuyatortar Canal. According to the morphometric parameters of the reservoir, the area is 12.7 km², the average depth is 26 m, the width is 5.1 km, the length is 3.3 km, the height of the dam is 22 m and the capacity is 87.5 million m³. A canal was built to bring 25 m³ / sec of water to the reservoir (9 km in length) and 10 m³ / sec to discharge water from the reservoir (15 km in length). The Jizzakh Reservoir is located in the Sharof Rashidov district and fully meets the water needs of 15,340 hectares of land and helps to irrigate more than 10,000 hectares of protected lands.

The Karavultepa reservoir was built in 1978 to improve the water supply to the southeast of the country. The Karavultepa reservoir has a capacity of 53 million m³ and receives water from the Tuyatortar canal on the Zarafshan River. The reservoir supplies water to Gallaorol and Bakhmal districts.

In the lower reaches of the Zaamin River in 1979, the Zaamin reservoir with a capacity of 52.1 million m³ was built. 40% of the water demand of the Zaamin region is provided by the Zaamin reservoir. Therefore, it is possible to develop measures for the rational use of water resources with information on the annual performance of the reservoir (see Table 1).

Table 1
Morphometric indicators of the Zaamin reservoir

Nº	The size	Indicators
1	Full project size	52,1 mln m ³
2	Scope of use	34,0 mln m ³

3	Dead volume	15 mln m ³
4	The size of the reservoir	3,2 km ²
5	The width of the reservoir	Maximum-700 m (average-350 m)
6	The depth of the reservoir	Maximum-73.5 m (average-17.7 m)

Zaamin requires more water than the established limit due to the expansion of irrigated areas in Zaamin, Lilakuye, Chorvador, Beshbulak, Beshkubi and many other farms that receive water from the reservoir. Therefore, the demand for water increases sharply during the summer months, and the problem of water scarcity arises. In order to prevent this problem, it is necessary to reconsider the crop types of farms and switch to planting or drip irrigation of crops that require as little water as possible.

The Arnasay reservoir was built in the eastern part of the Aydar-Arnasay lake system, at the confluence with the Chordara reservoir. The Arnasay reservoir was commissioned in 2003 and has a water capacity of 730 million m³. Arnasay reservoir supplies water to Mirzachul, Dustlik and Arnasay districts with the help of 3 pumping stations.

Undoubtedly, the largest reservoir built on the plains of Central Asia, that is, in the Mirzachul natural region, is the Sardoba reservoir. Construction of the reservoir began in 2010 at the site of the central branch of the South Mirzachul Canal and was completed in 2018. If we look at the morphometric dimensions of the huge hydraulic structure, the area is 58.7 km², water capacity is 922 million m³, maximum depth is 35 m, length is 33 km, height is 33 m. The Sardoba reservoir is expected to irrigate 146.2 thousand hectares of land in Akaltin and Mirzaabad districts of Syrdarya region, Arnasay, Mirzachul and Dustlik districts of Jizzakh region. Construction of a 15-megawatt mini-hydropower plant has also begun at the Sardoba Reservoir.

On the morning of May 1, 2020, a dam broke in the Sardoba reservoir. As a result of the flood, settlements and crops in Sardoba, Oqoltin and Mirzaabad districts were damaged. Buildings, roads, communications were destroyed. More than 60,000 people were evacuated from 22 villages in three districts.

Such a tragedy in the reservoir, called “Construction of the Century”, requires a comprehensive study and analysis of the Sardoba reservoir and its impact on the environment. It is no secret that any large-scale construction takes into account the benefits to the economy in the first place. The impact of construction on the surrounding landscape is often underestimated. As a result, the balance between nature and society is disturbed.

In addition to reservoirs, small settlements such as Novka, Khojamushkent and Sarmishsay have been built in the Mirzachul natural zone (see Table 2).

Table 2

Information about reservoirs and floodplains of the Mirzachul natural region.

τ/p	Reservoirs and floodplains	Built year	Source	Area, km ²	project capacity, mln.m ³
1	Jizzakh Reservoir	1973	Sangzar, Tuyatortar	12,4	87,5
2	Karavultepa Reservoir	1978	Tuyatortar	8,50	50
3	Zaamin Reservoir	1979	Zominsay	1,4	52,1
4	Arnasay reservoir	2003	Chordara Reservoir	140	730
5	Sardoba Reservoir	2018	South Mirzachul canal	58,7	922
5	Novka downpour room	1980	Rocks and floods	0,60	5
6	Khojamushkent downpour room	1981	Springs and floods	0,58	5
7	Sarmishsoy	1988	Springs and floods	0,56	5

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Source: Syrdarya-Zarafshan ITXBQ melorative expedition data, 2019

The aforementioned reservoirs have different effects on the surrounding landscapes, as well as on the water supply of irrigated lands. In particular, as a result of water absorption in the reservoir, groundwater levels have risen, soil salinity has increased and in some places there have been swamps.

Conclusion

In short, the study and assessment of changes in the landscapes of the Mirzachul natural region under the influence of the reservoir remains one of the most significant problems in Uzbekistan today. The reservoir is affected by changes in the environmental landscape components (groundwater, microclimate, soil, flora and fauna).

The construction of a reservoir in the Mirzachul natural area has a different effect on the surrounding landscape and agricultural land. The assessment of the impact of the reservoir requires the development and implementation of emergency response to man-made and natural disasters, taking into account the characteristics of the natural environment.

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EDUCATION ON THE CAUSE OF PARENT COMPLEX' TRAGIC FATE

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Abstract

Parent complex the King is an extraordinary Greek misfortune by Sophocles. Aristotle at any point accepting it as the example to clarify his outlook in his renowned Poetics. The pursuers consistently are contacted profoundly by the hopeless destiny of Parent complex, yet who causes the event of the awful sins? Parent complex needs to escape from his horrendous destiny, be that as it may, very much like a manikin of God, understands God's arrangement.

Keywords: Parent complex the King, a manikin, through and through freedom, destiny.

Introduction

Parent complex the King is quite possibly the most renowned plays of old Greek. His creator Sophocles is one of the three biggest Greek deplorable writers. This play has an

ideal plot. It recounts the story that the youngster Parent complex would grow up to execute his dad and wed his mom. Subsequent to hearing his forecasted destiny, Parent complex made an honest effort to dodge this thing occurring. The very activities taken to battle against this destiny, be that as it may, drove him to satisfy the prediction. Misfortune is an impersonation of people who are over the regular level. Sophocles' misfortune additionally follows this guideline. He shows the perusers an incredible heartbreaking saint, who cherishes his kin, regards his archetype and acknowledges his obligation courageously for his wrongdoings. Parent complex can't escape from God's grip, regardless of what exertion he has made. It appears to be that he is only a manikin of god who attempts to demonstrate his control over people. As in his article "Parent complex Rex: The awful Rhythm of Action", Francis Fergusson referenced "In one sense Parent complex endures powers he can neither control nor comprehend, the manikin of destiny". In the entire play, Parent complex is consistently battle to get away from the acknowledgment of the prediction, yet regardless of what he did, God's arrangement came to be valid finally. GOD'S PLAN

To show his transcendence, God make his arrangement. He originally let individuals realize what might occur and afterward let it occurred. The prophet was known even at the principal snapshot of the introduction of Parent complex. In this course, the helpless Parent complex with the high character become the manikin as an apparatus to understand God's arrangement. Regardless of what implies Parent complex used to change this prophet, all end up being to no end. For what reason did God do this? William Ellis said in a talk Reading for Writing " Parent complex represents Greek residents, who

don't trust God's insight and think they have a higher knowledge than God in their obviousness". It is something "from the most noteworthy motives", the casualty must choose the option to get an outright outcome. To frustrate the prescience, Parent complex' folks secured his feet and advised shepherd to slaughter him. In light of the shepherd's pity, be that as it may, Parent complex

PARENT COMPLEX' FREE WILL

"The occasions of this play shows a hidden relationship of man's through and through freedom existing inside the astronomical request or destiny and that both the ideas of destiny and unrestrained choice At the start of the misfortune, Parent complex made numerous moves which prompted his defeat, since he might have trusted that the plague will end and he could tranquilly examined the homicide [6]. While as a result of his duty and the incredible love for his kin, Parent complex decide to be with his kin to battle against the calamities and to do everything to end the plague.

Parent complex is incredible, not in uprightness of an extraordinary common situation—for his common position is a figment which will evaporate like a fantasy—yet in excellence of his internal strength: strength Parent complex is extraordinary on the grounds that he acknowledges the obligation regarding every one of his demonstrations, including those which are equitably generally ghastly, through abstractly guiltless. Kirszner and Mandell remarked that the hero ought to resemble most of us, just having some shortcoming or blemish. In Parent complex the King, Parent complex is additionally having some

shortcoming or defect surely, while as concerning his last torment, the existence of Parent complex appears, even right off the bat, has effectively been orchestrated by God. That is his predetermination. His entire life is only a snare that God had intended to show his control over individual.

Conclusion

Parent complex' freedom of thought and God's arrangement both bring the event of the misfortune. Yet, in the entire course, regardless of what sort of unrestrained choice Parent complex take, it comes simply better to demonstrate the prophet. Contrasted and the destiny, the unrestrained choice shows so frail strength. What's more awful, this strength is simply to push the incident of unfortunate destiny. In the play, Parent complex shows more like a manikin, whose hands and feet were constrained by another person. Also, his destiny unavoidably was chosen by his regulator.

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HISTORY OF JIZZAKH OASIS – MOJARM

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Abstract: This article gives information about the history, traditional way of life, customs and traditions of the village of Mojarm in the Jizzakh oasis.

Keywords: Mojarm village, traditional way of life, customs and modern tourism.

Introduction

One of the branches of the Great Silk Road, passing through the northern part of the Nurata Mountains, is on the road connecting Tashkent, Jizzak, Nurata, Karmana, and then Bukhara, and Tajik villages with a history of more than two thousand years are on the right, this road is on the side.

“The village of Mojarm shines with a ruby at the foot of the Nurata Mountains. “Since ancient times, people have been engaged in agriculture, animal husbandry and handicrafts in this village, which is distinguished by its charming nature,” wrote Professor Y. Nurnazarov.

The Mojarm River is the longest and widest river in the Forish Mountains. It has a basin of 56² km and a length of 36 km. The people of Mojarm are engaged in agriculture as well as gardening. They deliver nuts to many parts of the country. Almonds, pistachios and cumin grow in Mojarm.

Ba Forish misli Mojarm dehai purfayzu ehson nest,

Zaminash bekanoru nozu ne'matho farovon nest.

Zamone to ba Fashtak mardumi bisyor mezistand,

Vale imro'z kamodam va mardumash pareshon nest

Namo faxr bo chunin xalqi tavono, tojiki Forish.

Forish is not a village of grace like Mojarm,

His lands are infinite and abundant. Before Pashto, many people lived there.

But currently I am a camouflage and people are not scattered

Namo is proud of the Tajik forish of such a powerful nation.

The village of Mojarm is famous for its unique tree - spruce, which is very rare in Central Asia. It is said that this tree was planted by Alexander the Great when he buried the late commanders. The Mojarm spruce was also planted by Alexander the Great. In any

case, it is a sign of antiquity. The spruce tree is 20 meters long and 24 meters in diameter.

Foreigners also come to see the tree.

Seeds-the largest villages

Nº	Villages	The main generations	Generational division
1	Porasht	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Qishloqi 2. Mahmazamoni 3. Qarovulbegi 4. Kalmaki 	
2	O'xum	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Albaki 2. Sulтони 3. Tabaqti 	Soqigi, Yorboy, Mullone'mati, Davlati, Arbobi, Qazigi Solekhboy, Aliboy, Odinaboy, Nehkmahmadi Mulloartuqi, Mulloniyozhi, Mullomusoi, Turbagi, Bobochagi
3	Hoyat	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ko'yiki 2. Nodirboboi 3. Dokhayiti 	

4	Mojarm	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Qunuqsoy 2. Xalachi 3. Xalachi 	<p>Mullofoi, Doabdulati, Dorifi, Qalmoqi, Qozigi Shomakhmadi, Do'stmakhmadi, Korvoni, Davlatboqigi, Boqigi, Kochaki Ashurmakhmadi, Mulloi, Domo'mini</p>
5	Sintab	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Mulloi 2. Sultonxuuseyni 	<p>Boqigi, Najmiddini, Solikhi, Tamuri, Khofizi Ayoni, Bayrami, Yodgori, Kurama, Eshmakhmadi</p>
6	Sob	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yoqubi 2. Sultonmurodi 3. Khayloi 4. Arbobi 	
7	Ej	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Qozigi 2. Arbobi 3. Mulloi 4. Shokhigi 5. Cholmagi 	<p>Mormo'ho, Lumlumakon, Dakhonyaloqikho Ashuri, Tabarbakitfon, Maliki Boqisoqiyon Zumradshokhi</p>

The traditions of Mojarm village are similar to those of other Tajik villages and Farishishs. In the village of Mojarm, home hotels are open. Foreign tourists are shown the

lifestyle and nationality of the local population on the example of ecotourism and ethnotourism.

The tourism potential of Mojarm village is very high and it is necessary to develop special plans for its development and implement it for rural development.

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FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN TAX INCENTIVES FOR INNOVATIVE ACTIVITIES

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Abstract: The article examines and analyzes the foreign experience of taxation of innovative activities. Currently, the leading industrial countries apply various types of tax incentives to stimulate innovation. The main principle of the Western system is that tax incentives are provided not to scientific organizations, but to enterprises and investors. Foreign experience in tax support for innovation provides Uzbekistan with guidelines that can and should be used in the formation of a system of tax incentives for the scientific and innovative sphere.

Keywords: innovative activity, tax incentives, incentives.

Introduction

The most important condition for the scientific and technological development of any state is state stimulation of the innovation market [1].

In the last years, researchers have been interested in the problems of the state's role in stimulating innovation. An important place in this policy is given to the tax measure. The introduction of tax incentives in most developed countries was prompted

by governments seeking to induce private businesses to become more involved in funding national research and development (R&D) projects.

In developed countries, the system of tax privileges and incentives has existed for a long time. In the post-World War II United States, tax legislation enacted rules aimed at creating a favourable environment for the development of R&D and innovation activities of firms. So, since 1954, there was a procedure for deducting from the taxable amount of expenditures for research and experiments in the current year or amortization of these expenses for a period of up to 5 years. In addition, additional tax privileges have been provided for educational and research expenditures in the public interest. Since 1981, the main method of tax incentives has been a tax credit for R&D (ie, exemption from taxation of a certain amount of R&D expenditures).

The Main Findings and Results

In Canada, tax incentives for innovation have been in place since the early 1960s. XX century, and since 1967, the country introduced a special system of grants to stimulate innovation in firms.

Japan has extensive experience in tax incentives for innovation. The country practices six different approaches to stimulate innovation:

- system of accelerated depreciation for scientific education (since 1954);
- tax discounts on development costs (since 1966);
- special benefits on the cost of purchasing foreign technology (since 1956);
- tax discounts on amounts paid for the use of foreign technology (since 1953);
- special tax rebates for the purchase of new imported equipment (since 1951);

-Tax relief on research expenditures (preferential rate is 20% of the amount of the increase in R&D expenditures compared to the highest amount spent for the specified purposes in any year after 1966).

In Sweden, the tax exemption for innovation has been in place since 1973. The tax-exempt amounts are equal to 10% of the firm's R&D costs, and there is a special 20% discount on the increase in research costs in a given year over the previous year.

In France, the system for stimulating innovation has been in effect since 1983 [2].

Currently, leading industrial countries apply various types of tax incentives that stimulate innovation, from research and investment tax credits, targeted investment and innovative tax incentives allocated for the execution of important orders, to programs and projects for the creation, implementation and use of R&D results for reconstruction of production [3].

All tax incentives can be subdivided into volumetric ones, i.e. proportional to the amount of costs incurred, and incremental, calculated depending on the increase in R&D costs in comparison with the base year or the average level for a certain period [4].

In the Netherlands, the volume discount applies only to the amount of the salaries of scientists and engineers engaged in R&D.

The incremental discount is based on the increase in R&D costs achieved by the company over the base year or period average.

France, Canada, the United States, and Taiwan use incremental tax incentives. The maximum incremental rate is 50% in France. In Canada, USA, Japan and Taiwan it is 20%.

A key element of any national incentive model is a reduction in corporate income tax.

The most universal profit tax benefit is the write-off of current accumulated R&D costs when determining the tax base, as well as accelerated depreciation of equipment used for R&D. Thus, enterprises operating with profit can reduce their taxable base by the amount of qualified R&D expenses incurred in the current year. In addition, a number of countries have rules that allow companies to deduct more funds from the tax base than spent on R&D.

The most typical types of tax benefits implemented in recent years by industrialized and newly industrialized countries include the following: tax credit; write-offs from the taxable base; deferred taxation (tax relief for depreciation and temporary discounts); deduction of R&D expenses incurred during the year from the annual corporate income [5].

The tax credit allows industrial firms to reduce the already accrued income tax by an amount equal to a certain percentage of the qualified R&D costs incurred.

As for the deferral of taxation, this type of tax incentives is intended to resolve problems that arise for enterprises that spend funds on R&D and purchase the equipment necessary for this, but have not yet received sufficient profit to use “their tax benefits” in full. [6].

An increase in the share of benefits that ensure a favourable innovative climate is a general trend. In the United States, there are more than a hundred benefits that enhance scientific and technological progress (STP). The main advantage of tax support is that incentives are not provided in advance, but as a reward for real innovation.

The main principle of the Western system is that tax incentives are provided not to scientific organizations, but to enterprises and investors. Incentives plus competition provide a strong demand for research and innovation. Regular monitoring of benefits

allows the state to purposefully stimulate innovative activity in priority sectors, to influence not only the structure and number of scientific and innovative organizations, but most importantly, the structure of production [7].

Each country implements its own set of benefits, the combination of which depends both on the goals and objects of incentives and on a number of factors and restrictions of a more general nature.

Conclusion

All this testifies to the fact that despite the widespread use of tax incentives by industrialized and newly industrialized countries, there are no standard "recipes" that include certain combinations and guarantee a positive effect today. National systems of tax incentives for science and technology are formed gradually, taking into account not only the accumulated world experience, but specific factors, conditions and restrictions, individual for each country. In this sense, the foreign experience of tax support for innovation activity represents only certain benchmarks for Uzbekistan, which can and should be used to form a system of tax incentives for the scientific and innovative sphere, adequate to the specific historical conditions and restrictions of Uzbekistan.

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THE EXPRESSION OF CONCEPTUAL UNITS OF HAPPINESS IN TERMS OF PARTS OF SPEECH

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Abstract: This article reveals how the binary opposition of happiness and unhappiness is expressed by parts of speech. Analyzing the specific features of binary oppositions requires reference to the whole language corpus that reflects them. Therefore, the analysis of the different features between the synonymous series of means of verbalization of the concepts of happiness and unhappiness also reflects a specific aspect of our research work.

Keywords: concept, binary opposition, happiness, unhappiness, parts of speech

Introduction

Analyzing the lexical meanings of a word is a research method focused on word semantics and also involves identifying language units related concept. Analyzing the specific features of binary oppositions requires reference to the whole language corpus that reflects them [9. 140-153]. Therefore, the analysis of the different features between the synonymous series of means of verbalization of the concepts of happiness and unhappiness also reflects a specific aspect of our research work.

The conceptual field units of happiness in terms of parts of speech include the following words, which are synonymous:

Forms of adjectives and adverbs: happy, blissful, fortunate, fortunately, happily, successful, prosperous, lively, graceful, lucky, joyful, cheerful, cheery, glad, pleasing, joyous, merry, jolly, jovial.

But when the question had to be settled crosswise, she sat down keeping silence, and it seemed to her that in the near future there would be some interesting change in their lives, as if they were living a happy life in an antique way. (Kholmiraev Sh., 29).

Units of the concept of unhappiness in the form of adjectives and adverbs: unhappy, unhappily, unfortunate, unfortunately, ill-fated, ill-starred, unlucky [9], sad, sorrowful, pitiful, distressful, disastrous, calamitous, miserable, worried, anxious, doleful, mournful, wistful, grievous.

Oh! How unfortunate, how unhappy I am, that on this day my neighbors are awakened by the call to prayer and are running for their happiness, and my unhappy generation is still asleep in the bed of ignorance, quarreling with each other with the power of discord and enmity, side by side, exhausted and weak, they are still sleeping like soulless. ... Oh my Turkic sons from Turkestan! Wake up now! Just awaken from the sleep of ignorance, little doomsday has come![10].

Adjectives within the conceptual field units of happiness and unhappiness are relatively active. Affixation (-ли, -сиз, бе-, бад-) is more productive than the composition method (бахтиқаро, шўрпешона). Adjective-forming affixes in words learned from the Tajik language, as a result of being absorbed into our language over the centuries, can also create adjectives from Uzbek words. These affixes are now among the active word-forming units of the Uzbek language: **бебахт (unhappy)**, **бадбахт (unfortunate)**, **донгдор (famous)**, **салмоқдор (weighty)**, **билимдон (knowledgeable, connoisseur)**, **сепсув (full of water)**, etc.[11. 219].

The most commonly used units related to this parts of speech are the lexemes of happy and unhappy, with the invariants “fortunate/unfortunately”, “lucky / unlucky”, “successful/ unsuccessful”, “gracious / ungracious” with the closest meaning, belonging to the nuclear zone, the rest are peripheral units.

The functions specific to the adverb, on the other hand, can be expressed through a set of adjectives or by adding auxiliaries to the adjective, such as: ҳолда (in the way), равишда (in the manner), билан (with): масрурлик билан (with luck, with joy), қувончли ҳолда, қайғули тарзда, and so on.

Verb forms of the concept of happiness (verb-based expressions): бахтли қилмоқ, (to make happy) бахтиёр айламоқ (to make happy), масъудлик бағишламоқ (to give happiness), шод этмоқ (to rejoice), сарафроз этмоқ (to exalt), кулмоқ (to laugh), жилмаймоқ (to smile), (қувончдан) кўзига ёш олмоқ (to shed tears (of joy)), йиғламоқ (to cry), толеъ ёр бўлмоқ (to be fortunate), омад ёр бўлмоқ (to be lucky) and so on.

That was the only way **to make Mutal happy**. That night Etibor was sleepless. She also looked for other activities. The last plan was to cool Mutal's heart, to annoy him (Said Ahmad. Tazim, 9).

My sister came out onto the stage in a dancer's dress. She performed the dance so passionately that everyone who came to the event was amazed. My mother, who was standing next to me and watching my sister, **cried with joy**[12].

The verb forms of the concept of unhappiness (verb-based expressions) are: бахтсиз қилмоқ (to make unhappy), бахтсизлик келтирмоқ (to bring unhappiness), бахтиқаро қилмоқ (to make unhappy), бебахт қилмоқ (to make unhappy), бахтни қочирмоқ (to lose fortune), кулфат келтирмоқ (to bring misfortune), балога гирифтор қилмоқ, ғам-андуҳга ботирмоқ (to bring calamity), йиғламоқ (weep), кўзига ёш олмоқ (to weep) and so on.

That's right, 'said Sabirova, unhappily, and then suddenly burst into tears. "Don't you see, Unsinoваjon, that's what they did with me." They expelled me from the society. May God make my enemies blind! (Kholmiraev Sh., 43)

Among the conceptual field units of happiness and unhappiness, verb and verb-based expressions have a very active dynamic. The core units belonging to the verb are mainly formed in the analytic form by auxiliary verbs such as қилмоқ (make), этмоқ (grow), айламоқ (make, turn), бўлмоқ (grow, get), in the form of auxiliary verbs. In this case, the units belonging to the noun or adjective phrase in the compound verb meant an action relationship with an action-oriented object in ancient times, and then this relationship disappeared, and both elements were joined and became one word. They are semantically connected and form a whole [13]. Units such as кулмоқ (laugh), жилмаймоқ (smile),

күзига ёш олмоқ (shed tears), йиғламоқ (weep) are used for most emotional concepts, sometimes in the nucleus, sometimes in the peripheral layer. The object of our study is also specific to happiness and unhappiness (a person may cry or laugh from both joy or sorrow), in particular, when specific descriptive expressions are added, the reference situation becomes clear without context: «ширин кулгу» (sweet laughter), «заҳарханда кулгу» (sarcasmic laughter", etc.) are peripheral verbs, a paralinguistic unit according to the nature of objectification, but we found it necessary to add to the list of descriptive verbs when the image of this event is transferred to the language.

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THE ROLE OF HUMAN CAPITAL IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF INNOVATIVE EDUCATION

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Abstract: In this article is analyzed the role of human capital in the development of innovative education. The revealed is reforms being implemented in Uzbekistan by the Strategy action. The importance of not only material resources but also spiritual foundations in the development of innovative education is illustrated by examples.

Keywords: a priority, education, human capital, the systematic formation of schools, modern cadre, a generation, world standards, social sciences, university.

Introduction

At the new stage of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the process of innovative development of social and economic sectors has become an objective necessity. The process of innovative development has been chosen as a priority in all spheres of society, including higher education. In solving this promising task, it was recognized that higher education institutions and the subjects of the socio-economic system are an important part of the form of activity.

The improvement of state and society building defined in the Action Strategy, the deepening of democratic reforms, the formation of civil society, plays a key role in addressing important social issues for a new stage of development of society. In this

regard, it should be noted that this process requires direct human capital, ie ensuring the competitiveness of future professionals. The introduction of innovations in higher education based on innovative ideas, the recognition of bachelors and masters as highly qualified specialists, is a determining factor in the position of each subject of higher education in our country, in the world, in the global community. It also depends on how well the professors, teachers, officials, scientific and technical staff of the university are prepared for this complex activity.

The Main Findings and Results

President Sh.M.Mirziyoyev was said: “The tasks of in-depth teaching of special sciences, history of our country and world civilization, foreign languages and modern computer programs to children and youth have not been solved yet. The solution of another problem is also very important: it is the professional level of teachers and professors, their special knowledge. In this regard, it is necessary to create an environment that actively promotes the process of education, spiritual and enlightenment maturity and the formation of real value”. [1]

In order to achieve the above goals, great attention is paid to the systematic formation of schools specializing in the identification and proper orientation of talented youth, and the formation of a mentally appropriate innovative education is accelerating. In such institutions, the formation of not only educational subjects, but also a truly modern cadre and a generation of true patriots is a topical issue. In particular, on December 27, 2019, during the meeting at the Muhammad al-Khwarizmi School of Information Technology of the President Sh.M.Mirziyoyev: "I will stand by you and be a camel!" I believe that there are bright, educated, courageous young men and women. The best way to lead, to follow, is to set a personal example”,[2] he said confidently.

The rapid development of a globalizing society also requires the need to ensure the competitiveness of the qualified staff trained in universities. In this context, the content of education for future bachelors and masters, the organization of the educational process at the level of world standards must meet the requirements of a globalizing world, a national economy developing on an innovative basis, the social system. Therefore, the introduction of effective mechanisms for training qualified personnel in higher education is the most important condition for raising the spiritual, moral and intellectual development of bachelors, masters and future professionals to a qualitatively new level, as well as innovative forms and methods of education, new pedagogical technologies helps to apply.

As a result of reforms in higher education, university curricula are constantly being improved, subject teaching hours are being adjusted based on the requirements of a market economy, the requirements of graduates, is employers. The rapid development of the country is directly related to the patriotism of the trained specialists, their commitment to strengthening our sovereignty and national interests. In accordance with this requirement, which plays an important role in the system of social sciences in university education, for example, “The history of Uzbekistan”, “Strategy for the development of Uzbekistan. Civil Society”, “Philosophy” and “Religious” Studies.

The process of our country's entry into the world community as a sovereign state, its efforts to take a worthy place in all international systems is deepening. The proposal of the President of Uzbekistan to include the country in the top 50 most developed countries in the world is a strategic task and primarily involves the training of qualified personnel. At the current stage of development, innovative ideas and new technologies are constantly entering the training process. The main reason for this is, first of all, the compliance of

manufactured products with the requirements of the world market, ensuring competitiveness in the consumer market, in the form of finished products created by human labor, as a result of individual talent, special knowledge, high skills. Rapidly changing global development requires participants of socio-economic development, including future bachelors, to constantly acquire, increase and deepen their special knowledge, modern knowledge in the social sciences, specialties. The involvement of innovative ideas in the industry, their application in including small businesses, expands the social demand for knowledge in the social sciences and selected specialties.

Conclusion

This process was announced by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev's works, decrees, resolutions, the content, essence and Strategy of actions for further accelerated development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 are reflected in the steadily growing desire of civil society to master the development trends.[3] Also, the expansion of the integration of science, education and industry has created the task of improving the activities of universities aimed at training competitive personnel, training faculties and departments on the basis of innovative ideas, new pedagogical technologies. Ensuring the competitiveness of goods produced in Uzbekistan in the domestic market and in the world depends on the qualification of highly educated personnel, perfect knowledge of specialties and social sciences, as well as patriotism. The availability of opportunities to rationally use the experience of the world's leading universities in the preparation of future bachelors and masters is also an important factor in the training of highly qualified specialists.

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WAYS TO OPTIMIZE THE IMPACT OF THE OLDER GENERATION (GRANDPARENTS) IN THE FAMILY ON THE UPBRINGING OF YOUNG PEOPLE

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Abstract: This article highlights the importance of the family hearth in raising children. The role of the older generation in the formation of the moral values of an adult in the younger generation is analyzed.

Keywords: *family, harmony, spiritual wealth, upbringing, enlightenment activities, human relationship, national traditions, compromise.*

Introduction

At the heart of child rearing lies the determination of human relationships in the family. Family relationships are a unique “field” for testing and strengthening human relationships between people of different ages, genders, different personalities, with different levels of education and different specializations. It should be noted that in the family, first of all, attention is paid to moral education. The phrases "what is good and what is bad?", "Be polite, do not be rude" are often used in the family.

Family upbringing as a continuous process that lasts a lifetime - is a type of social upbringing, in which all members of the family take an active part, teach each other their knowledge and experience. Childhood, brotherhood and sisterhood, which are formed in the family, are a third world that arises from the union of two living beings, two worlds. Undoubtedly, the word "union" also means harmony, and if the family is more peaceful, the family life will be stronger.

Otherwise, marriage will turn into hell, husband and wife will become bitter rivals, bringing the fate and upbringing of children to an existing state, and the kinship-seed relationship will be damaged. As a result, it causes material and moral damage to society. In short, the family is not only the husband and wife themselves, but the family is a group of grandparents, husband and wife, their children, closest relatives, blood relatives, literally a household.

Therefore, the family is a social unit based on the natural, economic, legal, spiritual relations of people, united on the basis of their desires and goals [Alkarov, 18].

The Main Findings and Results

What our future looks like depends on the young people we raise today. The family is the foundation that carries out such a huge task and creates material and spiritual wealth. The family as a primary social unit of society has a complex structure, which in its activities reflects the needs and abilities of family members, not only the goals and objectives of various activities, but also educational activities.

The peculiarity of family upbringing is that it not only provides children with the general and emotional development of the individual, but also enhances the existing capabilities and moral maturity of the individual, passing on to them the parental, blood-kinship qualities of the parents. For this reason, family upbringing is always characterized by its presence, expediency and seriousness. The main task is to teach and advise the child on the people, etiquette, not only the experience of adults, but also the lifestyle, environment of the family, the profession of parents, the spiritual relationship of family members.

In order to protect our youth from falling into the virtual world, to fill their hearts with the seeds of goodness, it is necessary, first of all, to bring them out of the state of

marginality. Marginality is the fact that an individual or group remains in the "edge" of society, not belonging to a particular social group, class, stratum.

In other words, in the state of marginality, this or that person may remain "in the lurch." From the influence of society, family, neighborhood, "exit leads to indifference, ignorance, alienation from social life in a person who is in a state of marginalization.

The main "characteristics" of a person in such a situation are indifference to the problems of society, sluggishness, a decrease in the sense of involvement in the surrounding events, instability. The heart of such will be broken. The chances of such a person being influenced by others are always high. There is no great difficulty in capturing their hearts. This is extremely dangerous for society and the nation. That is why our spiritual and enlightenment activities should be aimed at overcoming the marginal situation that exists in some of our young people.

The upbringing of a perfect human being takes place because of the upbringing of a particular person, taken separately. Clarity is needed in education. If we can purify the heart of the pupil, sow the seeds of love, respect and reverence for him, we will undoubtedly create a healthy spiritual image of society, because in the East, ascension from the material to the spiritual world is always considered a step towards perfection[Mavrulov, 17].

The role of the family in the life of society and the individual, a valuable approach to its socio-philosophical essence and functions is one of the important factors in the radical reconstruction of our spiritual life.

In order to preserve the rich and profound national traditions of the family, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on February 2, 1998 decided to establish

the Republican Scientific and Practical Center "Family", taking into account the great importance of the family in the development of society.

The adoption of the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on June 27, 2018 "On approval of the concept of strengthening the family in the Republic of Uzbekistan" further increased the responsibility of the Research Center "Family".

In preparing young people for family life, they need to learn the whole system of family life, that is, to create a healthy family environment, to understand each other, to avoid small talk, to know compromise, to keep the house, to make a living, to be clean, beautiful, modest, father-in-law. it is necessary to instill and teach such beautiful qualities as honoring the mother-in-law, seeing the mothers-in-law as if they were born, and raising the children in a capable manner.

The relationship between the person and society, the role of social factors in the formation of personality, the conditions of the individual's adherence to socio-ethical norms, the role of the teacher in educating a harmoniously developed person were studied by Eastern thinkers Abu Rayhan Beruni, Abu Nasr Farobiy, Abu Ali ibn Sino, Kaykovus, Alisher Navoi, Abdullah Avloniy.

Conclusion

The environment is an area of opportunity that helps children meet their needs. The environment can be conditionally natural, social, cultural. The environment includes music, friendly company, educational activities, TV show, philosophy of life, nature corner, a room in your home, something you love and more. When the environment has spiritual, material and social education, it meets the needs of children, ensures the emergence of subject qualities in the individual, realizes the child's unique development it meets the needs of

children, ensures the emergence of subject qualities in the individual, realizes the child's unique development.

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REVIEW OF THE FERGANA VALLEY IN MEMORIAL WORKS DURING THE SHAYBANI RULE

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Abstract: In this article, the coverage of the history of the Fergana Valley in the memoirs in the XVI century is studied on the basis of historical sources. The information about the Fergana Valley in the memoirs is critically analyzed.

Keywords: Fergana Valley, Boburnoma, Tarihi Rashidi, Badoe'ul vaqoe, Shaybanis, memoirs.

Introduction

There are many historical sources related to the historical events that took place in the 16th century in the regions of Movarounnahr, Dashti Kipchak, Khorasan, Kashgar and Iran. Valuable information about the history of the Shaybanid period of the Fergana Valley, which we are studying, can be found in the sources created in the XV-XVII centuries. We found it necessary to analyze the historical sources used in the study on possible sources based on their characteristics. Involvement of the author in the information provided in this type of work increases the level of reliability of the data.

An important source in the coverage of the history of the Fergana Valley during the reign of the Shaybanids is the work of Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur "Boburnoma", which covers the events of 1493-1529. This memoir was called "Boburiya", "Voqeanoma",

"Tuzuki Boburiy", "Voqeoti Boburiy" and became known among scholars as "Boburnoma". The work was published in Kazan in 1857 by N.I. Ilminsky, published in London in 1905 by Mrs. A. Beverich. The Uzbek edition of Boburnoma was published in 1960 by P.Shamsiev and S.Mirzaev and republished in 1989. The work was translated into modern Uzbek in 2008 by V. Rakhmonov and K. Mullafojaev.

Boburnoma describes the historical events that took place in the Fergana Valley in the late 15th and early 16th centuries. The play contains important information about the location of valley cities, the distance between them, defense structures, population, nature, fauna and flora. The fact that Babur Mirza himself took part in the events in the Fergana Valley increases the reliability of the information. "Boburnoma" describes the conquest of the valley by Shaibanikhan and the events that took place before he left Fergana. After the death of Shaibanikhan, there was talk of the expulsion of the Shaybani army from the Fergana Valley under the leadership of the Mongol emir, and their appeal to Mirza Babur for help. The play also tells the story of Sultan Said Khan, who was in Kabul at the time, being sent to the valley, and Fergana was returned to Babur Mirza. After the defeat of the Shaybani sultans with the help of Ismail Safavi and the conquest of Samarkand, important events took place, such as the visit of Sayid Muhammadkhan, the uncle of Muhammad Haydar, the author of "History of Rashidi", on behalf of Sultan Saidkhan, the governor of Fergana, to Babur. In addition, Babur gave valuable information about the Shaybani sultans.

The Main Findings and Results

Another important source of information on the subject is the work of Muhammad Haydar Mirza "History of Rashidi." Muhammad Haydar Mirzo was born in 1500 in Tashkent. Amir Muhammad Hussein, whose father belonged to the Duglat clan,

was one of the trusted beys of Tashkent Khan Sultan Mahmudkhan. After the death of his father, he lived first in Bukhara and then in Badakhshan. His mother went to visit his cousin Babur and lived in Kabul until 1512. In his work "Boburnoma", Babur noted that Muhammad Haydar had a deep knowledge and was a good calligrapher. Together with the Mongol khan Sultan Saidkhan, he first went to Fergana and then to Kashgar, where he served until 1533. He served as father, army commander, and minister to Sultan Said Khan's son, Sultan Abdurashid Khan. When Abdurashidkhan ascended the throne, he found out that he was persecuting the emirs of Duglat and fled from Tibet to Kabul to Mirza Kamron. Then Agra went to King Humayun and entered his service. With the help of King Humayun, he conquered Kashmir in 1541 and ruled there until 1551.

Muhammad Haydar Mirza wrote "History of Rashidi" in Kashmir in 1544-1546. Created in Persian, this source provides valuable information on the history of Movorounnahr, Khorasan, Dashti Kipchak, Kashgar, Iran, Afghanistan, and North India. The work consists of two parts. This work has caused a great deal of interest in the scientific community. English by E.D. Ross in 1895, Z.P. Translated into Russian by Djalilova, LM Epifanova, Russian, 2010 into Uzbek by V. Rakhmonov, Ya. Egamova.

Muhammad Haydar Mirzo uses the term Fergana in relation to the valley after Babur Mirza in his work "Tarihi Rashidi". The availability of valuable information about the Fergana Valley in this source is also significant, as it complements the events described in the "Boburnoma". There is important information about the occupation of the valley by Shaibanikhan, the Shaybani sultans who ruled there, the emirs who served the Shaybani. One of the valuable aspects of the work for our research is that a lot of information about Fergana found in the part dedicated to Sultan Saidkhan is not available in other works. Among them are important information about the activities of Janibek

Sultan, the Shaybani who ruled in Akhsi, the activities of Haji Ali Bahadir, who ruled Andijan on his behalf, and the attack of the governor of Kashgar Abobakr Mirza on the valley in 1514. Sultan Saidkhan's war with Sultan Sevinchkhoja to keep the valley in his hands, his sending an envoy to Samarkand to Babur Mirza for help, and his diplomatic relations with the Kazakh Sultan Qasim Sultan were skillfully covered by Haydar Mirza. The historical events that took place in the valley in the first quarter of the 16th century, the people's uprising in Andijan after Sevinchkhojahan's death, and Sultan Saidkhan's attempts to support the rebels are not found in other sources. The author's own participation in the events of this work adds to the value of the source. "Tarihi Rashidiy" clearly describes the ethnic composition of the peoples living in the Fergana Valley, the production economy, lifestyle, the location of the fortresses, the number of troops that took part in the battles in this area. In our research, we mainly used the Russian and Uzbek editions of Tarihi Rashidi and, if necessary, referred to other editions.

Also, another source on the subject under study is the work of Rare Events. Zayniddin Wasifi wrote this work as a memoir. We can learn about his life and activities through this work. After many years of wandering, Wasifi settled in 1522 in the palace of Keldimhammadkhan in Shahrukhiya. The governor of Tashkent Suyunchihojahon came to Tashkent in 1525 after his death. Zayniddin Wasifi took part in the Khorasan march against the Safavids together with the troops of Tashkent and Fergana led by Keldimhammadkhan and the Shaybani army led by Ubaydullokhan. Badoe'ul Vaqoe describes historical events up to 1532.

Sadriddin Aini did a lot of research on the life of Zayniddin Wasifi and Badoe'ul Vaqoe and published Wasifi and his Conclusion. Badoe'ul vaqoe was written by A.N. Boldirev studied and published a critical text in 1961. This source was published in 1971 by

Kemal Aini in Tehran. In 1979, Naim Norkulov translated Badoe'ul Vaqoe from Persian into Uzbek.

This source covers the historical events that took place in Movarounnahr, Turkestan, Khorasan and Iran in the late 15th and first half of the 16th centuries. The information on the subject we are studying is found in the section dedicated to the activities of Suyunchikhojakhan, the story of bringing a woman from Ahangaran to Keldimhammad sultan, the statement of Keldimhammad sultan's accession to the throne of Tashkent, the march of Tashkent khan to Khorasan.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the fact that the authors themselves are involved in the historical events covered in the memoirs not only increases the reliability of the data, but also casts doubt on the objectivity of these events. A somewhat critical approach is required when analyzing data from this type of source.

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FEATURES OF CEREBRAL HEMODYNAMICS IN ISCHEMIC STROKE ON THE BACKGROUND OF POSTPONED COVID-19

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Abstract: From 2019 to 2020, a total of 141 patients of the neurological department of the Tashkent Somatic Hospital were diagnosed with an acute diagnosis of moderate severity (without loss of consciousness) in the basal carotid artery basin during this period. Among patients with IS - 118 (83.7%) underwent IS against the background of COVID-19. Among them there were 53 (44.9%) men and 65 (55.1%) women. These patients were included in the study group (SG). The remaining 45 people - with IS without a history of COVID-19 - were selected for the comparison group (GC). It was revealed that in patients with ischemic stroke against the background of the transferred COVID-19, patients with CE and LS subtypes of IS were more common. For these patients, no gross disturbances of blood flow through the extracranial arteries were found.

Keywords: COVID-19, ischemic stroke, blood, comparison group, patients, cerebral ischemia, cerebrovascular accidents.

Introduction

Ischemic stroke (IS) in recent decades has been one of the leading causes of death in older age groups. A generalization of the first results of the course of victims of coronavirus infection showed that the development of IS in such patients is very likely. The high mortality rate of elderly patients infected with COVID-19 is partly associated with the development of fatal cardiovascular complications, the most severe of which is stroke (1).

An analysis of the few available publications that mention the problem of COVID-19-associated ischemic stroke can show not only the significance of the problem, but also reveal the mechanisms of acute cerebral ischemia (2). The prevention of acute cerebrovascular accidents (ACVI) in those infected with COVID-19 seems to be one of the important clinical tasks that need to be addressed in conditions of high workload in specialized hospitals and a shortage of specialists.

Purpose: To identify the features of the main clinical and diagnostic indicators of cerebral circulation in patients after ischemic stroke against the background of the transferred COVID-19.

Material and research methods: Study design: single center, randomized.

The study included 141 patients from the neurological department of the Somatic Hospital of the city of Tashkent from 2019 to 2020 with an established diagnosis of IS in the basin of the internal carotid artery of moderate severity (without impairment of consciousness) in the acute period. In total, 67 (47.5%) men and 74 (52.5%) women were examined the average age was 52.1 ± 4.8 years. Among patients with IS - 118 (83.7%) had IS against the background of COVID-19. Among them there were 53 (44.9%) men and 65 (55.1%) women. These patients were included in the study group (SG). The remaining 45 people - with AI without a history of COVID-19 - were selected for the comparison group (GC). The groups were found to be comparable in terms of gender and age.

The study of cerebral hemodynamics was carried out using a duplex-triplex LOGIQ C-5 Premium scanner. Echolocation of extracranial vessels was performed with a linear transducer with a frequency of 10 MHz, visualization of intracranial vessels - using transcranial location with a phased transducer with a frequency of 2.5 MHz. Statistical processing of the obtained data was performed on a personal computer using the program statistics 8.0. The student test is considered reliable at $p < 0.05$.

The study was conducted with the informed consent of the patients.

Results and discussion: According to IS subtypes, SG patients were distributed as follows: atherothrombotic (AT) - 29 (24.6%) people, lacunar stroke (LS) - 48 (40.7%) patients and cardioembolic (EC) - 41 (34.7%) of the surveyed.

In patients with GC, AT was found in 24 (53.3%) patients, CE - in 12 (26.7%) patients and LS in 9 (20.0%) patients.

Thus, among the patients with MG, such subtypes of strokes as LS and CE were significantly more frequent, and in HS - AT.

When comparing the leading syndromes of SG and GC, significant differences in their prevalence within the group were revealed. In the main group, every first patient had a cephalgic syndrome, the absolute majority had astheno-vegetative and more than half of the examined SG had pyramidal insufficiency. Among patients with GC, cephalgic and astheno-vegetative syndromes occurred in no more than 25% of cases.

Duplex scanning of extra- and intracranial vessels revealed the following patterns.

Patients have occlusive processes in the form of tortuosity and stenosis. In SG, tortuosity was found in 21.4%; in the GC, reliably more often in 38.2% of cases. Thus, tortuosity of the carotid arteries was characteristic of patients with IS without a history of COVID-19. There was no statistically significant difference between the parties ($p > 0.5$).

Atherosclerotic changes were detected in 19.6% of patients with SG and 57.3% of patients with GC. There were no patients with common carotid artery (CCA) occlusion in the study.

Analysis of the linear blood flow velocity (LFV) by CCA in the SG showed a decrease in the left CCA (26.5 cm / s ; $\sigma = 3.14$) compared with the GC (30.9 cm / s ; $\sigma = 3.44$; $p < 0, 05$). Hereinafter, the data are presented as the arithmetic mean (M) and standard deviation (σ).

In patients with GC, there was a tendency to a decrease in the volumetric blood flow velocity in the CCA, and the internal carotid artery (ICA) on both sides. As for patients with GC, the volumetric blood flow velocity in the CCA and ICA on both sides slightly differed from the normal values (table).

Table

Data of volumetric blood flow rate (Q, ml / min) of extracranial arteries in patients with SG and GC (M + σ).

Artery	SG (n = 33)	GC (n = 54)	Norm
CCA	514 ± 96 *	468 ± 91 *	523 ± 89
ICA	276 ± 39 *	213 ± 48 * ^	292 ± 68

Note: * - reliability between groups and norm

($p < 0.01$), ^ - reliability between groups ($p < 0.01$).

A decrease in the volumetric blood flow rate and an increase in the linear blood flow rate in the extracranial vessels in the group of patients with IS without a history of COVID-19 compared with age norms, which speaks of an atherosclerotic process in the arteries, this explains the predominance of patients with AT subtype IS in this group.

Conclusion

Thus, it was revealed that in patients with ischemic stroke against the background of the transferred COVID-19, patients with CE and LS subtypes of IS were more common. For these patients, no gross disturbances of blood flow through the extracranial arteries were found.

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NEUROPHYSIOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE CONDITION OF PATIENTS WITH IDIOPATHIC SCOLIOSIS IN THE EARLY POSTOPERATIVE PERIOD

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Abstract: In this article, a retrospective analysis of complications in the early postoperative period was conducted in 57 patients with idiopathic infantile and juvenile breast scoliosis. During the surgical treatment of scoliosis, a variety of pathological syndromes of damage to the nervous system can occur. As can be seen from the study, in patients who underwent anterior mobilization and anterolateral epiphysiodesis of the thoracic spine as a separate stage of surgical treatment, neurological disorders were more pronounced and were observed in a larger number of patients than with combined surgical tactics.

Keywords: idiopathic scoliosis, neurological complications.

Introduction

One of the modern ways to treat scoliosis is to surgically correct this spinal cord. When carrying out these operations, there is a high risk of intra- and postoperative complications. The

question of the need for simultaneous middle and posterior surgical interventions or for these interventions in two separate stages also remains controversial (1, 2 , 3).

Attempts to maximally correct its deformity during surgical treatment of scoliosis often result in various neurological complications that occur in 0.6 to 25.4% of cases, according to various authors (4).

Material and methods: During the study, a retrospective analysis of complications in the early postoperative period in 57 patients with idiopathic infantile and juvenile thoracic scoliosis was carried out in the Department of Pediatric and Adolescent Vertebrology of the Research Institute of Traumatology and Orthopedics of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan. According to the indications and in accordance with the developed technique, all patients underwent anterior curvature mobilization and anterolateral epiphysiodesis on the convex side of the thoracic spine deformity.

Postoperative treatment of patients was standard and consisted of assessment of cardiovascular and respiratory system function, clinical blood test parameters, and coagulogram.

The patients were divided into 2 groups. The first group consisted of 37 patients, of whom 29 patients (45%) underwent anterior mobilization and 8 patients (13%) underwent anterolateral epiphysiodesis of the thoracic spine as a separate stage of surgical treatment. The second group included 27 patients who underwent surgery on the anterior spine together with correction of the deformity with a polysegmental construction and posterior fusion on the same day. Anterior curvature mobilization was performed in 6 patients (9%), anterolateral epiphysiodesis - in 21 patients (33%).

Complications such as pain syndrome, paramidal and sensory insufficiency were subject to analysis. Along with clinical and neurological examination, the intensity of pain syndrome was determined in patients on a 10-point visual analogue scale of pain (0 points - no pain, 10 points - maximum pain).

All patients in both groups experienced at least one of the above complications. At the same time, two or more complications occurred in 74% of patients in the first group and in 68% of patients in the second group. The most common complication in the first group was pain in the back and along the intercostal nerves. This complication occurred in 31 patients in group 1 (76%), and in 15 patients in group 2 (56%, $p < 0.05$). The average pain score on the VAS scale was 6.3 ± 1.8 points in group 1, while in group 2 it was significantly lower - 4.8 ± 1.7 points.

Sensitivity disorders in group 1 were detected in 55% of patients, in group 2 - in 26%. Sensitivity changes were in the nature of hyperesthesia, hypalgesia, sometimes hyperesthesia is replaced by hypesthesia. Most often, sensory disturbances began in the form of transient paresthesia.

Reduced reflexes were less common than changes in the sensitive area. In group 1, only 20.3% of patients showed a decrease in abdominal reflexes, 15.5% of patients showed a decrease in the knee reflex, and in 9.6% of patients, a decrease in the biceps reflex and Achilles reflex. In the second group, these indicators were 10.4%, 5.8% and 2.9%, respectively.

In the study of hemodynamic parameters, significant circulatory disorders were mainly determined in the posterior tibial arteries and arteries of the dorsum of the foot with the greatest degree of deviation from normal values.

Propensity for vasospastic disease (74% of patients in group 1 and 45% of patients in group 2) was found to be predominant on the side of the pain syndrome, compared with the mean values of Doppler studies of the patients examined.

Conclusion

Thus, during the surgical treatment of scoliosis, various pathological syndromes of damage to the nervous system can occur. As can be seen from the study, in patients who underwent anterior mobilization and anterolateral epiphysiodesis of the thoracic spine as a separate stage of surgical treatment, neurological disorders were more pronounced and were observed in a larger number of patients than with combined surgical tactics.

The data obtained regarding complications that occur after staged and combined surgical interventions in the postoperative period will minimize the risk of their occurrence.

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CHANGING DEMOGRAPHIC PROCESSES: TRENDS, CHALLENGES AND PROSPECTS

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Abstract: This article analyzes the demographic situation and examines changes in population growth rates. At the same time, the factors influencing the birth and death rates and the trend of migration processes are clearly indicated. Based on the results of the analysis, forecasts of changes in demographic indicators and population growth are given.

Keywords: demography, population, births, deaths, migration, labor resources, forecast, systematic analysis

Introduction

Research institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan, together with foreign partners, with the support of the United Nations Population Fund, have developed forecasts of the country's demographic development for the period up to 2050.

The forecast is based on a deep analysis of the main regularities and factors of changes in the population size and its sex and age structure for the period from 1950 to 2018. As a forecasting method, the methods widely used in international practice were used, which make it possible to consider the main indicators of demographic reproduction (fertility, mortality, immigration, emigration).

In terms of the prospects for fertility - in the country as a whole, the birth rate will continue to decline as a result of a steady increase in the well-being of the population, an increase in its cultural and educational level, and an increase in urbanization processes. So, if in 2018 the number of live births per woman was 2.57, then in 2030 2.35 is expected, in 2040 - 2.24 and by the end of the forecast period (2050) - 2.16 live births ... The decline in the total fertility rate will continue both among the rural and urban population. That is, the birth rate is expected to stabilize at the level of simple replacement.

Mortality assumptions imply that the rate of decline in indicators measuring the intensity of this process will remain the same as in previous years, or even increase.

As a result of an increase in the standard of living of the population, a qualitative improvement in the health care system, the intensity of mortality will gradually decrease. This will lead to an increase in the average life expectancy of women and men. Life expectancy will increase over the period 2018-2050 for men from 70.86 years to 75.62 years, for women - from 74.35 to 78.66 years. In general, a more rapid decline in mortality among men compared with women should lead to a convergence of indicators of the average life expectancy of men and women.

The Main Findings and Results

The increased openness of Uzbekistan, the expected more active participation of the country in the international division of labor will contribute to an increase in the migration loss of the population in the period until the beginning of the 2030s, with its subsequent stabilization at the level of 40 thousand people per year. The main results of the demographic development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the period 2018-2050. are as follows.

1. In the next three decades, the total population of the Republic of Uzbekistan will grow steadily and is most likely to reach 44.5 million people by 2050 (according to the average version), that is, it will increase by 37%. At the same time, during this period, the rate of population growth will differ. During the first eight years of the forecast period, the annual population growth rate is expected to decline rapidly, from an initial 1.6% to 1.0%, and then temporarily stabilize until a new phase of decline after 2040 begins from 0.85% to 0.6% by 2050.

Natural population growth will continue to play a decisive role in the demographic development of Uzbekistan in the future, although its contribution is expected to decline from 536 thousand people to less than 300 thousand people per year by the middle of the 21st century.

2. The decline in population growth rates will cause further aging of the population of Uzbekistan. It is expected that during the forecast period, the average age of the country's population will increase from 29.3 years to 36.9 years by the end of 2050, or increase by almost 8 years. At the same time, the average age of the female population of Uzbekistan will be 37.9 years, and the male population - 36.5 years.

3. Larger and in many respects unprecedented changes will be observed in the age structure of the population.

According to the forecast, despite the decline in the period 2018-2050, the birth rate and the share of children aged 0-17 years in the total population from 33.3% to 25.7%, their total number will be quite stable - about 11.4 - 11.8 million people. As for young people aged 18-23, as a potential contingent for higher education, their number will also be quite stable - 3.5 million people in 2018 and 3.6 million people each in 2030 and 2050.

However, in order to increase the level of coverage of children, adolescents and youth with secondary general and vocational education, to radically improve the quality of education by reducing the number of shifts, to optimize the occupancy of classes in order to create conditions for expanding individual forms of work with students, introducing advanced pedagogical technologies, further expansion of material technical base of educational institutions of all types, staffing them with qualified teaching staff.

4. Special attention should be paid to the forecast results in terms of the dynamics of the working-age population. While maintaining the established boundaries of working age, the number of this category of the population in the forecast period will increase from 8.6 million people in 2018 to 23.4 million people by 2050, or will increase by 26%. This indicates that in the long term, Uzbekistan will be a labor-secured region, which makes increased demands on the solution of the most acute social problem in the long term - ensuring employment of the population.

At the same time, despite a significant increase in absolute indicators, it is expected that the relative share of people of working age will decrease significantly - from 56.9% in 2018, to 55.8% in 2040 and 52.3% in 2050.

5. The results of the forecast indicate that in the period 2018-2050, a sharp increase in the number of persons of retirement age and an increase in their share in the age and sex structure of the population should be expected.

According to the forecast, the number of persons of retirement age (women 55 years old, men 60 years old and older) will increase from 3.2 million to 4.37 million in 2025, 5.2 million in 2030, 7.16 million in 2040 and 9.6 million people in 2050

The share of this category of the population in the total population of the country will grow from 9.7% in 2018 to 22.0% in 2050.

The rapid aging of the population will inevitably raise the question of changing the officially established retirement age and reforming the entire pension system, ensuring its financial stability.

6. In the next thirty years, the demographic burden on the economically active population will increase. So, if in 2018 there were three potential dependents for four potential producers, then in 2050 this ratio will be approximately nine dependents to ten producers.

Calculations of these indicators through the analysis of which category of dependents has a greater influence on the demographic load, shows that the share of dependents of childhood over the forecast period will decrease from 58.5% to 49.0%, while the share of elderly dependents will increase sharply from 17.1% to 41.0%. It can be concluded that the main component of the growth of the total indicator of the share of dependents after 2025 will be the increase in the indicator of the share of elderly dependents.

Conclusion

Thus, the observed changes in population dynamics will have the greatest impact on three socially important areas - social services and social protection of the population, the public health system and the labor market. And in the aggregate, and on the dynamics of economic growth. The results of the forecast of the demographic development of Uzbekistan can serve as a tool for the development and implementation of specific measures of state policy, the development of any adequate and potentially successful targeted strategies, programs of economic and social development of the country.

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THE ROLE OF PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF PHARMACEUTICAL SECTOR IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: The article examines the reforms related to the further development of the pharmaceutical industry as one of the priorities of the development of the social sphere, improvement of the provision of population and medical institutions with cheap, quality medicines and medical products by the example of the state-owned pharmaceutical industry of Uzbekistan (“Uzfarm sanoat”) and the pharmaceutical network development agency. The article analyzes the activities of organizations.

Keywords: Medicines, pharmaceutical activity, pharmaceutical industry, production of medicines, pharmaceutical network, medical product, powers of state bodies, modernization.

Introduction

As one of the foundations of the reforms carried out in the social sphere in our country, it is the further improvement of the healthy lifestyle of citizens.

February 7, 2017 of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Issues of further development of the pharmaceutical industry, improvement of provision of population and medical institutions with cheap, quality medicines and medical products, prevention of

unreasonable increase in prices of medicines, as one of the priority directions of development of the social sphere established in the strategy of actions on five priority directions of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, Also, a number of measures have been taken to ensure favorable conditions for the rapid development of the pharmaceutical network, approved by the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on additional measures for the rapid development of the pharmaceutical network" № PP-3532 on February 14, 2018. The role of relevant state bodies, organizations and enterprises in ensuring the development and improvement of the system of providing the population with quality medicines and medical products in our country, coordination and control of pharmaceutical activities of pharmacy institutions is of great importance. To date, the state-Stock Company of the pharmaceutical industry of Uzbekistan ("Uzfarm sanoat") has played an important role in the development of pharmaceutical industry in our country.

State-Stock Company of pharmaceutical industry of Uzbekistan ("Uzfarm sanoat"). Coordination of activities of associations, enterprises, organizations producing medicines and biological substances, decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan on measures to ensure more effective organization of the process of acquisition of rights over land parcels and other immovable property as part of the South Caucasus pipeline expansion project more ... state-owned pharmaceutical industry of Uzbekistan ("Uzfarm sanoat") according to the decision of the GI the concert was organized. It was determined that the concert will be considered in the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan in its activity.

1993-y Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan On November 11, the Charter of the state agricultural industry of Uzbekistan ("Uzfarm sanoat") was adopted by

the decree № 542 n"On approval of the Charter of the state agricultural conference "Uzfarmsoat". According to paragraph 11 of this Charter, the main goals and objectives of the concert were defined as:

the organization of the creation and production of medicines, the implementation of measures to meet the demand of the population, treatment and profiling institutions for medicinal products, biopreparations, other products for medical and sanitary and hygienic purposes;

cooperation with the Republican and local authorities of the state power on the issues of development of pharmaceutical industry, improvement of territorial placement of enterprises of this network, conduct of nature protection policy;

Implementation of a unified scientific and technical policy in the field of the creation of highly effective medicinal products and technologies of their production, together with the Ministry of Health, other ministries and departments;

to reduce their imports to the account of increasing production of dorivor drugs in the Republic itself, to develop and consistently implement a program of improvement and expansion of scientific, technical and economic cooperation with foreign partners.

Agency for the development of the pharmaceutical network. In order to improve the conditions for the development of pharmaceutical activity, to further increase the level of supply of population and health institutions with cheap, quality medicines, medical products and medical equipment, to introduce a unified system of coordination of their production, import and sale, In accordance with the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan № 5229 "on measures to radically improve the management system of the pharmaceutical network" on November 7, 2017, the agency for development of the pharmaceutical network was established under the Ministry of health of the

Republic of Uzbekistan. As a result, in connection with the establishment of this agency, the concert "Uzfarmsanoat" was finished.

According to the decree, the following state institutions were included in the Development Agency of the pharmaceutical sector:

The State Center for expertise and standardization of medicines, medical products and medical techniques of the Ministry of health of the Republic of Uzbekistan; Uzbek Chemical-Pharmaceutical Research Institute; Tashkent Scientific-Research Institute of vaccines and zardoblar; Research Institute " Oriental Medicine; Innovation scientific-production pharmaceutical cluster "Tashkent Pharma Park".

The main objectives of the agency are as follows: development and implementation of a sustainable development strategy through the introduction of a modern pharmaceutical network, including its state-of-the-art support; Organization of the study of the conjuncture of the pharmaceutical market, a systematic analysis of the state of supply of population and health institutions with pharmaceutical products, and on the basis of which the development of proposals for further replenishment of the domestic market and localization of production; assistance to Network Enterprises in establishing cooperation with leading foreign pharmaceutical enterprises, mastering the production of competitive, high-quality new types of pharmaceutical products in domestic and foreign markets; state management of the pharmaceutical network, including through the state registration of pharmaceutical products, standardization, certification, technical regulation, as well as licensing of pharmaceutical activities (with the exception of retail sale of medicines and medical products); Organization of the production of innovative and high-quality medicines, medical products and medical equipment, satisfaction of the population's need for these products, preparation of pharmaceutical specialists on the

basis of international educational standards and on specialties with high demand, consistent integration of Pharmaceutical Education into the system of the international scientific community and coordination of the activities of the Directorate.

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PROTECTION OF THE RIGHT OF HUMAN ENVIRONMENTALLY SAFE

LIVING

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Abstract: The article analyzes the norms and processes of protection of human rights on the basis of analysis of the current legislation in the field of human and civil rights, the methods of protection of the right through the court and by filing a complaint to a high-ranking body (official) over the body that caused the violation of this right

Keywords: Human rights protection mechanism, environmental hazard phenomenon, environmental safe residence permit.

Introduction

It is known that the existence of norms and processes of protection of human rights is an important condition for the observance of established rights in practice. These measures create legal guarantees of observance, protection and protection of human rights.

Main Part

Based on the analysis of the current legislation in the field of human and citizen rights, this situation is known that a person's environmentally safe residence permit is protected in the following two ways: a) his right to self-defense; b) protection by the system of state bodies.

According to Article 43 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan[1], the state provides for the rights and freedoms of citizens enshrined in the Constitution and laws. At the same time, the state is not the only entity that guarantees the right of citizens to a favorable environmental natural environment. After all, citizens also have the right to independently defend their rights "in all ways not prohibited by law". In addition, other types of organizations are also entitled to ensure the rights of citizens. Thus, as a subject of relations in the field of ensuring the right to environmentally safe living, the state is considered an element of an excellent system in an organic state, entering into a number of intertwined relations with other elements of the system.

With the help of state institutions, protection is divided into administrative and judicial order protection. The law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on complaints to the court over actions and decisions that violate the rights and freedoms of citizens" gives the citizens the right to submit an administrative complaint over the decisions of the relevant bodies issued in collegial and individual order. Consequently, citizens can complain about any action or decision that violates the right to environmentally safe living. The decision, which will be the basis for filing a complaint, can be taken by state bodies or their officials, self-governing bodies of citizens, enterprises, organizations and institutions, public associations. In order to file a complaint against such decisions, it is necessary that the rights and freedoms of citizens with them are violated or that they are hindered from their

implementation, that they are imposed on him by lawlessly or that he is subject to unlawful liability.

This law gives the applicant the choice of the applicant himself or herself. He can apply to the court or to the higher standing Organization of the decision-making body, to the self-governing bodies of citizens and other institutions. The citizen has the right to appeal directly to the court if he is dissatisfied with the consideration of the complaint by the state body, which has the obligation to consider the complaint.

Article 44 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan stipulates that "each person is guaranteed the right to defend his rights and freedoms through the court, to appeal to the court over illegal actions of state bodies, officials, public associations".

According to Article 52 of the law "On protection of nature" of the Republic of Uzbekistan[2] "legal entities and individuals have the right to appeal to the court with a claim to stop harmful activities in terms of the environment, natural environment, human health and property of people, ecology that damages the national economy" . Also, citizens have the right to recover from the damage caused to themselves and their property in a judicial order.

The right to judicial protection is an important inviolable right of man from ancient times. This right is enshrined in the Universal Declaration of human rights and the International Covenant on civil and political rights.

Protection of the right through the court is carried out by the method of filing a claim in court. The right of a citizen to sue in court as a legal instrument of protection not only protects the interests of the plaintiff, but also serves to ensure legislative and legal order, which leads to a healthy and sustainable development of the whole society. At the

same time, such a right leads to control over the state, to the fight against bureaucracy and abuse of power.

Conclusion

According to the legislation, the rights and freedoms of citizens, as well as the right to claim in the fate of those whose interests are violated (or aimed at violating), are established. The claim on such activity can not be made if there is a danger to the whole society from movement or inaction. However, in most cases it is difficult to prove that a particular action or inaction violates the rights of a citizen to whom it belongs. If the action (decision) or inaction contrary to the relevant right of the Bard-yu is proved in court, the rights of other citizens who are within the limits of influence in this case will also be protected. A distinctive feature of the protection of the right to environmentally safe living is that by protecting the rights of a citizen or group of citizens, the rights of all citizens who can be affected by environmental hazards, while the interests of society and the state are also protected.

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SOME ISSUES OF IMPROVEMENT OF ADMINISTRATIVE JUSTICE IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: Currently, one of the most important areas of the legal doctrine of most foreign countries is the creation of a fair and stable legislative system. The complexity and acuteness of this issue is manifested not only in identifying and introducing effective norms into the process of legal regulation of social relations, but also in understanding its methodological and conceptual foundations, correctly defining the essence and subjects of legal regulation. In this case, scientific research is being conducted to further improve the work of rule-making in developed countries, including ensuring the legality and promotion of legislation, conducting a comprehensive examination, including prevention of disputes over departmental regulations. The norm has a special place in the field of creativity of legislative acts. In particular, a separate approach is needed on the part of public administration bodies when issuing departmental legal documents. The control over these documents by the court will prevent human rights violations. This article describes this problem.

Keywords: administrative justice, departmental normative-legal document, jurisdiction, public-legal dispute, administrative court.

Introduction

The formation of an effective judicial system requires a clear division of cases within the competence of different judicial bodies, in order to ensure timely legal and fair consideration of cases. Cases are the responsibility of the legislators among the courts, they must develop a clear order of rules and criteria for limiting the powers of courts to verify the legality (constitutionality) of regulations that are clear, meaningful, consistent and, most importantly, understandable, as well as in court. At this stage of development, rules and criteria for determining the jurisdiction of courts to review regulatory documents should correspond to the powers of various courts and avoid conflicts, and measures should be taken to eliminate them if conflicting circumstances are identified. To do this, first of all, it is necessary to develop the current procedural norms in the legislation in accordance with modern requirements.

To date, a number of measures have been taken to create an effective and fair judicial system in Uzbekistan and to address problems that have arisen in the past. For example, the Code of Administrative Procedure (CAP) was adopted, and according to this code, the authority to consider mass legal disputes was transferred to the administrative courts. As a result, it was established that the conduct of disputes under departmental regulations is regulated by this Code.

The Main Findings and Results

However, it was noted that working with such a function was poorly implemented and some problems arose due to the lack of clearly explained mechanisms. As a result, in a number of cases, the rights and interests of citizens and legal entities protected by the Constitution and laws are violated. This led to the formation of insecurity of citizens before the judicial

authorities and state bodies. To eliminate such shortcomings, administrative courts were created, and consideration of such cases was determined to come into their competence. In this case, according to the Article 30 of CAP, the consideration of cases of conflict of departmental regulatory legal acts was classified as cases falling under the jurisdiction of the Supreme Court. However, the implementation of such a system in practice was not fully compensated by scanning for the shortcomings that arose today, and we can see some shortcomings in practice. In particular, insufficient research work has been carried out on the theoretical foundations of court decisions on the recognition of departmental regulatory legal acts invalid. In addition, the institution of court resolution of cases on the recognition of departmental normative legal acts as invalid is considered an innovation for the legislation of our country and an integrated system for the consideration of such a case is not formed by scanning.

Implementation of departmental normative-legal regulations of the current legislation to as certain that it is not valid in the past period gives rise to a number of legal problems that need to be addressed. This may be followed by the following:

Firstly, the cases on recognition of departmental normative legal acts as invalid are not settled in detail in the issue of suitability; Secondly, the affiliation of cases to the judiciary to invalidate departmental normative legal acts is not fully regulated; Thirdly, the procedural procedure for examining cases on the invalidity of departmental regulatory legal acts is not perfect; Fourthly, the execution of court documents on the recognition of departmental

The emerging controversial aspect of the consideration of disputes of the Supreme Court on departmental normative legal acts is that we see that such cases do not have a clear border with the jurisdiction of the constitutional court.

Constitutional law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the constitutional court of the Republic of Uzbekistan” adopted on May 31, 2017, defines the issues within the competence of the court, in accordance with which the constitutional court determines the conformity of decisions of bodies of local public administration, interstate treaty and other obligations of the Republic of Uzbekistan Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

At the same time, the work on consideration of a dispute on regulatory legal acts adopted by ministries, state bodies and departments is not within the competence of the Constitutional Court. On the contrary, it was established that the consideration of such disputes falls within the competence of the Supreme Court. However, in accordance with the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, it is defined as “the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan considers the work to bring the documents of the legislative and executive authorities in accordance with the Constitution.” This means that the consideration of this type of dispute, in general terms, is within the competence of the Constitutional Court and can create a controversial situation when considering such disputed cases.

Belonging to the judgment. Despite the large number of departmental regulatory documents that contradict the Constitution and legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the fact that citizens have fewer cases of going to court indicates the need to study the practice of this area. In this category, it can be assumed that there are certain problematic aspects when cases are referred only to the Supreme Court. If, in addition to this opinion, we take the legislation of the Russian Federation as an example, then Article 20 of the Code of Administrative Procedure of the Russian Federation^[1] considers the following administrative cases as the first instance of the Supreme Court of the Russian Federation, regional court, city court of federal significance, autonomous regional court. , representative bodies of city

authorities are authorized to view dispute work on their documents. Or we see that with such work in the Azerbaijani state, the right to appeal to the court of appeal and to appeal to a higher court is ensured. In Germany, too, this type of work is not considered the highest authority [2].

Proceedings. Departmental regulatory legal documents the third problem in the judicial review of cases that are recognized as invalid, these are problems directly related to the consideration of the case. Despite the fact that chapter 22 of the CAP is given a special procedure for considering this kind of work, today a number of problems arise.

Of these, the subject has the right to apply to the court. In accordance with applicable law, citizens and legal entities have the right to apply to the court. In accordance with Article 179, a citizen or legal entity in respect of whom a departmental regulatory document is applied, the right to apply to the court with a statement declaring this document to be fully or partially invalid is guaranteed. But October 9, 1997 in the Cabinet of Ministers

Conclusion

In general, today in the field of justice the tasks for the future to improve the activities of administrative courts are an effective factor determining the following: -further improvement of the system for ensuring constitutional human rights and freedoms, primarily their protection from unlawful actions and decisions of state bodies and officials; -effective protection of the rights and interests of citizens and legal entities in the event of judicial opposition; -improving the enforcement practice of administrative courts and creating a solid legal framework necessary for the effective functioning of the system.

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THE EFFECT OF COMMUNITY INTELLECT ON SCANDAL PROPENSITY

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Abstract

This examination pointed toward exploring relationship between friendly knowledge and tattle propensity. Members were chosen from sixty college understudies in Bangkok utilizing Tromsø Community Intellect Scale (TSIS) and The Propensity to Scandal Questionnaire for information assortment. Consequences of various relapse investigations demonstrated that community data measure, community abilities, and community mindfulness could clarify 40.6 percent of difference to talk inclination. Discoveries uncovered that community data measure affected tattle inclination though friendly mindfulness adversely affected tattle propensity. This suggested that respondents with a higher capacity to determine and anticipate others' sentiments and conduct just as comprehend their messages during the community collaboration were bound to talk about others. Also, members with a more prominent ability to perceive and know about oneself as well as other people's emotions and practices in the relationship were more averse to babble.

Keywords: Community knowledge, Scandal, Scandal inclination

Introduction

Community insight has progressively become a fascinating subject with regards to community brain science and hierarchical conduct. This capacity has been stretched out from enthusiastic knowledge and considered vital for vocation achievement. Goleman brought up that community knowledge is the blend of community mindfulness and community office, which is basic for life achievement. Community knowledge suggests the capacity to detect others' inclination and practices and assemble relationship with them prompting acquire cooperation for objectives accomplishment in the working environment. Community knowledge is frequently seen as "individual's expertise."

Scholars accepted that community insight can be created to prevail with regards to working connections. Tattle is a type of casual discussion among individuals zeroed in on private matters of others. In spite of the facts that tattle is community wonder occurred in regularly of life, it is frequently seen as a freak conduct. Regardless of the negative insight, numerous people are keen on trading evaluative data of others, which is a tattle. Past research showed that tattle give both positive and negative side. The new examination showed the connection between certain tattle and personal development and pessimistic tattle and self-advancement. In the working environment, tattle is discovered to be a rousing element to shield bunch individuals from non-cooperators. As appeared, tattle assumes a significant part in friendly collaboration and has been passed between individuals who have regular foundation or shared interest. This conduct is thought to be seemed to satisfy people from numerous points of view like empowering participation, diminishing burdens, and raising personal development. A new investigation of Stanford scientists uncovered that when people got data about others' practices through tattle, they every now and again utilized what they have figured out how to help the cooperator. Then again, the individuals who disregard the standard of collaboration can be then barred from bunch exercises. This infers the capacity to comprehend others' emotions and practices, which alludes to "community insight."

Community Intellect

Community insight is an individual's ability to adequately interface with others, and impact them to cooperate with oneself. People with community knowledge comprehend and perceive how others feel, and realize what to impart in friendly communication. The idea of community insight was initially presented by a notable analyst Thorndike who characterized community knowledge as "the capacity to comprehend and oversee people and insight. Numerous explores in friendly insight in a beginning phase had been based on crafted by Thorndike. From there on, the exhaustive comprehension of psychological turn of events and individual conduct had been contributed. In the right on time of 1980s, the idea of community insight was presented in a business standard as proven by various distributed books and articles around there. Community knowledge was unmistakably featured on the renowned book of Gleeman, Emotional Intellect: Why It Can Matter More Than IQ, and the accompanying one in Community Intellect: The New Science of Community Relationships, which inspected the intercorrelations among feelings, insight and practices to portray the idea of community insight seeing someone.

Tattle Propensity

Tattle is characterized as a discussion of individual data about a truant that is passed on in an evaluative way. Tattle is normally seen as a degenerate conduct as proven by term "casual chitchat "," shop talk or "inactive talk". In spite of the fact that tattle is regularly seen as a negative conduct, various analysts tended to the advantages of tattle in different manners including data trade, stress help, receipt of amusement, improve their comprehension of others and building companionship, and use data to control others' activities. Previous research found that people used data got from tattle to agreeable interface with the individuals who considered helpful and separated with the individuals who disregard the standard of cooperation in the association.

Conclusion

This current examination was astounding as it seemed, by all accounts, to be the principal concentrate in the field of hierarchical conduct particularly in Thai setting that researched the linkage between friendly insight and tattle inclination. Albeit the connection between the general community knowledge dependent on the blend of three measurements proposed by Silvera et al. and propensity to prattle was not discovered, two sub-sizes of community knowledge showed a critical effect on tattle inclination. As referenced already, community data measure impacted tattle propensity while community mindfulness was found to negatively affect inclination to prattle. Discoveries of this examination upheld the idea of community knowledge and tattle. As friendly data measure alludes to the capacity to perceive and anticipate others' sentiments and practices just as the capacity to perceive messages passed on during discussion in friendly circumstances, the more community wise individual regarding this capacity was probably going to discuss others' close to home and delicate undertakings to gather this data to use as a component of their assessment to comprehend others' emotions and actions. This discovering upheld the idea of tattle as friendly capacities that individuals set up to satisfy their requirements in numerous structures including improve their comprehension of others and building fellowship, and use data to control others' activities. Then again, people who had higher community mindfulness, which suggests to the capacity to learn and get oneself as well as other people's feelings and activities in the relationship, tended not to talk or trade evaluative data about outsider as these factors were found in a contrary connection. As people understand the clouded side of tattle and its outcomes, they make an effort not to discuss others' private or delicate story to keep up their connections. When tattling about the individual who is missing from the discussion, the person who is in the tattling circumstance can carry this data to advise to that non-attendant. Discoveries of this

investigation contribute information in both community knowledge and tattle themes and can be utilized for the broad examination in this field.

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FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT TRENDS OF PARLIAMENTARY CONTROL OVER THE STATE BUDGET

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Abstract: This thesis describes the stages of development of parliamentary control in Uzbekistan within the framework of one of the most important forms of "parliamentary control" - the state budget.

Keywords: Parliamentary control, state budget, state budget execution, finance

Introduction

Parliamentary control is an independent institution of parliamentarism, which has a long history of developing various forms of supervisory activity. The exercise of control is an important part of the work of any Parliament. The control function of the Parliament is a process carried out in harmony with the legislation. Parliamentary control is often called political control, because the control powers of the parliament are based not only on its own rights, enshrined in the law, but also on the opinion of the voters, who represent the highest authority of any democratic state

What are the stages of the formation of the institution of “parliamentary control” over the State budget in the Republic of Uzbekistan?

The period up to the 2000s. Since the adoption of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 1992, the function of parliamentary control has been gradually developing. In particular, in accordance with paragraph 8 of Article 78 of the Constitution, adopted in 1992: the adoption of the budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the proposal of the Cabinet of Ministers and control over its implementation, the introduction of taxes and other mandatory payments are defined as the exclusive powers of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which is the first manifestation in the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan of “parliamentary supervision” as the exclusive competence of the Parliament.

2000-2011. The processes of development of parliamentary control in the XX century are directly related to the reforms implemented in the Republic of Uzbekistan on the transition to a bicameral parliamentary system. As a result of the national referendum held on 27 January 2002 and in accordance with the Law of 24 April 2003, Chapters XVIII, XIX, XX, XXIII of the Constitution were amended and supplemented. As a result of amendments and additions to the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan in April 2003, along with the formation and operation of a bicameral parliament in the country, a clear definition of the constitutional powers of the Government and other authorities, the Oliy Majlis significantly strengthened the legislative powers of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The exclusive powers of the Oliy Majlis, provided for in Article 78 of the Constitution, are now assigned to the joint powers of the Chambers of the Oliy Majlis and are allocated the powers “on the proposal of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan to

adopt and monitor the implementation of the state budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan”, ”on the introduction of taxes and other mandatory payments”.

2011-2016. The Law of 18 April 2011 amended and supplemented articles 78, 80, 93, 96 and 98 of the Constitution [1]. According to these amendments, the introduction by the Oliy Majlis of the parliamentary institution of expressing a vote of no confidence in the Prime Minister, the systematic report of the government to the parliament on topical issues of socio-economic development of the country, as well as the right of the president to approve decrees on the appointment of the chairman of the Accounts Chamber to a certain extent strengthened the role and place of the parliament in the system of organization of state power, expanded the powers and functions of the legislature in the field of control, increased the requirements for the quality of legislative and control and analytical work, carried out by the highest legislative body of the country. The above-mentioned changes introduced a new institution of parliamentary control for the first time in the practice of the constitutional administration of Uzbekistan, for example, the right to express no confidence in the Prime Minister of the country was introduced. In carrying out these reforms, the experience gained from the analysis of the practice of constitutional development in the field of state and law in such democratic countries as Germany, France, Great Britain, the United States, and Japan was widely used. The reforms carried out in the field of parliamentary control reached a new level with the adoption of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2016 “On parliamentary control [2]”.

The period from 2016 to the present. Today, the state allocates huge amounts of budget funds for the systematic socio-economic development of all regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The correct flow of these budget funds in the areas to which they are directed requires individual control. In the implementation of this control, the role of

the legislative framework, which launched a new mechanism, is invaluable. We are talking about the adoption of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On amendments to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On parliamentary control”.

It is appropriate to say that this law lays the foundation for the mechanism of “parliamentary control”. The reason is that the law clearly defines the subjects, objects, forms of parliamentary control, the procedure for the implementation and consequences of parliamentary control. The document notes that the subjects of parliamentary control are the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan; the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan (hereinafter referred to as the Senate); committees, commissions of the Legislative Chamber, the Senate; factions of political parties in the Legislative Chamber.; Deputies of the Legislative Chamber; members of the Senate; The Commissioner for Human Rights of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan exercises parliamentary control over the implementation of the state budget.

Conclusion

The introduction of “parliamentary control” over the implementation of the state budget in the Republic of Uzbekistan is of great importance. Based on this, in our country, parliamentary control in this direction is carried out by high-level state bodies. In the future, it is expected to introduce changes that will expand the scope of “parliamentary control”.

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ENVIRONMENTAL CONTROL OF PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION BODIES IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: this article analyzes the most pressing environmental problems of today and the role of environmental control in their solution, the main tasks of environmental control.

Keywords: ecology, environment, public administration, environmental control.

Introduction

As the industry develops, various environmental issues are also growing. In particular, today the world is concerned about the reduction in climate change, the abolition of the ozone and soil, the decline in the forest and the soil, the formation of biodiversity, as well as problems of drug trafficking.

The Main Findings and Results

Therefore, there are a number of measures to address environmental issues in the country, the protection of the environment, the use of emissions, recycling energy sources, and today, the largest environmental problems in the country. However, today the following topical environmental issues are recognized by ecologists:

1. The ecological crisis by the Aral Sea;
2. Reduction of land, water and biological resources;

3. Low access to renewable energy sources;
4. Identification of the natural environment and sources of contamination, technical and methodological opportunities for analytical and methodological monitoring, control, special equipment;
5. Mining wastes, former uranium deposits, especially to them state in border areas;
6. Improvement of the system of processing and absorption of industrial and household waste;
7. The influence of neighboring countries located in the region;
8. There is no sufficient database for natural environment and the use of natural resources [1].

It should be noted that the elimination of these environmental problems is our high responsibility for the next generation. Proofing the activities of public administration bodies is an important tool to carry out environmental control functions in addressing such problems. Ecological control of the Republic of Uzbekistan is a concept of ecological control, according to which environmental control, prevention, detection, and ending the violation of the requirements of the legislation in the field of environmental protection and rationalal resources, to increase the efficiency of nature protection activities. Aimed is a system of public and public measures [2].

As the main tasks of environmental control, we can specify the following:

- ✓ prevention and limitation of violations of the legislation in the field of environmental protection and rational use of natural resources;

✓ Identifying the state of the environment, lead to environmental pollution, developmental use of natural resources, and conditions for citizens who may underestimate the life and health of citizens;

✓ Determination of the economic activities of the activities or economic activities and other activities in environmental requirements;

✓ Exhibition of rights and legitimate interests of legal entities and individuals in the field of environmental protection and rational use of natural resources, ensuring the fulfillment of obligations;

✓ Avest changes in the environment, its forecasting state, the use of natural resources, and informational organizations and other organizations and citizens;

✓ Ensuring the participation of civil protection bodies, non-governmental non-profit organizations and citizens in the implementation of nature protection activities and the implementation of state environmental programs and other environmental programs.

In addition, the state-own environmental policy consists of a number of areas, which can specify the following:

Formation and development of environmental control system;

Creating a favorable environment for the life and health of citizens;

Special authorized state bodies in environmental control (here are the local public authorities, government and economic administration bodies, businesses, environmental protection and improvement of organizational and legal mechanisms for cooperation in ensuring the rational use of natural resources;

Development of international cooperation in environmental control.

Conclusion

To achieve these tasks, first of all, further increase the responsibility of public administration, the strengthening of public control over their activities is an important tool.

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INSTRUCTIVE VALUATION IN THE TIME OF DIGITIZING

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Abstract

Overall instructive investment and execution are portrayed by wild imbalance. This not just reflects inconsistent inclusion in and profits by innovation (in the past alluded to as the "advanced gap") yet in addition typifies age-old lopsided characteristics between and inside countries, propagated by uncalled for frameworks and biased practices. Appropriately, the respectable point of 'advanced value' can't be accomplished in detachment: the fundamental treacheries (prominently instructive lopsided characteristics) should initially be cured, along these lines giving an unmistakable objective to computerized consideration.

Keywords: Digitization, Educational investment, Educational Valuation.

Introduction

Profound DISPARITIES IN THE DIGITAL AGE

The world, nations inside it, organizations inside and across those nations, and consequently individuals' lives, are being – and will, dramatically and to a great extent eccentrically, keep on being – drastically changed by perpetually quickly advancing innovation, as a result by Digitising. The World Economic Forum's originator reveals to us that "... we remain near the very edge of an innovative insurgency that will in a general sense change the way we live, work, and identify with each other... in its scale, degree, and intricacy, the change will be not normal for anything mankind has encountered previously".

It would be gullible not to perceive that prior assumptions that web-based media would empower the billions to become worldwide town residents have tragically demonstrated whimsical. Deceptive, degenerate and savage conduct are increased by the web and amplified through the counter friendly interruptions of web-based media. Conceivably, we are at the limit of a time of overall popularity based connections – however entering and appreciating that arising age should be joined by astute precautionary measures and a fitting worldwide system to oversee the diverse social and data networks is simpler said than instituted. In this manner Zuboff cautions against the "more profound, ruinous predations of reconnaissance private enterprise" and Brindle discusses "our broke perspectives, contending fundamentalisms, debilitating of social security's, and doubt of each other".

We are presently without a doubt in VUCA conditions, portrayed by unpredictability, vulnerability, intricacy and uncertainty, exemplified by general digitization. Numerous emotional depictions have been drawn and diverse awesome estimates formed. Notwithstanding, absence of availability makes advanced innovations hard for most of

numerous populaces, while the significant expenses of information and voice groups make them exorbitant. There likewise are relentless advanced partitions across sexual orientation, topography, age, and pay measurements inside each country.

Theoretical free enterprise, Uberised and Amazonified working conditions, and the impending post human economy can possibly settle in and worsen imbalance – both inside and between countries, especially between the industrialized and creating world. There are idealistic speculations about advancement – about an extraordinary mechanical bound forward or about mavericks' capacity to jump ages kept down by effectively obsolete advances. Worriers insist that the tremendous divisions among rich and helpless will consistently be with us, in influence relations just as in abundance and pay. While bury public jumping can't happen inside current conceptualizations, interminable disparity is neither unavoidable nor satisfactory. Also, it is instruction (however unquestionably not in its current structure) that may go about as impetus, with the humblest of people having the option to 'learn' right out of burden and the most devastated sharing and getting a charge out of exercises similarly with the most special.

Training: THE GREAT UNEQUALISER

Notwithstanding the educare illumination trademarks, schooling frameworks stay outfitted to giving consistent work to build the abundance of a couple, fitting individuals to the work environment, and inducing the bogus idea of instruction as human asset venture. Instruction, as by and by rehearsed, is the foe of value, regardless of voluminous arrangements and horde political addresses despite what might be expected. At the trademark levels, variety is great and disparity detested. By and by, and in instructive organizations and cycles all over, categorisation and dismissal are overflowing. While

training (as talked about beneath) should not be focused on nor evaluated in terms of 'value', general network rides instructive organizations worldwide and cuts across the institutional, cultural and recorded variables that led to malevolent socio-instructive segregation.

Instructively, we can't win the Information Campaign, nor in fact the Knowledge Battle, not to mention the Wisdom War, with middle age weapons and a dictatorial order framework. We as a world have taken in an extraordinary arrangement from the monetary and mechanical periods of globalization so far and, if we consider those exercises, have the fundamental ideas for the seriously difficult period of conceiving, developing and keeping an all inclusive instructive construction, required and empowered by our coordinated world framework. Reactions to the instructive difficulties of the Digital Age ought to be planned and conveyed in full comprehension of the completely new conditions, significant freedoms and likely risks. Whenever reacted to fairly, participative and imaginatively, Digitization offers an unrivaled chance to review uneven characters.

Notwithstanding, pre-stacked handheld workers to which people may interface can conquer this issue, even in far off settings. It is perceived too that a larger part of the world's essential and optional schools are without power, and that physically or sunlight based worked PC frameworks may at times be accessible meanwhile. Considerably more thus, it is perceived that, if such basic discriminatory inadequacies are not tended to and helped, the world's hidden issues won't ever be settled. This may well have financial legitimizations however the ethical ones are quickly apparent – and instructive organizers can't try not to face such issues.

Conclusion

Digitisation-Based Education As Valuation Nothing instructively will at any point be the equivalent once more. With Digitization, the world is so significantly and profoundly changed that altogether new instructive methodologies are both vital and conceivable. We discuss all inclusive between connectedness being exemplified in the Global School; comparative acknowledge might be derived from essentially seeing a 5-year old altogether at home with a gadget containing a zillion occasions the computational force of the mightiest work area at the turn of the thousand years.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST PREVENTION: UZBEK AND INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE

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Abstract: The article analyzes the norms and processes of preventing conflict of interests in public service in accordance of the current legislation in the field of corruption, the methods of preventing conflict of interests and developing forms and ways of informing about situation of conflict of interests.

Keywords: Corruption, impartial, conflict of interests, declaration of income, property and conflict of interest of civil servants.

Introduction

Despite the fact that large-scale reforms have been carried out to combat corruption in our country, to eradicate its various manifestations, the indicators of corruption still remain high in our society. According to the information given by the prosecutor general of the Republic of Uzbekistan Nigmatilla Yoldoshev as proof of our opinion, in 2017-2019 the issue of criminal responsibility of 6127 officials on corruption was resolved [1] and in accordance with the report of the International Transparency agency in 2020, we can say that the list of 180 countries in the index of countries with corruption of the Republic of Uzbekistan is ranked in 146th [2].

It seems to us that the failure to comply with the conflict of interests, along with the acquisition of money, extortion, fraud, property, is also one of the manifestations of corruption.

In particular, conflict of interest arises in those cases when the personal interests of civil servants affect or may affect the impartial and impartial performance of their service duties. The personal nature of civil servants includes their personal or close relatives, as well as their access to any nafs or advantages for other persons who may be in close or business relationships.

The Main Findings and Results

It should be noted that the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On combating corruption" has been given a tariff on the concept of conflict of interest, and personal (direct or indirect) violence is called a conflict of interest to a situation that affects or may affect the performance of a person's career or service obligations to the extent. This means that for the occurrence of a conflict of interest, there are situations in which a person can influence or influence the impartial and impartial performance of the services entrusted to him. According to the current legislation, in the event of a conflict of interest, it is established that the civil servant should take the necessary measures in order to prevent the conflict of interest in accordance with the procedure established by the legislation.

If we pay attention to the current legislation, we can see that in the current legislation documents on prevention of conflict of interest, the procedure and mechanism for resolving conflict of interest by civil servants is not developed at the level of international requirements. For example, in the law "Combating corruption" only the definition of the concept of conflict of interest, as well as the fact that when there is a

conflict of interest, the civil servant is satisfied with the need to inform his high-ranking leader. Also, the exemplary rules of conduct of employees of Public Administration bodies and local executive authorities, approved by the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 62 of March 2, 2016 on the Prevention of conflicts of interest, are also in force, and these rules have left many issues open for the Prevention of conflicts of interest.

In particular, in the above-mentioned legislation, the existence of a number of uncertainties regarding with the practical application of the rules for the Prevention of conflict of interest, the absence of the organizational and legal framework for the declaration of income, property and conflict of interest of civil servants, as well as the fact that the civil servant who has not complied with.

However, countries such as Germany, Kazakhstan, and Hungary have already reached these issues in their legislation a few years ago.

Taking into account the above-discussed actual problems, we found it necessary to propose the following proposals to the legislature on further improvement of organizational and legal basis of the solution of conflict of interest in the civil service, in particular in the field of public procurement, increasing the transparency and accountability of the activities of the Civil Service, and increasing responsibility for non-fulfillment:

First of all, by making various additions to Article 21 of the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Combating corruption", we should reduce the discretionary powers to prevent conflicts of interest and clearly define the procedure and term for informing the civil servant.

Because the law does not allow profiling the conflict of interest to be carried out unless it is clearly established how long and in what form the civil servant will inform the

head directly about the conflict of interest, as well as what measures the leader who received the message about the conflict of interest should take.

For example, in Article 51 of the law of the Republic of Kazakhstan "On public service", which is the state Army for the Prevention of conflicts of interests, it is established that immediately after the civil servant finds a message about the conflict of interest, it is necessary to immediately warn the head of the buyer or the Rabar of the state:

- a) in connection with the occurrence of conflict of interest, the authority of this position is assigned to another civil servant;
- b) change of duties of civil servant;
- d) take other measures to eliminate conflicts of interest [3].

Therefore, we can say that in this law of the Republic of Kazakhstan the civil servant should immediately inform the leadership in writing about the conflict of interest and that the fact that it is established that he will take one of the measures established by the leadership, which is reported by him, has led to the restriction of the reduction of powers.

Article 21 of the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Combating corruption" is proposed in the following edition:

"The civil servant is prohibited from using his / her powers in the event of a conflict of interest. The civil servant must inform the head of state or the high-ranking state body in writing within 24 hours of the possibility of a conflict of interest or occurrence. The immediate head of the state body or the civil servant of the above-mentioned state body must take one of the following measures to prevent and resolve the conflict of interest immediately within 5 days of receipt of information from other sources:

a) in a situation where conflict of interest has arisen or may arise, the duty of the civil servant in the same matter is assigned to another civil servant;

b) the duty of the civil servant to prevent conflicts of interest must be changed".

Secondly, the development of a normative legal document on the Prevention of conflicts of interest in the provision of civil service and provision of civil servants with the use of this document serves to eliminate corruption in this area. Currently, there are standard rules of conduct of employees of Public Administration and local executive authorities, approved by resolution 62 of the Cabinet of Ministers, and the instructions established in this document do not contain specific instructions on how the civil servant will behave in a state of conflict of interest. However, the instructions of the Federal Ministry of internal affairs of Germany for the Prevention of corruption in 2004 year are already in force, and this document will be applied to all state bodies and organizations. Two documents have been attached to this directive, one is the code of Conduct for the fight against corruption, the other is the statute for the Prevention of corruption for employees of the Supervisory Authority and heads of state bodies [4]. This document gives clear and systematized explanations to civil servants on prevention of corruption, including prevention of conflicts of interest.

Therefore, we must introduce into our legislation the legal framework for the declaration of the conflict of interests, property and incomes of civil servants. That is, we will interpret the development of the law "on the declaration of income, property and conflict of interest of civil servants". This practice is also reflected in the legislation of the state of Moldova, and on June 7, 2016 the law "on declaration of the conflict of income, property and interests of civil servants" was adopted. This law provides for the declaration of property belonging not only to civil servants themselves, but also to their parents,

spouses and children, including property belonging to members of the family acquired from childhood and business entities [5]. That is, the declaration of the property and assets of civil servants serves to determine the circumstances in which the conflict of interests may arise.

Conclusion

According to the above analysis, it is possible to conclude that the norms for the Prevention of conflicts of interest in the Republic of Uzbekistan are not fully developed, as well as the practice of the application of Law (Court) in this field does not have a negative impact on the reputation of our country on an international scale, have a negative impact on.

Improvement of legislation to combat these consequences and prevent conflicts of interest in the provision of Public Service is an important step in the fight against corruption of our country.

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LEGAL FRAMEWORK FOR THE REGULATION OF CIVIL SERVICE IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This article discusses proposals and recommendations for the implementation of reforms in the field of public service, the importance of the Constitution in the organization of public service, constitutional principles and their implementation, the relationship between public service and public civil service, the essence of the draft law "On public civil service", the role Constitutions in the creation of public service.

Keywords: civil service, public civil service, constitutional principles, labor contract, service contract, personnel policy.

Introduction

Our country is carrying out large-scale reforms aimed at improving the efficiency of the civil service. In particular, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD-5843 of October 3, 2019 “On measures to radically improve the system of personnel policy and public service in the Republic of Uzbekistan” and the Agency of the Republic of Uzbekistan of Uzbekistan for the development of public service under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. 4472 “On measures to organize the activities of the civil service” laid the organizational and legal foundations for the organization of the civil service. The

program of priority measures to radically improve the personnel policy and the system of civil service in the Republic of Uzbekistan ,the task is to strengthen by law the basic concepts, regulations and guarantees of the civil service in the Republic of Uzbekistan by improving the draft law “On civil service” taking into account the recommendations of foreign experts and the general public. On this basis, the draft Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Civil Service” was developed and submitted for public discussion.

The Main Findings and Results

We all know that for many years the adoption of the Law “On Civil Service” has been a pressing issue. The absence of a single law that defines the general aspects, foundations, types, organizational and legal mechanism of civil service, the procedure for its passage, as well as the legal status of a civil servant, has caused many problems. The bill was revised several times, but was not passed for some reason. Also, the development and adoption of the draft law “On Civil Service” was provided for in the Action Strategy for the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021 and the Concept of Administrative Reforms of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Many scholars define public service in different ways. In particular, legal scholar O.T. Khusanov writes that the state service consists of services in representative, executive, judicial and other state bodies that perform its functions on behalf of the state [10]. In the legislation of foreign countries, the concept of civil service is almost identical, ie the civil service is defined as an activity aimed at ensuring the implementation of the powers of public authorities on a professional basis. An analysis of the legislation of foreign countries and the scientific work of legal scholars shows that the civil service is a part of the civil service. In particular, the legislation of the Republic of Armenia includes the civil service, judicial, diplomatic service, special defense service, national security, police, tax, customs service and a number of

public services. The civil service system of the Kyrgyz Republic includes civil service, military, law enforcement and diplomatic services. The Russian civil service system consists of such types as the state civil, military and law enforcement service. In the Federal Republic of Germany, public civil service is called public service. The division of the civil service into such types means that there are types of civil service regulated by special laws in the legislation of each state. In the legislation of our country, military service, law enforcement services, taxation, customs service and a number of other types of public service are regulated by separate legislation, but there was no legislation regulating public service and the mechanism of its organization.

Public service in the Republic of Uzbekistan is comprehensively regulated by the Constitution and a number of legislative acts. In particular, social relations arising from the organization of the civil service, the transition to the civil service, are regulated by the constitutional, administrative, financial, labor and other legislative spheres.

The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan determines the basis for the organization of the activities of state bodies and officials in the Republic of Uzbekistan, and its implementation is regulated by the legislation on public service. Today, almost all countries of the world take an active position in the legal support of the civil service. The fact that many legislators have laid a constitutional foundation for the establishment of a civil service institution is positively assessed. In particular, such a rule has been introduced in the United States, France and Germany and other countries. In particular, the Constitution of France of 1958 and the Constitution of Germany of 1949 contain such norms [11].

As mentioned above, the basis for the organization of public service is set out in the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The civil service plays an important role in

fulfilling the tasks set by the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. It ensures democratic balance, adherence to the basic principles of the rule of law, and the protection of human rights and freedoms. Reforms in public policy through the civil service will be implemented in a democratic way.

Several articles of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan directly strengthen the basic principles of the organization of the civil service and the transition to the civil service. That is, on the basis of the principles and other provisions of the Constitution on the public service of the Republic of Uzbekistan (ie the people's government (Articles 7-14), human and civil rights and freedoms (Articles 18-52), state structure (Articles 68-75), the judiciary (Articles 106-116), local self-government bodies (Articles 99-105, etc.). We can see that the idea of “the people should serve the people, not government agencies” Set out in the concept of administrative reform is also based on the Constitution.

However, it should be noted that the constitutions of developed foreign countries clearly state that citizens have equal rights when entering public service. In fact, the Italian Constitution of 1947 enshrined equal rights for both sexes when entering the civil service and to hold elected office on equal terms [12].

The provision of the main aspects of the civil service, its organizational structure and functioning is directly related to its principles. The principles of civil service determine not only the functioning of the civil service, but also the entire system of state bodies, important aspects of its organization. The principles of civil service are strict rules reflecting the tasks and functions of government bodies, civil servants in the civil service system. The principles of civil service reveal the general picture of the main directions of activity of civil servants and fix them in the norms of the legal institution of civil service.

Current laws and other regulations adopted on the basis of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan also play an important role in the legal regulation of the civil service. These include the Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan and resolutions of the Oliy Majlis, documents adopted by the President and the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan, decisions made by local governments within their competence, documents adopted by central executive bodies. As noted, the draft law “On Civil Service” is currently being developed and discussed. The draft law also defines the scope of the law and the areas in which it does not apply: the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, deputies of the Legislative Chamber and members of the Senate of the Oliy Majlis, the Central Election Commission of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Ombudsman), Applies to all civil servants of the Republic of Uzbekistan, except for deputies of the Supreme Council of the Republic of Karakalpakstan and representative bodies of state power and judges. The legal status of civil servants serving in law enforcement, defense, security, diplomatic, customs, tax and rescue services is regulated by separate legislation. Military service in the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan and service in law enforcement agencies are a special state service and are regulated by separate legislation.

Indeed, there are separate laws regulating public service in the areas mentioned above. For example, the Law on Internal Affairs, the Law on the State Security Service, the Law on Defense, the Law on General Military Service, the Law on the State Tax Service, the Law on the State Customs Service and other similar special laws.

Conclusion

In short, the bill also provides that a citizen of the Republic of Uzbekistan is a civil servant holding positions included in the state register of civil service positions. The register of civil service positions, that is, a list of civil service positions in hierarchically organized government bodies and organizations, is approved by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Now there is no need to argue who is a civil servant and how to determine his legal status, social guarantees, assessment of his work.

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MONETARY ADVANTAGE AND FIRM'S VALUE: A STUDY OF CASTING, CASTING PRODUCTS AND DRILLING SECTOR FIRMS

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Abstract:

The discussion on capital construction has been appropriate for quite a long time, with conceivable contentions both for and against expanded degrees of monetary influence. The current examination is given to considering the effect on the association's worth with the assistance of different monetary proportions. The entire investigation comprises of examination of the Casting, Casting Products and Drilling Sector Firms. The fundamental concern is to contemplate the connection between capital design and firm worth and whether it is in similarity with the MM approach. The different expressive insights have likewise been considered for exadrilling the effect on the obligation financing design in India for by and large assembling area firms and individual assembling area firms. The monetary writing and observational confirmations are additionally considered for contemplating the targets of the study. The present investigation assessed the connection between capital construction and firm estimation of Casting, Casting Products and Drilling Sector Firms listed on the BSE-500 for long term period and the all out number is 31.To

decide the most useful extents of value and acquired financing to make ideal capital construction is one of the principle undertakings for the interaction of monetary management. The generally discoveries of the examination show that there is a negative relationship existing between return on resources and monetary influence in the event of Casting, Casting Products and Drilling Sector.

Keywords: Capital Structure, Monetary Advantage, Monetary Ratio, Firm's Value.

Introduction

The MM approach which returned path in 1958 and from that point a few examinations have been led in the territory however this being a unique idea required periodical examinations and survey. In this way, over the most recent twenty years, various hypotheses have been proposed to clarify the varieties in the obligation to-value proportions among firms. In request to consider the issues of corporate capital construction, a rundown of writing is portraying the significant speculations that worry the worth importance of capital structure. Even today monetary chiefs specialists actually wrestle with the inquiry in regards to the wellsprings of capital that are being utilized to influence the estimation of the firm. The different monetary proportions are considered to clarify the varieties in the degree of capital construction accordingly addressing the effect on the firm estimation of Casting, Casting Products and Drilling Sector Firms. The study is directed to analyze the example of monetary influence and firm worth. It likewise includes the investigation of capital design of Casting, Casting Products and Drilling Sector Firms and zeroing in on dissecting capital construction with the assistance of monetary coefficients that limits the expense of capital and boosts the firm value. This concentrate additionally gives additional proof of the capital construction hypotheses relating to a non-

industrial nation and inspects the effect of monetary influence on company's presentation in the event of Casting, Casting Products and Drilling Sector Firms. To decide an ideal capital design for Casting, Casting Products and Drilling Sector Firms is a multi-layered issue that has tested and intrigued scholastics and practitioners for quite a while. The current investigation gives understanding into the long existing clash between the unadulterated Modigliani and Miller (MM) hypothesis and the customary hypothesis having an effect of capital design choices on company's worth.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

To investigate the capital construction of chose Casting, Casting Products and Drilling Sector Firms and its effect on the estimation of the firm.

To survey the determinants of capital construction and its impact in choosing the monetary design of Casting, Casting Products and Drilling Sector Firms.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Vung, O.L. (1998) directed examination "Resource qualities and corporate obligation strategy: an experimental test" and closed new administrative speculations of the firm that have developed with regards to office hypothesis. These new perspectives carry more authenticity to the hypothesis of capital construction by tending to organization issues with regards to the firm which is seen as a nexus of agreements among different gatherings, where the legally binding relationship includes motivating force clashes emerging from the quest for personal circumstance. The discoveries recommend that there is a negative connection among development and the degree of influence just as tracked down no deliberate relationship between firm size and complete obligation

proportion. The investigation showed that there is no deliberate relationship between firm size and capital construction.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The current investigation will depend on the information gathered from auxiliary sources. The budget summaries of the organizations under investigation are gathered from different sources, for example, Annual reports of the organizations, CAIE (Center for Audit the Indian Economy) and Capitaline database. This study is spread over a time of a long time from 2002-2010 for the Casting, Casting Products and Drilling Sector Firms., which are recorded on the Bombay Stock Exchange (BSE-500). The factors considered in the current examination are monetary proportions and monetary proportions are considered as an intermediary for the firm worth.

Conclusion

If there should arise an occurrence of Casting, Casting Products and Drilling Sector, the valuation proportions clarified 33 % of the varieties in capital design and the justification the equivalent is that varieties could be clarified by other illustrative components like the reception of credit approaches in Indian banks and the expulsion of limitations on loan fees on loaning and stores expanded the expense of getting and hindered these organizations from acquiring obligation financing. It can likewise be deciphered that the Castings, Casting Products and Drilling Sector firms are having an inordinate monetary influence yet has low profit from capital utilized. The justification this is that the organizations are having the moderately high premium expense using a credit card offices allowed in Indian situation coming about into most reduced revenue cover proportion for example 27.660. The outcomes portray that Casting, Casting Products and Drilling Sector

is considered to have the most noteworthy monetary influence contrasted with other Manufacturing Sector Firms which adversely affects its productivity. The organizations in this area are having negative relationship between's fixed resources turnover proportion and monetary influence which demonstrates that the organizations with low complete resources are fundamentally capital concentrated firms with high added esteem, which need higher measure of obligation to back their resources.

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FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF THE LEGISLATIVE FRAMEWORK
REGULATING THE SPHERE OF HIGHER EDUCATION IN THE REPUBLIC OF
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Abstract: The article analyzes the norms and processes of regulating the sphere of higher education on the basis of analysis of the current legislation in the field of education, the methods of regulating of education is among the fundamental areas that are being analyzed, criticized and reformed in our country

Keywords: Formation and development of the legislative framework regulating the sphere of higher education.

Introduction

Today, the issue of education is among the fundamental areas that are being analyzed, criticized and reformed in our country. The Head of State Sh. M. Mirziyoyev, in his speeches, repeatedly draws public attention to the issue of education. The President notes that “It is clear to all of us that science, education, and upbringing are the cornerstone of development, a force that multiplies the power of the country and the people. Tomorrow, the future of the Motherland is inextricably linked with the education system and the upbringing that our children receive today.”

The Main Findings and Results

Today, the state faces an important task, namely, to stimulate the development of the "Third Renaissance", which is based on the development of education and science in the country. Large-scale reforms are being carried out in the state, which affect both the education system as a whole and the legislative framework of this sphere, which is the basis for the implementation of these reforms. The legislative framework, affecting any aspect of regulation, is the embodiment of the national policy of the state.

The formation and development of the legislative framework regulating the sphere of education of the Republic of Uzbekistan can be divided into several stages, each of which embodies the norm enshrined in the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan in Article 41, according to which "Everyone has the right to education"[1].

Based on the analysis of the development of the legal framework in the field of education, it can be divided into four stages:

The first stage, the legislative framework from 1992 to 1997;

The main normative legal act regulating the sphere of education was the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" of 02.07.1992, in which the main task of education, according to Article 2, was to ensure the protection of the constitutional rights of citizens to education, to determine the principles of relations, competencies and responsibilities of individuals and legal entities in the field of education, legal guarantees for the free development of education in the Republic of Uzbekistan [2].

This law established the basic principle on which the state policy in the field of education was based, as well as the education system, the rights, duties and responsibilities of participants in the educational process. They served as the basis for the development of the field of education.

The second stage, the legislative framework from 1997 to 2017;

This stage begins with the adoption of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Education” of 29.08.1997, which led to the structural restructuring and renewal of the education system.

This Law provided for a fundamental reform of the education system, as a result of which compulsory secondary education was transferred from eleven to twelve years, and on the basis of granting students the right to choose the direction of education, it began to include: compulsory vocational education, as well as secondary special education.

According to the World Bank’s 2014 research on the modernization of the higher education system in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the overall coverage of the higher education system in Uzbekistan fell from 17% in 1991 to 9% in 2011, and was low by regional and international standards as of June 2014 [3].

On the basis of the Law “On Education”, the "National Program for Training Personnel" was adopted, which, in accordance with the Law, assumed the reform of the education system and the implementation of these reforms in several stages:

1. **1997-2001**-assumed the creation of legal, personnel, scientific and methodological, financial and material conditions for the reform of the education system and its development on the basis of maintaining the positive potential of the existing training system.

2. **2001-2017 rr.**- The main focus was on the implementation of the National Program. As a result, there was a complete transition to compulsory general secondary and secondary specialized vocational education, which was supposed to guarantee the provision of professional orientation and training based on practice, as well as the formation of independent thinking and primary skills of work.

The third stage, the legislative framework from 2017-September 2020.;

In connection with the inauguration of Sh.M. Mirziyoyev in December 2016, 2017 was marked by reforms in all spheres of the state. The field of education has undergone significant reforms at all its levels. In his speeches, the Head of State has repeatedly noted the importance of education and education of the country's population: "Today, in the field of education and upbringing, a new time is coming in the lives of our children. Filling it with a new, even deeper meaning and content, achieving national progress depends only on ourselves, on the unity and cohesion of our people, on our tireless, hard work." It is worth noting that in the period from 2017 to September 2020, the Law "On Education" of 1997 and the "National Training Program" were in force. However, even at that time, these normative legal acts did not fully meet the current trends in the development of education in relation to world standards.

In 2018, the Presidential Decree "On measures to radically improve the system of general, secondary and secondary special and vocational education" was issued. According to this decree, compulsory general secondary and secondary special education was reduced to eleven years, both on the basis of general education schools, and academic lyceums and specialized colleges. This reform was carried out in order to provide the labor market with personnel that meet its current trends.

The fourth stage, the Legislative framework from September 2020 to the present;

On September 23, 2020, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" was adopted. This law improved the mechanism for regulating the education system, which required meeting modern requirements, and also framed the reforms previously regulated by Decrees and Resolutions.

In accordance with this law, one of the main types of education in the country is higher education. It provides training of highly qualified personnel in the areas of bachelor's and master's degrees. The country's higher education sector has undergone significant reform. So, it was established that the minimum duration of training on the basis of a bachelor's degree will be a period of three years (previously four), a master's degree – one year (previously two).

Conclusion

Summarizing the above, we can conclude that in the first years of Independence, the Republic of Uzbekistan outlined the right course regarding the trends in the development of education, which we see reflected in the current Law "On Education". The period from 1997 to 2017 was characterized by us from different sides, however, we believe that the reformation of education of that period absolutely did not justify itself, but only led to a number of unresolved problems: the loss of the status of a teacher, a sharp decline in the coverage of graduates with higher education, the loss of the level and quality of education; the results of which the Government of the country is now trying to resolve. Today, the government of the country looks to the future, for this reason, all conditions are created for young people so that a larger stratum of the population is highly educated and competitive and strives for continuous knowledge acquisition.

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CONSTITUTIONAL GUARANTEES OF GENDER EQUALITY

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Abstract: The article analyzes the norms and processes of protection of women's rights and equal opportunities on the basis of analysis of the current legislation in the field of human and civil rights, the methods of protection of the right through the court and by filing a complaint to a high-ranking body (official) over the body that caused the violation of this right.

Keywords: women's rights and equal opportunities protection mechanism.

Everyone is entitled to all rights and freedoms, without distinction of any kind, such as race, color, sex, language, religion, political or other opinion, national or social origin, property, birth or other status.

Introduction

One of the main elements of the structure of the principle of human equality is the achievement of full equality between men and women in all spheres of public life.

Article 46, recognizing the equal rights of men and women, fully reflects in the Constitution the provisions of the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (New York, 18 December 1979) [1].

Article 2 of the Convention obliges States parties to "incorporate the principle of equal rights of men and women in their national constitutions or other relevant legislation, if this has not already been done, and to ensure, by law and other appropriate means, the practical implementation of this principle".

The exercise of the constitutional right enshrined in article 46 is the responsibility of the legislative, executive and judicial branches of government, law enforcement and enforcement agencies.

The Main Findings and Results

The mechanisms for implementing the provisions of article 46 of the Constitution are reflected in national legislation.

Election code [2] of the Republic of Uzbekistan contains provisions providing for the provision of women with at least a 30% quota of the total number of candidates for deputies nominated by a political party, both to local representative bodies and to the Parliament also, in each political party, women's wings have been created, through which participation in the implementation of targeted programs, participation in solving problems of public life is carried out.

In this regard, the Presidential Decree of 2 March 1995 “On measures to enhance the role of women in the State and public construction of the Republic of Uzbekistan” established the post of Deputy Prime Minister. It is established that the chairman of the Women's Committee is appointed to it.

In the field of family relations. Article 2 of the Family Code establishes the equality of women and men in family relations. Thus, the Family Code [3] establishes the conclusion of marriage on the basis of the principle of voluntary participation of men and women (Article 14), equality of personal and property rights of spouses (Article 19), resolution of intra-family issues by mutual consent, priority of family education of children, care for their welfare and development (Article 21), choice of occupation, profession and place of residence (Article 22). The Family Code also establishes the right of everyone to enter into

a prenuptial agreement upon marriage, which defines the property rights and obligations of the spouses in marriage and in the event of its dissolution.

The above-mentioned provisions of this Code correspond to article 16 of the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women, in which States parties ensure, on a basis of equality of men and women: (a) the same rights to marry; (b) the same rights to freely choose a spouse and to marry only with their free and full consent, and others. Also, article 23, paragraphs 2-3, of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights establishes that men and women who have reached the age of marriage are recognized as having the right to marry and the right to found a family.

In the country, women on an equal basis with men have equal rights to receive education, quality medical care, and social protection. The right to a pension with a reduction of the generally established age by one year, i.e. upon reaching the age of fifty-four, is granted to women with at least twenty years of work experience, in cases provided for by the Law "On State Pension Provision for Citizens". The State also ensures equal access of men and women to education and science.

Conclusion

The Labor Code establishes the equality of men and women in the possession and use of labor rights. Defines the concept of discrimination in labor relations as " The establishment of any restrictions or the granting of advantages in the field of labor relations, depending on gender, age, race, nationality, language, social origin, property and official status, attitude to religion, beliefs, membership in public associations, as well as other circumstances not related to the business qualities of employees and the results of their work»

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THEORETICAL AND LEGAL ISSUES OF THE PROSECUTOR'S OFFICE IN THE STATE MECHANISM

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Abstract

The importance of a deep and comprehensive study of the place of the prosecutor's office in the mechanism of our state from the point of view of the separation of powers and their role in the system of checks and balances, in providing a mechanism for the legal protection of the rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of the individual in the difficult socio-economic and political conditions of the reform of society is beyond doubt

Keywords: One of the main guarantees of ensuring the rule of law in the State is the activity of the Prosecutor's Office, which is the only State body whose purpose is solely to oversee the uniform implementation of laws throughout the country.

Introduction:

The proclamation of human rights and freedoms as the highest value does not mean their effective implementation in practice, it requires an effective, really functioning mechanism for their implementation, ensuring and protecting from the standpoint of guarantees of individual rights. Recently, more attention has been paid to this problem in the literature, as evidenced by recent dissertation research,

publications at the level of monographs, collections of scientific papers, journal and scientific articles. It is noteworthy, however, that for various reasons, a number of issues that are in the plane of statics and dynamics of the functioning of the prosecutor's office in the mechanism of separation of powers, ensuring guarantees of individual rights, become the subject of special research.

Findings and results

In the context of the formation of a legal state, the rule of law in public administration is of particular importance, because ensuring accurate and consistent enforcement of the law by officials and state bodies increases the authority of law, implements the mutual responsibility of the state and the individual.

Meanwhile, in the sphere of public administration, it is still not possible to achieve the implementation of the principles of the rule of law, in which violations are most often committed by the executive and administrative bodies in the center and in the field, opposition to the prosecutor's office in eliminating violations of the law, interference in their activities to establish and eliminate violations of the law. As a result, elements of instability are introduced into State and public life, and the rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of citizens are ignored and violated.

One of the main guarantees of ensuring the rule of law in the State is the activity of the Prosecutor's Office, which is the only State body whose purpose is solely to oversee the uniform implementation of laws throughout the country. The Prosecutor's Office is maximally adapted to the performance of this function, as a single centralized system.

The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan declares that State power in the Republic of Uzbekistan is exercised on the basis of the division into legislative, executive and judicial branches (article 11). However, the Basic Law of the State left open the question of the place of the prosecutor's office in the system of state institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Unfortunately, the current Law on the Prosecutor's Office does not fill this gap in full. A functioning conceptual model does not provide a complete and clear answer to both theoretical and many practical questions. This is quite understandable, because the current political life of Uzbekistan is a controversial and extremely complex sphere, where deep and rapid changes are observed: the rejection of old stereotypes and the search for new ones, the rethinking of historical experience and the criticism of classical authorities.

Using the conducted research, accumulated materials, as well as generalizations and analysis of the practical activities of the prosecutor's office and judicial practice, we tried in this study to consider the concept, position and historical development of the prosecutor's supervision bodies, aspects of their interaction with the legislative, executive, judicial bodies of state power, local self-government bodies, as well as to determine the place of the prosecutor's office in the structure of state institutions, and without claiming in any way to be the ultimate truth and full coverage of the issues under consideration, to express our ideas and views, arguing for them.

The degree of development of the problem. The multidimensional nature of the topic of the dissertation research suggested the need to address various branches of knowledge, in particular, works in the field of theory of state and law, philosophy, political science, and various branches of law.

The objectives of this work are to provide a general theoretical study of the place and role of the prosecutor's office in the mechanism of separation of powers, the functions of prosecutor's supervision; in the further development of prosecutor's supervision, the organization of law enforcement activities; development of theoretical provisions that characterize the essence and significance of the correct building of procedural and organizational relations of the prosecutor's office with the legislative, executive, judicial authorities, local self-government bodies, through their constructive interaction, and concretization in this aspect of the most effective, effective ways and means in the context of the rights and powers granted by law to the prosecutor's office; in making scientifically based proposals for improving the legislation regulating the legal status of the prosecutor's office, relations between the prosecutor's office and state authorities, as well as recommendations on the effectiveness of their activities in the state mechanism.

In this study, based on the study and analysis of many works by leading scientists, historical materials, the issues of the emergence and development of prosecutor's offices, their place in the system of separation of powers, as well as the main directions and forms of interaction with state bodies of legislative, executive and judicial power, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, local self-government bodies were considered. The opinions of scientists, politicians, and legal experts on the role and place of the Russian prosecutor's office in the system of state institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan are analyzed with an emphasis on the current stage of development, with the determination of the vector for the future and with an assessment of the current legislation.

On the basis of the conducted research, proposals are formulated to improve the legal framework for the construction and operation of the prosecutor's office, to

consolidate these issues at the legislative level, as well as functional areas, supervisory powers of the prosecutor's office and the mechanism of interaction with state authorities.

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ADVANTAGES OF A DUAL-BASED LEARNING SYSTEM IN VOCATIONAL EDUCATION

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Abstract: This article discusses the advantages of a dual-based learning system in vocational education and conducts research on this topic. The documents of the Second UN International Congress say that the 21st century has brought to mankind an economy and society that is radically different from other eras, and this will inevitably affect the system of technical and vocational education, designed to be a “bridge to the future”. Quality training of qualified specialists. “The innovative direction of the life education paradigm is determined by the combination of two logics - the logic of education (development of citizens' skills) and the logic of economics (optimal use of human resources).

Keywords: “duality,” “single organizational integrity”, vocational education, manufacturing enterprise, Axiological, Ontological, Technological.

Introduction

The most significant aspect of the current stage of development of the vocational education system is the integration processes that reflect changes in the structure of the vocational education system, on the one hand, and the interaction of the vocational education system, on the other. It is the new approach to the vocational education system that will ensure the quality training of future highly qualified specialists.

The advantage of the dual education system is that an important role in the interaction of training and production areas for the training of specialists is the level of practical orientation and, consequently, the employment of graduates.

The introduction of dual education into the educational process of vocational educational institutions is an essential step towards their promising future. This system fully complies with the basic principles of a competency-based approach to vocational education based on modern state educational standards: the unity of theory and practice,

an integrated interdisciplinary approach at the center of the educational process, an orientation towards program skills and knowledge, network forms of education the need to organize the educational process.

Duality means “duality,” “single organizational integrity”. This form of education has emerged as a product of social partnership, which is a mechanism of close cooperation between the state and employers in training highly qualified personnel in accordance with the requirements of the labor market.

The Main Findings and Results

Dual training is vocational education, in which the theoretical part is based on the organization of professional education (30-40% of the study time), and the practical part is in the manufacturing enterprise, in the workplace (60– 70% of the study time). The main meaningful concept of dual education is based on strengthening the practical orientation in teaching through the synthesis of learning and production processes.

Dual education as a methodological characteristic presupposes a coordinated interaction between the spheres of education and production, built on a single methodological basis in the preparation of specialists of a certain profile within the framework of organizationally different forms of education. This interaction is based on the unity of three methodological foundations [1]:

1. **Axiological** (equality of values and goals of training and production);
2. **Ontological** (competency-based approach);
3. **Technological** (organization of educational and professional activities). Principles

of dual education include:

- formation of students’ professional skills and professionally oriented learning technologies in the learning process.
 - creating a unique learning and production environment;
 - formation of integrated modular educational programs of interdisciplinary communication;
 - Combination of theoretical and practical aspects of training future specialists (universality);
 - flexibility and variability of educational technologies to the content of the educational process;
 - developing the specialist’s ability to adapt socially to changing production conditions;
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- Implementation of measures for the training of qualified personnel for the manufacturing enterprise of the educational institution on an equal partnership basis;
- Fulfillment of obligations by the parties;
- creating an open information environment on the joint activities of the manufacturing enterprise and the educational institution.

The goals of the introduction of a two-tier education system can be seen in the following [3]:

1. Improving the model of training qualified specialists, taking into account the real needs of the economy in qualified personnel to increase the investment attractiveness of Uzbekistan;
2. Development of professional standards of professions for business development;
3. Development and modernization of educational programs in accordance with the requirements of professional standards;
4. Change the requirements for the organization and content of educational programs;

Dual education for schoolchildren is a great opportunity to gain knowledge, stability and confidence in the future. This system plays an important role in the adaptation of students to professional and work activities. It also enhances students' sense of professional responsibility and accountability and allows them to easily adapt to the work team. In educational institutions, students have only theoretical ideas about production, and then it is difficult to adapt them to practical work. In this way, collaborative, two-way learning serves as a starting point for future student success.

Conclusion

Dual education is, first of all, highly effective education, training of qualified personnel and their unhindered employment. Secondly, from an economic point of view, this education is self-financing [2].

The advantages of a dual education system are as follows:

1. Practical training of specialists can be carried out not only in manufacturing enterprises, but also in organizations. For this, classes are held in workshops, laboratories, training sites and other premises of the organization.
2. The content and structure of educational programs should fully meet the needs of enterprises and organizations.

3. Establishing a close relationship between the educational institution and the partner organization and the enterprise based on mutual trust will play an important role in their future activities.

4. The fact that students get acquainted with the activities of the enterprise during their studies, work in the enterprise, allows them to quickly adapt to the future work process.

5. Constant theoretical activity in an educational institution serves as the best incentive for studying practical work at an enterprise, but the production process is practically not affected. Collaborative learning develops students' practical skills and improves their level of preparation.

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